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THE EVOLUTION OF THE SOIL FERTILITY IN THE BORȘ TOWN, BIHOR COUNTY, IN THE PERIOD 1987 - 2021

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The town of Borș occupies a total area of 43.4 Km², of which about 35.4 Km² are occupied by agricultural land. In order to study the evolution of soil fertility, analyzes were carried out in the period 2020-2021 on the main trophic indicators of the soil: the pH value, the phosphorus content and the potassium content. The analyzes were performed only at the level of the arable layer. In order to estimate the evolution of the soils, the cartograms drawn up on the entire surface, based on research and laboratory analyzes in 2020, the cartogram of PH values, the cartogram of the state of potassium supply and the cartogram of the state of phosphorus supply were compared with the cartograms of the same indicators, drawn up at the level of 1987.

Keywords: fertility, TEO units, cartograms, supply status, soil units

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INTRODUCTION

The town of Borș is located in the N-W part of Romania, in the western part of Bihor county. Together with the localities: Biharia, Paleu, Cetariu, Ineu, Oșorhei, Sânmartin, Nojorid, Sântandrei, Toboliu and Girișul de Criș, it is part of the metropolitan area of the city of Oradea (Fig. 1, 2)

Figure 1. The town of Borș. Location within Bihor county

Figure 2. The metropolitan area of the city of Oradea

From a geographical point of view, the town of Borș is located in the Borșului Plain, a subdivision of the Crișurilor Plain. The Borșului plain occupies the soil surfaces from the south of Crișul Mic to Crișul Repede, the altitude is 98 - 110m, it extends through the Crișului Repede meadow to Oradea, with altitudes of up to 120m. On the diagonal of the Diocese of Bihor - Santăul Mic the altitude it is 110m, with the character of an intermediate plain, on the valley of Crișului Mic, on the right of Crișului Repede and along the border, the plain has the character of a meadow (fig. 3)

Average annual precipitation is 635 mm. The most frequent winds are from the south, north and southeast.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the terrace areas and the higher areas of the alluvial plain, soil units were formed represented by: Fluvisols, Phaeozems and Eutric Cambisols..

Most of the alluvial plain is occupied by the types of soils: Fluvisols and Phaeozems. In the low-lying areas of the alluvial plain, with water table at critical or subcritical depth, Gleysols and gleyic subtypes of other soil types have formed. In Table 1, soil units from Borş are presented.

Table 2 shows the values of the main chemical soil indicators per soil unit, determined at the level of 2021

Table 1

Soil Unit	Relief	Material of solification	Water level (m)
Haplic phaeozems	terrace	lossoid material	3
Gleyi-luvic phaeozems	terrace	lossoid material	2
Haplic phaeozems	terrace	lossoid material	3
Mollic Cambisols	terrace	lossoid material	2
Fluvi-eutric Cambisols	alluvial plain	material aluvionar.	0,9
Eutric Cambisols	terrace	lossoid material	2
Gleyi-eutric Cambisols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	1,2
Gleyi-mollic Cambisols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	1,2
Gleyic Phaeozems	alluvial plain	alluvial material	1,0
Mollic Gleysols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	0,9
Mollic Fluvisols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	3,0
Gleyi-mollic Fluvisols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	2,0
Gleyic Fluvisols	alluvial plain	alluvial material	1,2
Arenic Fluvisols	meadow	alluvial material	3,0
Eutric Fluvisols	meadow	alluvial material	3,0

Table 2

The values of the main chemical soil indicators per soil unit, determined at the level of 2021

Soil Unit	pH	CaCO ₃ %	Humus %	total N %	mobile P mg/100g soil	mobile K mg/100g soil
Haplic phaeozems	6,0	0,2	2,39	0,11	0,8	6,1
	5,65	0,2	1,99	0,09	1,2	8,6
Gleyi-luvic phaeozems	5,8	0,2	2,38	0,11	7,6	11,8
Haplic phaeozems	7,2	0,4	4,08	0,19	1,00	3,3
Mollic Cambisols	6,5	-	2,40	0,21	5,2	6,5
Fluvi-eutric Cambisols	7,8	-	2,35	0,09	3,6	7,6
Eutric Cambisols	7,3	0,2	3,70	0,21	3,7	8,6
Gleyic Phaeozems	7,00	0,4	2,47	0,13	3,9	11,4
Mollic Gleysols	6,95	0,4	2,78	0,13	6,8	12,4
Mollic Fluvisols	7,4	-	3,67	0,17	14,4	24,8
Gleyi-mollic Fluvisols	7,10	-	4,21	0,21	5,1	10,5
Gleyic Fluvisols	6,10	-	2,64	0,17	1,4	7,2
Arenic Fluvisols	5,9	-	1,14	0,09	1,2	4,7
Eutric Fluvisols	6,4	-	3,72	0,19	1,9	6,1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evolution of soil fertility potential could be established following the creation of maps: Map of pH values, Map of soil supply in K and map of soil supply in P. The maps were drawn up at the level of 1987 and 2021 respectively. The maps drawn up at the level of 1987 were made on the basis of the documentation made available by OSPA Bihor, while the cartograms drawn up for the year 2021 were based on the research, studies and

analyses carried out in the period 2020 - 2021. In Figure 5 and 6, the cartograms of the pH values for the year 1987 are presented comparatively and the year 2021.

Figure 6. Cartograms of pH values for the year 1987

Figure 7. Cartograms of pH values for the year 2021

Figure 8. Cartogram of K supply status (ppm) - 1987

Figure 9. Cartogram of K supply status (ppm) – 2021

Figure 11. Cartogram of P supply status (ppm)- 2021

Figure 10. Cartogram of supply status (ppm) - 1987

CONCLUSIONS

1. Conclusions regarding the evolution of the pH value during the period 1987 – 2021

Compared to 1987, a decrease in areas with acidic soils (pH 5.1 – 5.8) and an increase in areas with slightly acidic soils (pH 5.81 – 6.80) can be noted. The areas occupied by neutral and weakly alkaline soils generally occupy the same areas. The change in pH values over time is mainly due to the ameliorative works carried out by administration of carbonate amendments.

2. Conclusions regarding the evolution of soil potassium supply, in the period 1987 – 2021.

Compared to 1987, at the level of 2021, the areas with well-supplied soils in potassium decrease and the areas of medium-supplied soils increase. At the same time, the appearance of soils poorly supplied with potassium is noted.

Conclusions regarding the evolution of soil phosphorus supply, in the period 1987 – 2021.

At the level of 2022, there is an increase in the areas with well and medium soils supplied with

phosphorus and a decrease in the areas with poorly and very poorly supplied soils. The changes made between 1987 and 2021 regarding the supply of soil with nutrients for plants are mainly due to the application of an undifferentiated agricultural technique on crops and the administration of organic and chemical fertilizers in doses uncorrelated with the specific consumption of plants and the soil's reserve of nutrients.

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RESEARCH ON THE PROTEIN CONTENT OF SOME GRAIN SORGHUM HYBRIDS GROWN IN INAND, BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study analyses the protein content of some grain sorghum hybrids grown in 2019-2020 in Inand, Bihor County, on a soft clay illuvial soil. Sorghum has a similar chemical composition to corn, but with a slightly higher protein level. This cereal can be integrated into the nutrition recipes of most farms' animal breeding. The current genetics in the sorghum field has introduced for cultivation sorghum hybrids with low tannin content, so-called "low tannin" hybrids, the absence of tannins leading to a high digestible energy of the animals.

Keywords sorghum, protein, hybrids
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INTRODUCTION

Sorghum is the species that resists the high temperatures during the summer and achieves high productions even in conditions of water stress, it is a plant with a weak attack of diseases and pests, the most important disease being fusarium, but hybrids with high tolerance created to this disease have been.

The sorghum crop requires less input than the corn crop, sorghum having a well-developed root system with double absorbent pulps compared to those of corn makes very good use of nutrients from the soil, especially mineral nitrogen.

Sorghum is not pretentious compared to the preceding plant, however, cultivation in monoculture leads to the impoverishment of the soil in nutrients.

From an ecological point of view, one hectare of sorghum absorbs annually up to 50 - 55 t/ha/year of CO₂ from the atmosphere, while deciduous forests absorb 16 t/ha/year of CO₂, and the rest of the cereals 3 - 10 t /ha/year. Sorghum is a productive species, undemanding to soil fertility, to drought, it involves minimal expenses for cultivation and processing and does not produce losses, the waste being usable.

Sorghum can be a good alternative to corn crop. This is due to the fact that sorghum is the species that resists the high temperatures

during the summer, the pollen being viable up to 40^o C.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We chose 5 sorghum hybrids for this study, 3 hybrids are produced by the company Euralis Semences France, they are: Armorik, Mousson and Alize and 2 are from the company KWS Germany: Arsenio and Lupus. Two hybrids out of the five have white grain colour: Mousson and Arsenio, Armorik and Lupus have orange grain colour, and Alizee has red grain colour.

For the grain sorghum crop, we prepared the soil similar to the grain corn crop.

After harvesting the preceding plant, we did deep ploughing, at a depth of 22-25 cm, with ploughs equipped with differs and in aggregate with a star harrow.

In the spring, we worked the soil with the disc harrow, followed by the harrow with adjustable tines at a depth of 8-10 cm

The day before sowing, we carried out a work with the combiner, which conferred the quality of the germinal bed, through the better degree of levelling, settlement and shredding of the soil. Fertilization of the experiments was carried out in the spring phase.

The first stage was applied under the plough, 200 kg of complex fertilizers 16.16.16., the second application of fertilizers was executed at sowing, 90 kg of complex fertilizers

20.20.0, and the third application was executed at the mechanical grid 100 kg of nitrogen.

The density at sowing was 300,000 germinating grains/ha at a distance of 70 cm between rows.

For weed control, a pre-emergent weeding was carried out with Dual Gold 980 EC 1.2 l/ha, the seeds being treated with Concept III, a "safener" type substance that protects the sorghum plant at emergence from the action of the anti-grass herbicide Dual Gold 980 EC.

At the 3-leaf stage of the sorghum plant, a post-emergence herbicide with Casper 0.4 kg/ha was carried out.

Harvesting was done with the grain combine at 14% humidity

The biochemical composition of the sorghum grains was determined with the help of the Pfeuffer NIR analyser, with which the protein, starch, fat, and ash contents were determined.

The research was carried out for 2 years, 2019 and 2020.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

After harvesting the sorghum, we took a sample of 2 kg of seed from each hybrid to determine the chemical composition.

Figure 1 shows the graph of the chemical composition of the sorghum hybrids, the hybrid with the highest protein content is Mousson with 12.01% followed by Lupus with a lower content than Mousson with 0.45%, respectively Alizee, Armorik and Arsenio with a protein content of 0.78%, 1.14% and 1.57% lower than Mousson. The first stage was applied under the plough, 200 kg of complex fertilizers 16.16.16., the second application of fertilizers was

Following the chemical analyses of the hybrids grown in 2019 presented in table 1, the protein content of the hybrids is as follows: Mousson 12.01% protein, Lupus with 11.56%, Alizee 11.23%, Armorik 10.87% and Arsenio 10.53%.

Table 1

The chemical composition of sorghum grains in 2019 , Inand, Bihor County

The name of the hybrid	Total protein (%)	Amidon (%)	Fats (%)	Ash (%)
ARMORIK	10.87	72.4	2.2	5.58
MOUSSON	12.01	67.8	2.9	6.72
ALIZEE	11.23	68.3	2.4	6.13
ARSENIO	10.53	70.5	3.1	5.50
LUPUS	11.56	71.3	2.6	6.24

Figure 1 Graph of the chemical composition of sorghum grains, 2019, Inand, Bihor County

Table 2 shows the chemical analyses of the hybrids cultivated in 2020, where the following protein values were recorded: Armorik 11.42%, Mousson 12.12%, Alizee 11.42%, Arsenio 10.46% and Lupus 11.62%.

Figure 2 shows the graph of the chemical composition of sorghum grains. The hybrid that

registered the highest protein is Mousson 12.12% followed by Lupus with a lower protein content of 0.5% respectively Armorik, Alizee and Arsenio with a lower protein content of 0.7% and 1.6%.

Table 2

The chemical composition of sorghum grains in 2020, Inand, Bihor County

The name of the hybrid	Total protein (%)	Amidon (%)	Fats (%)	Ash (%)
ARMORIK	11.42	69.1	2.4	5.81
MOUSSON	12.12	67.2	3.1	6.87
ALIZEE	11.42	69.8	2.6	6.20
ARSENIO	10.46	72.3	3.2	5.72
LUPUS	11.62	71.9	2.9	6.32

Figure 2 **Graph of the chemical composition of sorghum grains, 2020, Inand, Bihor County**

In figure 3 we presented the protein graph of the hybrids recorded in the two years of the study. In 2019, the protein in the chemical composition of Armorik, Mousson, Alizee and Lupus hybrids is lower than that recorded in the 2020 study year, 10.87%,

12.01%, 11.23% and 11.56% compared to 11.42%, 12.12%, 11.42% and 11.62%.

The Arsenio sorghum hybrid is the only one that had higher protein in 2019 compared to 2020, 10.53% compared to 10.46%.

Figure 3 The protein graph of sorghum hybrids registered in 2019 and 2020, Inand, Bihor County

CONCLUSIONS

The hybrid that recorded the highest protein during the 2 years of study was Mousson with a protein of 12.01% in 2019 and 12.12% in 2020.

The hybrid that registered the lowest protein is Arsenio 10.46% in 2019 and 10.53% in 2020

In the 2020 study year, the highest protein content of hybrids was recorded compared to 2019, namely Armorik 11.42% protein in 2020 compared to 10.87% in 2019, Mousson 12.12% protein recorded in 2020 compared to 12.01% recorded in 2019, Alizee 11.42% protein in 2020 compared to 11.23% in 2019, Lupus 11.62% protein in 2020 compared to 11.56% in 2019.

The only sorghum hybrid with a higher protein increase in 2019 compared to 2020 was Arsenio with 10.53% in 2019 compared to 10.48 in 2020.

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RESULTS REGARDING THE QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE TRAITS OF NEW POTATO LINES CREATED UNDER THE EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS OF NIRDPSB BRASOV

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Abstract

A evaluation of 5 potato breeding lines was carried out between 2021-2022 to NIRDPSB Brasov. The lines were analyzed from a morphological point of view, the foliage structure falling between the intermediate type (21-1901/7) and the stem type (19-1876/7), with the tubers showing yellow (1941/8) or red skin (19-1876/7) and a pulp color varying from yellow (21-1895/1) to cream (21-19017/). The productions obtained, in different climatic years, were on average between 39.86 t/ha (21-1901/7) and 21.58 t/ha (Brasovia, control variety). To the analyzes carried out, the general appearance of the tubers ranged between 1.03 for line 1895/1, considered the most attractive and 2.63 for line 1901/7, the least attractive. The lines from the class A/B (1895/1 and 1939/2) present tubers that remained whole after boiled, being able to be easily used in salads (boiled potatoes) and other cold dishes. Class B and B/C lines (1901/7, 1867/7 and 1914/8) have tubers that can partially crumble when cooked, have a gummy or mealy consistency and a medium-fine texture. These tubers lend themselves to a wide range of culinary preparations, from mashed potatoes and soups to baked and fried potatoes. The potato lines are well adapted to climatic and soil conditions and were send for testing in the network of National Institute for Testing and Registration of Varieties.

Keywords: potato, breeding, morphological characters, culinary values, yield.

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INTRODUCTION

Potato breeding has like permanent objective the creation of new varieties with high yield capacity, resistant/tolerance to differerent pests and diseases and with qualitative qualities able to satisfy the processors and customers demands. Obtaining new potato varieties is a challenging task, due to the genetic complexity of the potato as an autotetraploid species and the high heterozygosity of the species (Jansky and Spooner, 2018; Ruiz de Arcaute et al., 2022).

During the selection process, the breeder assesses the breeding material in terms of about 50 qualitative, resistance, or agronomic traits, usually independently inherited. It became increasingly difficult to select recombinants in the offspring of tetraploid parents that meet the requirements of the modern variety (Zimnoch-Guzowska et Flis, 2021). Therefore, typically one variety has been selected from around 100,000 clones (Ross 1986) over 11–12 years. Potato production is estimated to be 359 million tons per year all over the world, cropped on 16.5 million hectares (Eurostat, 2021) so it stands as the third most important food-source crop after wheat and rice, and the most

important non-cereal food crop (Devaux et al., 2020).

It is also necessary to improve some important traits in varieties focused on a commercial objective, such as plant maturity and quality traits. A correlation between late plant maturity and higher tuber yield has been reported (Schönhals et al., 2016), but genotypes with early tuber set and faster tuber bulking can better escape diseases severity (Khan et al., 2013), so earliness and good yield might be needed, for instance, in warm environments.

Takes many years to build up sufficient quantities of seed tubers for commercial production and the risk of contamination by pathogens increases with each multiplication step (Lindhout et al., 2011).

Obtaining varieties by categories of use that respond to changing ecological conditions and that require a minimum of chemical treatments, corresponding to a less aggressive technology towards the environment, is the desire that breeders are trying to fulfill (Hermeziu, 2019). Thus, understanding how environmental factors determine growth patterns and production has been one of the most important issues on potato crop research, which aims to help improve the management of agricultural resources (Villa et al., 2020).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To the NIRDPSB Brasov each breeding cycle starts with a cross between two genotypes, tetraploid varieties, followed by many years of selection and multiplication (Chiru et al., 1992; Hermeziu et al., 2015): seedlings, vegetative populations, descendants, comparative crops (3 years in the network of National Institute for Testing and Registration of Varieties – ISTIS), obtaining the license and registration in the National List of Cultivated Varieties.

The experience was conducted in the fields of the Laboratory of breeding and plant selection, between 2021 - 2022, on a cambic chernozeum soil. In both years the pre-crop was wheat and for fertilizer was used 1000 kg/ha N:P:K:15:15:15+S. The size of the plots was 9 m², the repetition is three-fold, the planting scheme is 75 × 30 cm, having 4 rows with 10 plants each one. Planting was done manually in May 3, 2021 and in April 7, 2022. Treatments for weed control (pre- and post-emergent), for Colorado beetle and for late blight control (alternating systemic products with contact) were applied in accordance with good agricultural practice and specific climatic conditions. No irrigation was used.

The resistance to black wart (*Schynchitrium endobioticum*) was determined at Pojorata Centre Suceava. The starch content and processing quality were determined in the NIRDPSB Brasov laboratory. Also resistance to late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) and viruses

were determined in the fields and laboratories of NIRDPSB Brasov.

Brasovia variety was chosen like control. It's a mid-early variety, with upright growth habit, white flowers and round-oval tubers with yellow skin, white-yellow flesh and a good yield capacity (30-40 t/ha).

The results were processed by the analysis of variation and the significance of the differences was established by the method of multiple comparisons.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The territory where is situated NIRDPSB Brasov is part of the pre-mountain plain of Barsa Country, located in the southeast corner of Transylvania, as a depression surrounded by mountains, crossed from one end to the other by the Bârsa river. The altitude is between 550 and 722 m and the geographical position and the configuration of the relief influence the climate character. The dominant soils are the cambic cernoziomoids (44.9% of the surface) and the relic cambic-glacial cernoziomoids (36.1% of the surface). Bârsa Country is in the transition zone between the Mediterranean and continental climate, being influenced by both types of climates. The weather is determined by the predominance of one or another of these influences (Petricele, 2006; Hermeziu et al., 2020).

Table 1

Air temperature and rainfalls during the experiment

Year	Month						Average
	April	May	June	July	August	September	
2021	6.9	12.3	17.3	21.0	18.5	12.4	16.3
2022	8.3	14.8	19.0	20.6	20.2
MMA	8.5	13.6	16.5	18.1	17.5	13.6	15.9
							Total
2021	39.2	77.0	109.0	71.1	100.8	32.0	389.9
2022	64.8	48.3	62.2	50.1	62.1
MMA	50.0	82.0	96.7	99.8	76.4	52.5	407.4

According to the data taken from Weather Station Ghimbav, in 2021, April was colder than normal and the amount of precipitation that fell was 39.2 mm, which is 10.8 mm lower than the MAA. In May, the air temperature was lower by 1.3°C compared to the multiannual average, and the amount of

precipitation was lower by 4.97 mm compared to the MAA value. June was a rainy month (106,1 mm), with precipitation in the first two decades even daily and with slightly higher temperatures than average (+0.8°C). In July the situation changed completely, registering much higher temperatures (+2.9°C) and a lower level

of precipitation, by 28.7 mm compared to the multiannual average.

In 2022 (Table 1). April start with higher temperature and rainfalls and May was more hot and drier than usually. June was a drier month too, the amount of rainfalls being with 34,5 mm lower compared to the multiannual average (96.7 mm). The months of July (+.5°C more than MAA) and August (2.7°C more than MAA) continued to be warmer than normal and with a low volume of precipitation (less 49.7 mm than MAA in June, respectively less 14.3 mm than MAA in August).

From a morphological point of view, the foliage structure falling between the

intermediate type (21-1901/7) and the stem type (19-1876/7), with the tubers showing yellow (1941/8) or red skin (19 -1876/7), a pulp color varying from yellow (21-1895/1) to cream (21-19017/) and the deep of eyes. The growth habit varied between upright (21-1901/7) to semi-upright (21-1895/1) and the flower color from white (21-1901/7 and 21-1895/1) to purplish pink (1939/2) (Table 2).

Table 2

The morphological characters of the new breeding lines

Breeding line	Foliage structure	Growth habit	Flower color	Tuber classification			
				Shape	Pulp color	Skin color	Deep of eyes
19-1876/7	stem type	upright	light pink	short oval	light yellow	medium red	shallow
1941/8	stem type	upright	light pink	oval	light yellow	yellow	very shallow
21-1901/7	Intermediate type	upright	white	short oval	cream	yellow	very shallow
1939/2	Intermediate type	semi-upright	purplish pink	oval	cream	yellow	shallow
21-1895/1	stem type	semi-upright	white	oval	medium yellow	yellow	shallow

The breeding program developed at the NIRDPSB Brasov imposed the restrictive condition that all varieties to be resistant to potato wart (*Synchytrium endobioticum*), biotype 1, to control this extremely dangerous pathogen. The resistance to wart disease was tested at Pojorata station (Suceava county). According to that tests the presented lines are resistant to potato wart.

From the Table 3 it can be seen that the resistance of the new varieties to viruses is good and very good, similar to the control variety, which enables potato seed production without additional difficulties. The resistance to late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) on foliage and tubers varied between resistant and medium sensitive.

Table 3

Lines resistance evaluation to leaf roll viruses, PVY and late blight (NIRDPSB Brasov fields)

Breeding line	PVY*	Leaf roll virus*	Late blight*	
			to leaf	to tuber
19-1876/7	8	7	8	9
1941/8	6	7	6	8
21-1901/7	6	6	7	9
1939/2	7	7	7	8
21-1895/1	6	6	6	7
Brasovia	7	7	6	7

* 1- sensitive

9 - very resistant

In 2021, with the exception of line 21-1895/1, all the others recorded higher productions than the control variety, with significantly positive values (19-1876/7 and 1941/8) and significantly distinctly positive (21-1901/7/1939/2).

The yield recorded in 2022 exceeded the control variety to lines 19-1876/7, 21-1901/7 and 1939/2 (Table 4). The main causes

of lower yields are the lack of soil water during tuber growth and the uneven distribution of precipitation during the growing season.

Climatic changes characterized by hot summers and very low volume of rainfalls in the second part of the vegetation period negatively influence the formation and accumulation of potato production.

Table 4

Total yield obtained to the new breeding lines(t/ha)

Genotype	Yield (t/ha)		Dif. (t)		Sign.		Mean
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	
19-1876/7	44.10	30.15	20.45	10.65	*	**	37,13
1941/8	43.04	17.19	19.39	-2.31	*	ns	30.11
21-1901/7	45.55	34.17	21.89	14.67	**	***	39.86
1939/2	47.93	30.70	24.27	11.20	**	**	39.32
21-1895/1	29.13	19.33	5.47	-0.17	ns	ns	24.23
Brasovia (control)	23.65	19.50	-	-	-	-	21.58
DL5%	16.24	-	-	6.34	-	-	-
DL1%	21.65	-	-	8.55	-	-	-
DL0,1%	28.20	-	-	11.35	-	-	-

From the average of the two years, it can be seen that all the lines exceeded the control. In 2021, except line 1939/2 all the others lines had higher yield by 20 t/ha. In special climatic conditions (prolonged

drought) from 2022 all lines behaved satisfactorily, line 21-1901/7 having an increase of 14.67 t/ha compared to the control variety.

Table 5

Culinary values of boiled potatoes

Line	Appearance	Taste	Color	Crushing on boiling	Consistency	Mealiness	Moisture	Starch structure	Cooking type
1895/1	1.00	1.38	4.88	1.00	2.75	2.63	2.13	1.50	A/B
1901/7	2.63	2.13	3.88	2.38	2.38	2.88	2.88	2.88	B/C
1867/7	1.00	2.00	5.38	1.25	1.75	3.25	3.00	2.63	B
1939/2	1.13	1.88	4.13	1.13	2.75	2.25	2.00	1.88	A/B
1914/8	1.25	2.00	4.00	1.38	2.00	2.75	2.38	2.25	B

To the analyzes carried out on January 21, 2022, the general appearance of the tubers ranged between 1.03 for line 1895/1, considered the most attractive and 2.63 for line 1901/7, the least attractive. Taste ranged from 1.38 for line 1895/1 rated excellent to 2.63 for line 1901/7 rated good. Crushing on boiling was established according to its behavior. The

tubers of line 1895/1 (1.03) remained whole, and those of line 1901/7 (2.38) crumbled the most among all the analyzed samples. The consistency of the pulp is a measure that expresses the strength of the tubers. The hard ones show a higher resistance (lines 1895/1 and 1939/2 both with a value of 2.75), and the floury ones a weaker resistance (1867/7 with a

value of 1.75). The less mealiness potatoes have a pleasant palatability, while the floury ones are drier and more difficult to swallow. Visually, the less floury potatoes remain whole (line 1895/1 - 2.63), while the floury ones crack very hard (1867/7 - 3.25). Moisture was determined visually by sectioning and ranged from 2.00 at line 1939/2 (considered the wettest) to 3.00 at line 1867/7 (considered the driest). Starch structure was determined by mastication of a potato slice, distinguishing between coarse (line 1901/7 - 2.88) and fine (line 1895/1 - 1.50) tubers. The color ranged from 5.38 (yellow) on line 1867/7 to 3.88 (yellowish) on line 1901/7. The lines from the class A/B (1895/1 and 1939/2) present tubers that remained whole after boiled, being able to be easily used in salads (boiled potatoes) and other cold dishes. Class B and B/C lines (1901/7, 1867/7 and 1914/8) have tubers that can partially crumble when cooked, have a gummy or mealy consistency and a medium-fine texture. These tubers lend themselves to a wide range of culinary preparations, from mashed potatoes and soups to baked and fried potatoes (Table 5).

CONCLUSIONS

The potato lines 1895/1, 1901/7, 1867/7, 1939/2, 1914/8 were bred at the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov. Obtaining them is part of the objective of the potato breeding program, represented by the creation of early varieties, resistant to water stress, immune to wart disease and with high resistance to pests and diseases. Regarding the yield, all the varieties provided good and very good productions (39,86 - 24,23 t/ha) in difficult climatic years.

It should be emphasized once again that the variety represents the most important technological factor. A defense for certified seed from Romanian varieties takes into account their superior adaptability to climate and soil conditions and therefore the possibility of obtaining productions of 40-60 t/ha, constant over time and depending on the area.

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ECOLOGICAL AND TAXONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE MOTHS (INSECTA, LEPIDOPTERA) IN THE TINCA AREA (BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA) DURING 2018-2022

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this work are presented taxonomical and ecological data about the moths (Insecta, Lepidoptera) from Tinca area, Bihor county during 2018 -2022. There were identified 277 species belonging to 27 families and 215 genera, 1 subspecies and 1 form, the dominant ones being those belonging to Noctuidae, Geometridae, Erebidae families. *Ephestia woodiella* Rich. & Thom and *Anarsia innoxia* Greg. & Kars. are mentioned for the first time in the Bihor county. In terms of categories and degrees of danger (IUCN, 2000 -2001), the following have been identified: 9 vulnerable species, 30 near threatened species, 1 endangered species, 1 data deficient species, 3 critical endangered species. There were obtained ecological data of these species, unknown in the scientific literature. *Proserpinus proserpina* Pall is a Natura 2000 protected species.

Keywords: nocturnal, lepidoptera, Tinca, Bihor.

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INTRODUCTION

The Tinca area is located in the south-western part of Bihor county, belonging to the historical province of Crişana, in the north-western part of Romania. The climate is temperate – continental, the average altitude is 110 m. The hydrographical network is various: the Crişul Negru river, some lakes. The vegetation belongs to the oak stage having a predominant central – European origin (BERINDEI et al., 1972). The disappearance of species or the diminution of their population, the emergence of new species, either accidental in territory, insufficient faunal data, observing some ecological aspects not published in the scientific literature are just a few reasons that make it absolutely necessary to publish the faunal data observed in nature. Data about the fauna of nocturnal lepidoptera from Tinca area were published by different authors (PEIU, 1971; ILIE et al., 2018; ILIE, 2019; ILIE et al., 2019; 2020a, 2020 b; 2021a, 2021 b).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The researches were carried out in the period 2018 – 2022 in different ecosystems in the area and the surroundings of Tinca. The insects were collected with the entomological net both day and night (at light traps) or by hand (the caterpillars). For the identification of the species were used different sources (Rakosy, 1996; Szekely, 2010; pyrgus.de; lepiforum.de; en.m.wikipedia.org). The classification of the species according to the degree of endangerment was done according to a single source (Rakosy, 2003) and the systematic classification of the species was done according to fauna-eu.org; lepiforum.de.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During the period 2018 – 2022, the following species were identified:

Sphingidae Family Latreille, 1802

Agrius convolvuli (Linnaeus, 1758)

Acherontia atropos (Linnaeus, 1758) – VU

Macroglossum stellatarum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Hyles euphorbiae (Linnaeus, 1758) – NT

Deilephila porcellus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Proserpinus proserpina (Pallas, 1772) - VU

Adelidae Family Bruant, 1851

Cauchas fibulella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Nemophora fasciella (Fabricius, 1775)

Adela reamurella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Adela croesella (Scopoli, 1763)

Coleophoridae Family Bruand, 1850

Coleophora anatipenella (Hubner, 1796)

Tineidae Family Latreille, 1810

Euplocamus anthracinalis (Scopoli, 1763)

Triaxomera parasitella (Hubner, 1796)

Monopis monachella (Hubner, 1796)

Zygaenidae Family, Latreille, 1809

Jordanita globulariae, (Hubner, 1793)

Jordanita notata (Zeller, 1847)

Pterophoridae Family Zeller, 1841

Stenoptilia pterodactyla (Linnaeus, 1761)

Pterophorus pentadactyla (Linnaeus, 1758)

Emmelina argoteles (Meyrick, 1922)

Emmelina monodactyla (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cnaemidophorus rhododactyla (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Crambidae Family Latreille, 1810

Pyrausta purpuralis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Pyrausta despicata (Scopoli, 1763)

Pyrausta sanguinalis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Pyrausta aurata (Scopoli, 1763)

Patania ruralis (Scopoli, 1763)

Chrysocrambus craterellus (Scopoli, 1763)

Chrysocrambus linetella (Fabricius, 1781)

Diasemia reticularis (Linnaeus, 1761)

Cydalima perspectalis (Walker, 1859)

Anania hortulata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Anania coronata (Hufnagel, 1767)

Anania verbascalis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Anania fuscalis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Dolicharthria punctalis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Agriphila selasella (Linnaeus, 1767)

Agriphila brioniellus (Zerny, 1914)

Agriphila inquinatella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Agriphila straminella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Agriphila geniculea (Haworth, 1811)

Agriphila tristella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Catoptria falsella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Catoptria pinella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Ostrinia nubilalis (Hubner, 1796)

Sitochroa palealis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Sitochroa verticalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Pediasia contaminella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Uresiphita gilvata (Fabricius, 1794)

Loxostege sticticalis (Linnaeus, 1761)

Udea ferrugalis (Hubner, 1796)

Scoparia subfusca (Haworth, 1811)

Thysanotia chrysonuchella (Scopoli, 1763)

Eudonia lacustrata (Panzer, 1804)

Eudonia mercurella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Crambus lathoniellus (Zincken, 1817)

Chrysoteuchia culmella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Calamotropha paludella (Hubner, 1824)

Cataclysta lemnata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Paratalanta pandalis (Hubner, 1825)

Aporodes floralis (Hubner, 1889)

Nomophila noctuella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Platytes cerusella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Gracillariidae Family Stainton, 1854

Parectopa robiniella (Gustafsson, 1973)

Gelechiidae Family Stainton, 1854

Carpatolechia fugitivella (Zeller, 1839)

Sitotroga cerealella (Olivier, 1789)

Acompsia cinerella (Clerck, 1759)

Stomopteryx hungaricella (Gozmany, 1957)

Neofaculta ericetella (Geyer, 1832)

Helcystogramma rufescens (Haworth, 1828)

Nothris lemnisellus (Zeller, 1839)

Anarsia innoxia (Gegersen & Karsholt, 2017)

Saturniidae Family Boisduval, 1837

Saturnia pavonia (Linnaeus, 1758) - VU

Saturnia pyri (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - VU

Notodontidae Family Stephens, 1829

Ptilodon capucina (Linnaeus, 1758)

Nolidae Family Bruand, 1847

Earias clorana (Linnaeus, 1761)

Nola aerugula (Hubner, 1793) – NT
Meganola albula (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Nycteola siculana (Fuchs, 1899) – VU

Tortricidae Family Latreille, 1803

Syricoris lacunana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Celypha striana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Celypha rufana (Scopoli, 1763)

Acleris variegana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Philedone gerningana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Notocelia udmanniana (Linnaeus, 1758)

Agapeta zoegana (Linnaeus, 1767)

Agapeta hamana (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cydia pomonella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cydia amplana (Hubner, 1799)

Aethes triangulana (Treitschke, 1835)

Hedya pruniana (Hubner, 1799)

Cnephasia asseclana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Epiblema foenella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Eudemis profundana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Eucosma obumbratana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

Grapholita funebrana (Treitschke, 1835)

Pandemis heparana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Phalonidia contractana (Zeller, 1847)

Lasiocampidae Family Harris, 1841

Macrothylacia rubi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Malacosoma neustria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Poecilocampa populi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Eriogaster rimicola (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - VU

Lasiocampa trifolii (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - EN

Cnephasia asseclana (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Hedya pruniana (Hubner, 1799)

Syndemis musculana (Hubner, 1799)

Pyralidae Family Latreille, 1809

Oncocera semirubella (Scopoli, 1763)

Hypsopygia costalis (Fabricius, 1775)

Eurhodope rosella (Scopoli, 1763)

Pyralis farinalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Aglossa caprealis (Hubner, 1809)
Aglossa pinguinalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Endotricha flammealis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Emateudes punctella (Treitschke, 1833)

Plodia interpunctella (Hubner, 1813)

Episcythrastis tetricella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Phycita roborella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Homoeosoma inustella (Ragonot, 1884)

Homoeosoma nebulella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Synaphe punctalis (Fabricius, 1775)

Phycitodes albatella (RAGONOT, 1887)

Phycitodes binaevella (Hubner, 1813)

Acrobasis consociella (Hubner, 1813)

Acrobasis advenella (Zincken, 1818)

Ephestia woodiella (Richards & Thomson, 1932)

Drepanidae Family Meyrick, 1809

Thyatira batis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Clix glaucata (Scopoli, 1763)

Watsonalla binaria (Hufnagel, 1767)

Elachistidae Family Bruand, 1851

Agonopterix arenella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Lecithoceridae Family Le Marchand, 1947

Lecithocera nigra Duponchel, 1836

Scythrididae Family Rebel, 1901

Scythris sinensis (Felder & Rogenhofer, 1875)

Scythris scopolella (Linnaeus, 1767)

Hepialidae Family Stephens, 1829

Triodia sylvina (Linnaeus, 1761)

Plutellidae Family Guenee, 1845

Plutella xylostella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Micropterigidae Family Herrich -

Schaffer, 1885

Micropterix calthella (Linnaeus, 1761)

Oecophoridae Family Bruand, 1851

Esperia oliviella (Fabricius, 1794)

Chimabachidae Family Heinemann, 1870

Diurnea fagella (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Erebidae Family Leach, 1815

Prodostis stolidia (Fabricius, 1775)

Euplagia quadripunctaria (Poda, 1761)

Phragmatobia fuliginosa (Linnaeus, 1758)

Schrankia costaestrigalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
 - NT
Hyphenodes humidalis (Doubleday, 1850) -
 DD
Diaphora mendica (Clerck, 1759)
Polypogon tentacularia (Linnaeus, 1758)
Spilosoma lubricipeda (Linnaeus, 1758)
Eilema caniola (Hubner, 1808) - NT
Leucoma salicis (Linnaeus, 1758) - NT
Lygephila cracca (Denis & Schiffermuller,
 1775)
Scoliopteryx libatrix (Linnaeus, 1758)
Catephia alchymista (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Laspeyria flexula (Denis & Schiffermuller,
 1775)
Hypena rostralis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Hypena proboscidalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Diacrisia sannio (Linnaeus, 1758)
Orgyia antiqua (Linnaeus, 1758)
Euproctis similis (Fussli, 1775)
Catocala hymenaea (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Catocala sponsa (Linnaeus, 1758) - NT
Catocala conversa (Esper, 1787) - CR
Catocala promissa (Denis & Schiffermuller,
 1775) - NT
Catocala elocata (Esper, 1787) - NT
Paracolax tristalis (Fabricius, 1794)
Chelis maculosa (Gerning, 1780) - VU
Euclidia glyphica (Linnaeus, 1758)
Hyphantria cunea (Drury, 1773)
Amata phegea (Linnaeus, 1758)
Atolmis rubricollis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Dysgonia algira (Linnaeus, 1767) - NT
Herminia tarsicrinalis (Knoch, 1782) - NT
Lymantria dispar (Linnaeus, 1758)

Geometridae Family Deach, 1815

Epione rependaria (Hufnagel, 1767) - NT
Ennomos quercinaria (Hufnagel, 1767) -
 NT
Selenia dentaria (Fabricius, 1775) - NT
Orthostixis cribraria (Hubner, 1799) - VU
Aplasta ononaria (Hubner, 1823) - VU
Xanthorhoe fluctuata (Linnaeus, 1758) &
 Schiffermuller, 1775)
Xanthorhoe montanata (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775)
Lythria purpuraria (Linnaeus, 1758)
Cyclophora annularia (Fabricius, 1775) -
 NT
Cyclophora linearia (Hubner, 1799)
Cyclophora suppunctaria (Zeller, 1847) -
 CR
Timandra comae (Schmidt, 1931)

Scopula immorata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Scopula rubiginata (Hufnagel, 1767)
Scopula floslactata (Haworth, 1809) - NT
Scopula virgulata (Denis & Schiffermuller,
 1775)
Scopula ornata (Scopoli, 1763)
Scopula caricaria (Reutti, 1853) - NT
Scopula subpunctaria (Herrich - Schaffer,
 1847) - NT
Scopula marginepunctata (Goeze, 1781)
Ematurga atomaria (Linnaeus, 1758)
Idaea seriata (Schrank, 1802)
Idaea muricata (Hufnagel, 1767)
Idaea aversata (Linnaeus, 1758) -
 remutata form and typical form
Idaea politaria (Hubner, 1799)
Idaea degeneraria (Hubner, 1799)
Idaea rusticata (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) -
 NT
Operophtera brumata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Lycia hirtaria (Clerck, 1759) - NT
Hipoxistis pluviana (Fabricius, 1787) - NT
Ectropis crepuscularia (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775)
Peribatodes rhomboidaria (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775)
Cosmorhoe ocellata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Chiasmia clathrata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Costaconvexa polygrammata
 (Borkhausen, 1794) - NT
Colostygia pectinataria (Knoch, 1781)
Chlorissa cloraria (Hubner, 1813) - NT
Chlorissa viridata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Isturgia arenacearia (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Ligdia adustata (Denis & Schiffermuller,
 1775)
Penthophtera morio (Linnaeus, 1767) - NT
Hypomecis punctinalis (Scopoli, 1763)
Synopsia sociaria (Hubner, 1799)
Macaria alternata (Denis &
 Schiffermuller, 1775)
Camptogramma bilineata (Linnaeus,
 1758)
Opisthograptis luteolata (Linnaeus, 1758)
 - NT

Noctuidae Family Latreille, 1809

Helicoverpa armigera (Hubner, 1808)
Melanchnra persicariae (Linnaeus, 1761)
Leucapamea ophiogramma (Esper, 1794)
Deltote deceptaria (Scopoli, 1763)
Deltote bankiana (Fabricius, 1775)
Macdunnoughia confusa (Stephens, 1850)
Noctua pronuba (Linnaeus, 1758)
Noctua comes (Hubner, 1831)

Brachionycha nubeculosa (Esper, 1785)
Acronicta rumicis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Acronicta tridens (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Euxoa aquilina (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Ochropleura plecta (Linnaeus, 1761)
Ponometia candefacta (Hubner, 1831)
Eucarta virgo (Treitschke, 1835)
Autographa gamma (Linnaeus, 1758)
Apamea monoglypha (Hufnagel, 1766)
Elaphria venustula (Hubner, 1790)
Lacanobia oleracea (Linnaeus, 1758)
Lacanobia suasa (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Emelia trabealis (Scopoli, 1763)
Cosmia affinis (Linnaeus, 1767)
Trachea atriplicis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Spaelotis ravidata (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Conistra rubiginosa (Scopoli, 1763)
Conistra erythrocephala (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Phlogophora meticulosa (Linnaeus, 1758)
Aedia leucomelas (Linnaeus, 1758)
Mythimna albipuncta (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Mythimna ferrago (Fabricius, 1787) - subsp. argyristis
Hoplodrina blanda (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Hoplodina ambigua (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Agrotis segetum (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Agrotis cinerea (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Agrotis ipsilon (Hufnagel, 1766)
Agrotis clavis (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - NT
Agrotis exclamationis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Agrotis puta (Hubner, 1803)
Eupsilia transversa (Hufnagel, 1766)
Valeria oleagina (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Actinotia polyodon (Linnaeus, 1761)
Oligia strigilis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Oligia fasciuncula (Haworth, 1809) - VU
Oligia latruncula (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Tyta luctuosa (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Hecatera dysodea (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Cerastis rubricosa (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)
Acontia trabealis (Scopoli, 1763)
Hadula trifolii (Hufnagel, 1766)

Mesogona oxalina (Hubner, 1803)
Peridroma saucia (Hubner, 1803)
Caradrina clavipalpis (Scopoli, 1763)
Caradrina morpheus (Hufnagel, 1766)
Xilena vetusta (Hubner, 1813)
Talpothila matura (Hufnagel, 1766)
Anarta trifolii (Hufnagel, 1766)
Dysgonia algira (Linnaeus, 1767) - NT
Cryphia algae (Fabricius, 1775)
Amphipyra berbera (Rungs, 1949)
Polyphaenis sericata (Esper, 1787) - CR
Mamestra brassicae (Linnaeus, 1758)
Hadena capsincola (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)

Legend - VU - vulnerable species; NT - near threatened species; EN - endangered species; DD- data deficient species; CR - critical endangered species.

There were identified 277 species belonging to 27 families and 215 genera, 1 subspecies and 1 form, the dominant ones being those belonging to Noctuidae - 62 species (22.38 %), Geometridae - 46 species (16.60 %), Crambidae - 41 species (14.80 %), Erebidae - 33 species (11.91 %) families, followed by other families: Tortricidae, Pyralidae - 19 species (6.85 %), Lasiocampidae, Gelechiidae - 8 species (2.88 %), Sphingidae - 6 species (2.16 %), Pterophoridae - 5 species (1.80%), Nolidae, Adelidae - 4 species (1.44 %), Tineidae, Drepanidae - 3 species (1.08 %), Zygaenidae, Saturniidae, Scythrididae - 2 species (0.72 %), Oecophoridae, Gracillariidae, Hepialidae, Micropterigidae, Elachistidae, Coleophoridae, Chimabachidae, Lecithoceridae, Notodontidae, Plutellidae - 1 species (0.36 %).

Ecological observations: - *Operophtera brumata* L. - one female specimen, December 13-15, 2018, t = 0-3^o C (day), t = -6^o C (night). In this species, the adults appear in nature in September - October, and the females are apt and climb to the canopy of the trees for laying eggs, the wintering takes place in the egg stage. So, the existence of the female on this date and on the ground is surprising!

- *Hyles euphorbiae* L. - one specimen, September 8, 2018; October 12, 2018; November 7, 2018, t = 20^o C; November 13, 2018, t = 17^o C. According to literature (SZEKELY, 2010) in this period the species must be in the stage of pupa, the flight period is August - first week of September (the second generation), therefore the period of flight was extended with two months.

- *Polygogon tentacularia* L. - one male specimen, February 15, 2018, t = 5^o C; one female specimen, November 22, 2018, t = 5^o C; three male specimens, December 8, 2018, t = 4^o C; November 23, 2019, t = 16^o C. According to literature (RAKOSY, 1996), the flight period is May 15 – July 15.

- *Chelis maculosa* Gern. - one male specimen, April 2, 2019, t = 21^o C, presence earlier with one month than normally (SZEKELY, 2010).

- *Proserpinus proserpina* Pall. - one female specimen, October 22, 2019. According to the literature (Szekely, 2010), the species was supposed to be at this time in the pupae stage (nymph) by April next year. In this case, it is either an additional generation or the usual flight period (May - June) has been extended by four months due to the very high temperatures from July to October. Also, the literature (SZEKELY, 2010) states that the species flies at dusk of the sun! This observation shows that there may be exceptions, the female specimen was collected flying at noon (11.40 AM); one female specimen, Tinca, April 1-2, 2020, t = 9 – 11^o C (the flight period is earlier with one month).

- *Stenoptilia pterodactyla* L. - one specimen, January 7, 2020, t = 7^o C (very surprising appearance at this date!); one specimen, April 17, 2020 (early appearance, because the high temperatures, the flight period is: the end of June – August).

- *Macroglossum stellatarum* L. - one specimen, February 28, 2020, t = 8^o C (very strange appearance, the flight period became in the second half of May (SZEKELY, 2010); one specimen, Tinca, April 12, t = 12^o C; one specimen, April 10, 12, t = 20^o C; one specimen, Tinca, March 25,26, 2022, t = 17^o C; one specimen, Tinca, September 30, 2020. Note its presence during a torrential rain visiting the flowers, feeding on their pollen. This fact is not observed in diurnal butterflies, perhaps very fast flight does not affect the scales of the wings during the rain!; one specimen flying during the drizzle to look for flower pollen, Tinca, October 2, 2020; one specimen flying, Tinca, March 20,

CONCLUSIONS

During 2018 – 2022, in the Tinca area there were recorded 277 moth species, belonging to 27 families and 215 genera, 1 subspecies and 1 form. Data were obtained on the feeding behavior of *Macroglossum*

2022, t = 1^o C. The flight of the species at this temperature is surprising! According to the literature (Szekely, 2010), this species has two annual flight periods: mid-May – mid-June and August-November. The observations made in the Tinca area in the period 2020-2022 highlighted the existence of the third flight period: April – May. *Oenothera speciosa* Nutt through the internal structural peculiarities of its flowers works as a real trap, sometimes deadly from *Macroglossum stellatarum* L.- one specimen, Tinca, August 6, 2022. This plant is native to North America and was introduced to Europe for decorative purposes. If this plant is cultivated on ever-larger areas, it will have a dramatic impact on the populations of this lepidoptera (ZLATKOV et al. ,2018). - *Diacrisia sannio* L.- one specimen, Tinca, April 23, 2022; May 22, 2022. According to the literature (pyrgus.de) the flight period is June – July and the second generation in August. Other scientific source (lepiforum.de) mentions the flight period during May – July. In these cases, the species appeared earlier due to high temperatures in April and May. - *Platytes cerusella* Den. & Schiff. - one specimen, Tinca, September 1,2022. According to the literature (lepiforum.de; ukmoths.org.uk/species/platytes-cerusella), the adult moths fly in May – July. The presence in this period can be explained either by the existence of an additional annual generation or by the extension of the flight period of the first generation..Both of these likely situations are certainly duo to climate changes that have occurred in recent years.

In terms of categories and degrees of danger (IUCN, 2000 -2001), the following have been identified: 9 vulnerable species, 30 near threatened species, 1 endangered species, 1 data deficient species, 2 critical endangered species.

Proserpinus proserpina Pall is also a Natura 2000 protected species. *Ephestia woodiella* Rich. & Thom and *Anarsia inoxiella* Greg. & Kars. are mentioned for the first time in the Bihor county and probably in the Romanian fauna.

stellatarum L., in unfavorable weather conditions, unpublished in the scientific literature. This species has three annual generations in the Tinca area. *Oenothera speciosa* Nutt is a real deadly trap for *Macroglossum stellatarum* L. In some species premature flights, prolongation of the flight

period or even flight at very low temperatures have been observed. In terms of categories and degrees of danger (IUCN 2000 – 2001), 33 species have been identified. *Proserpinus proserpina* Pall is a Natura 2000 protected species. *Ephestia woodiella* Rich. & Thom and *Anarsia innoxia* Greg. & Kars. are mentioned for the first time in the Bihor county.

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Moths from the Tinca area (photos by ILIE A.L.)

Macroglossum stellatarum L on *Oenothera speciosa* Nutt. flower

Acronicta rumicis L – larva

Hyles euphorbiae L.

Actinotia polyodon L.

Ephestia woodiella Rich. & Thom.

Anarsia innoxia Greg. & Kars.

ANALYSIS OF THE CONSUMPTION OF AGROO-FOOD PRODUCTS IN THE CURRENT PERIOD

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Specialists in the field say that Romania is a country with a very high agricultural potential. Due to the soil and climate conditions, a variety of crops can be cultivated in our country and, consequently, the number of animal species to be reared can be increased to allow the supply of food consumption for the population. The authors of the present paper analyse food consumption availability in Romania so that the food security of the population can be ensured, as well as the possibilities of Romania to ensure usable food resources from its own production. In order to carry out this analysis, the authors resorted to data collection and processing, to mathematical and statistical calculation, and to graphic interpretation. The results of the analysis highlight, unfortunately, that, for over three decades, Romania has been importing most of the basic products – meat, fruits, vegetables – because of the inefficiency of the agri-food agents and of the inability to function of the agri-food chains under market economy conditions. The high share of imports of food shows a lack of concentration of the supply of agri-food products and the inability of Romanian producers to be competitive on both domestic and international markets.

Keywords: agricultural potential, food security, production, import, export

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INTRODUCTION

In the European Union (EU), the structure of the agricultural land fund in the second decade of the 3rd Millennium shows that six countries – France and Spain with over 16% each, followed by Germany, United Kingdom, and Poland with over 9% each, and Italy and Romania with over 8% each – had the largest shares of agricultural land (Mateoc-Sîrb et al., 2013; Gavrilescu, 2019).

These countries concentrated about 78% of the agricultural area and about 71% of the arable area of the EU. According to the provisional results of the General Agricultural Census 2020 (GAC 2020) in Romania, the

agricultural area used was 12,763 thousand ha. The structure of the land fund of Romania highlights the large share of the arable land area of over 67.2% – 8,571.00 ha – (more than in 2010) of the agricultural area, which ranks Romania first in the hierarchy in terms of agricultural potential (Table 1, Figure 1). Unfortunately, though Romania has favourable conditions for cultivating a wide range of crops, GAC 2020 shows that the main crops are maize, wheat, sunflower, and rapeseed, representing 73.1% of the cultivated arable land, compared to about 67.7% in 2010. (National Institute of Statistics, 2022)

Table 1

Structure of the land fund in Romania		
Specification	2010 (thousand ha)	2020 (thousand ha)
Arable land including greenhouses and solaria	8,306	8,571
Grasslands and hayfields	4,506	3,724
Permanent crops	312	344
Family gardens	182	124

Total	13,306	12,763
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Source: General Agricultural Census (RGA), 2020

Figure 1. Structure of the Land Fund of Romania (ha)

Both rural economy, as a whole, and agri-food economy, as an important element of rural economy, have different structures in Romania compared to the European Union. (Mateoc-Sîrb et al., 2022; Venig et al 2022)

Romanian rural economy is mainly agricultural (about two thirds) or agri-food (more than three quarters). (Eurostat, 2019). In the EU, the processing of agricultural raw materials in food (raw value bearers) shares more than half of the agri-food economy while, in our country, the production of agricultural raw materials (agricultural economy) has a much higher share of the value total of the final agri-food production (over 75%). (Gavrilescu, 2018; Mateoc-Sîrb et al., 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

At national level, agriculture is one of the most important branches of the Romanian economy (Gavrilescu et al., 2017). In carrying out this analysis, the authors started from the premise that, within the economy of each country, agriculture holds an important position regardless of the degree of agricultural development due to natural and human resources, to the contribution to the creation of the gross domestic product, to the gross added value, and to the contribution to domestic and foreign trade.

The contribution of agriculture to economic development can be determined by an analysis of the multiple functions it performs, as well as by its contribution to social balance

and stability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Agriculture should **ensure the food security of the population**, that is, permanent access to a sufficient, acceptable quality food for all citizens, to lead an active and healthy life.

Food security is determined through the prism of three elements: *food availability* – expressing the daily needs of food from a quantitative, qualitative, and assortment point of view (about 2,700 kcal/inhabitant/day and minimum 55 g of proteins of which half of animal origin – according to FAO recommendations); *security of food supply* – implying the existence of a certain volume of products, of the stocks (reserves) of food from one's own production or their redistribution through exchanges between countries; *economic accessibility* – requiring the acquisition by the population of the necessary food at affordable prices.

Each state needs to ensure the food security of its citizens because the issue of access to food for the population contributes to peace and social peace, stability and prosperity. Currently, food security, population's access to basic agricultural and high-quality agri-food products are major issues and concerns of the states of the world – mainly of developing or underdeveloped countries.

Specialists in the field consider that access to food is a problem that can be an

important factor leading to instability worldwide.

Another problem is **food safety**. According to World Health Organisation data, annually over two million people (of which a significant share is represented by children) die because of diseases transmitted through food. Food can contain viruses, bacteria, parasites or chemicals that cause over 200 diseases, from enterocolitis to cancer. Diseases transmitted through food influence national economies and burden the health systems, thus affecting the socio-economic development of the states.

In Romania, food safety is regulated by Law 150/2004 on food safety. This law represents the basis for ensuring a high level of

protection of people's health and consumers' interests.

The analysis of the average annual consumption per inhabitant in the main products, in Romania, has highlighted a change in consumer behaviour of during the analysed period (2014-2020). There are some products in which consumption has decreased: cereals and cereal products, potatoes and eggs; in some products, consumption has increased: vegetables and vegetable products, fruit and fruit products, sugar and sugar products, milk and dairy products, fish and fish products, and meat, meat products and edible offal (Table 2, Figures 2 and 3).

Table 2

Evolution of average annual consumption per inhabitant in the main products

Specification	UM	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
kg/locuitor								
Products of plant origin								
1. Cereals and cereal products <i>in grain equivalent</i>	kg	207	211.2	208.4	208.2	205.4	204.2	204.4
<i>in flour equivalent</i>	kg	156.4	159.8	157.6	157.3	155.1	154.3	154.6
2. Potatoes	kg	100.8	98.3	95.5	96.6	95.5	92.2	93.4
3. Vegetables and vegetable products (in equivalent fresh vegetables), legumes, grains and melons	kg	182.9	182.6	178.3	187.8	202.1	196.6	194.4
- vegetables and vegetable products (in equivalent fresh vegetables)	kg	158	158.5	155.8	162.1	173.4	170.2	167.8
4. Fruit and fruit products (in fresh fruit equivalent)	kg	80.2	87.8	96	96.1	110.8	111.3	107.6
5. Sugar and sugar products (in refined sugar equivalent)	kg	21.1	25.6	25.3	25.7	25.4	25.6	25.5
Animal products								
6. Milk and dairy products, in milk equivalent of 3.5% fat (excluding butter)	l	244.2	243.4	246.2	244.1	250.7	252.2	252.6
7. Eggs	buc	246	262	267	255	236	241	236
8. Fish and fish products (in fresh fish equivalent)	kg	4.9	5.5	5.9	6.3	6.7	6.4	6.3
9. Meat, meat products and edible offal (in fresh meat equivalent)	kg	60.9	66.4	68.6	71.5	76.2	77.7	77.4

Source: General Agricultural Census (RGA), 2020

Figure 2 Evolution of average annual consumption per inhabitant in the main products of plant origin

Figure 3 Evolution of average annual consumption per inhabitant in the main products of plant origin

Regarding the assurances of food consumption, the analysis of statistical data shows that our country's agriculture succeeded only in cereals and cereal products to ensure its consumption necessities: for all other basic

products, it has to resort to imports to ensure the necessary consumption for population (Table 3, Figures 4 and 5).

Table 3

The evolution of the main agri-food products in Romania

	Years	Resources thousand t	Production thousand t	Import thousand t	%	Export thousand t
Products of plant origin						
1. Cereals and cereal products in grain equivalent	2020	23,070	19,089	3,981	17.3	11,525
	2019	32,370	30,017	2,353	7.3	14,204
	2018	33,176	31,112	2,063	6.2	12,066
2. Potatoes	2020	3,217	2,699	518	16.1	24
	2019	3,163	2,627	535	16.9	38
3. Vegetables and vegetable products (in equivalent fresh vegetables), legumes, grains and melons	2018	3,428	3,022	405	11.8	43
	2020	5,249	3,605	910	17.3	90
4. Fruit and fruit products (in fresh fruit equivalent)	2019	5,240	3,766	865	16.5	135
	2018	5,328	3,990	845	15.9	133
	2020	4,094	2,527	1,328	32.4	108
5. Sugar and sugar products (in refined sugar equivalent)	2019	3,779	2,465	1,314	32.1	113
	2018	4,225	2,958	1,265	29.9	98
	2020	665	187	478	71.9	126
6. Milk and dairy products, in milk equivalent of 3.5% fat (excluding butter) - mii hl	2019	784	292	492	62.8	122
	2018	631	137	494	78.3	111
	2020	64,063	52,812	11,251	17.6	2,437
7. Eggs – mil pcs	2019	62,946	52,568	10,378	16.5	2,464
	2018	63,263	52,835	10,428	16,5	2,791
	2020	5,910	5,446	464	7.9	316
8. Fish and fish products (in fresh fish equivalent)	2019	5,994	5,564	430	7.2	381
	2018	6,061	5,713	348	5.7	428
	2020	129	19	110	85.3	8
9. Meat, meat products and edible offal (in fresh meat equivalent)	2019	163	24	140	85.9	12
	2018	135	23	112	83.0	6
	2020	1,588	1,028	560	35.3	153
	2019	1,606	1,046	580	36.1	163
	2018	1,609	1,035	574	35,7	171

Source: calculations using INS, 2021, 2022

Figure 4. Ensuring consumption availability in the main products of plant origin

Figure 5. Ensuring consumption availability in the main products of animal origin

According to statistical data registered by the National Institute of Statistics in 2020, the degree of self-deprivation (%) in the main basic products consumed in Romania is as follows: cereals and cereal products – 155.6%; vegetables and vegetable products – 82.3%; fruit and fruit products – 68.55; sugar and sugar products – 34.9%; milk and dairy products – 86.4%; eggs – 96.8%; meat, meat products and edible offal – 72.1% and fish and fish products – 15.7%.

The data highlights the imbalances in Romanian agriculture and the inability of the Romanian farmers to produce enough to ensure the necessary consumption.

CONCLUSIONS

Agriculture is one of the branches of major importance that can contribute to the relaunch of the country's economic growth, especially since agriculture cannot take over any other economic activity because the demand of food is essential and has a permanent character for human existence, on the one hand; on the other hand, agriculture provides raw materials necessary to relaunch many other industries (agri-food, textile, chemical, pharmaceutical, cosmetics, energy, etc.).

In Romania, the agri-food production sector has been severely affected since the 90s, by destroying the functional agri-food chains in the centralized economy and the powerlessness of entrepreneurs to create new functional chains to cope with competition in a market

economy. As a result, our country has become an importer of most basic products consumed by the Romanians.

In 2020, meat and meat products imports represented 35.0%, fruit and fruit products imports represented 32.4%, sugar and sugar products imports represented 71.9%, and fish and fish products imports represented 85.3% – way too much for Romania which has a high potential to provide for the consumption requirements in basic products from its own production.

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THE LABOR FORCE IN AGRICULTURE IN ROMANIA, A CURRENT CHALLENGE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the last 15 years, the European Union has lost 30% of its agricultural workforce, and the trend is worrying. To stop this phenomenon, appropriate policies are needed at the European level. Climate change, technological progress and labor mobility have profoundly transformed the field of agriculture. Agricultural machinery is becoming more and more efficient, and computers are increasingly important in agricultural processing technologies, but physical labor in agriculture is not going away anytime soon. In recent years, farmers in the European Union have faced a labor shortage, partially offset by a migration of workers from Eastern European states. At the level of the European Union, the deficit cannot be compensated because the labor force in agriculture registers a decline, from year to year. The agricultural sector in Romania faces an acute labor shortage, and farmers must make efforts to become attractive and efficient. Young people who go to work abroad do not return to work in agriculture. The present paper is an analyze of the situation regarding the labor force in Romania, nowadays.

Keywords: workforce, agriculture, economy, agricultural policy

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INTRODUCTION

There are many angles of view of the workforce structure; thus, the structure of the labor force can be viewed through the lens of participation in economic activity or employment, through that of economic branches and sectors, occupations, etc. Many times, the criteria according to which the workforce is structured are combined. The labor market, in the broad sense, includes problems related to employment, unemployment and the quality of work, productivity, earnings and the cost of work (Ciulinariu, 2019). The employed population represents the main component of the labor force or the active population, the other component being represented by the unemployed.

The labor market is the one that has the right essential purpose allocating jobs to different fields, categories, branches and sub-branches, having as ultimate goal of fulfilling or facilitating both demand and supply specific needs. This purpose is constantly present on the labor market, without there can be no fluctuation and diversification of supply and

demand (Masot, 2021). Another purpose of the labor market it is also to provide information constantly regarding the demand and supply of work, regarding to the way in which the salary evolves or involves employees, the conditions that must be met by both the employer and the employee on the labor market, etc. Exposure of those who are part of the labor market to this information is extremely important because this market must represent the neutral "ground" and transparent for all entities involved in labor market specific processes (Vasile, 2019).

A third purpose of the labor market is to educate both the demand side and the supply side towards one certain behavior necessary for mode development in which they communicate and why not, and how they cope (Ghangshyam, 2015). The labor market encourages through this purpose a climate of social protection and confidence of future young people employed in what they assume related market systems.

Two major aspects are currently grinding Romanian agriculture from the perspective of human capital: the first is the aging of the population, and the second, the lack of qualifications. Almost 60% of the labor force involved in agriculture is represented by people over 60 years old, only 74 thousand of the

almost one million workers in agriculture between 30 and 40 years old. There are multiple programs both to stimulate young people moving to the countryside and to qualify resources, but the procedures are cumbersome and the results are visible only in the long term. On the other hand, in agriculture employers are looking for people who are really qualified, not just passed through various superficial courses. Difficulties in finding competent human resources exist not only for primary qualifications, but also at the level of higher education graduates. Even if the number of Agronomy graduates is high, many of them choose other fields of activity. On the other hand, the training provided within the formal university education system is not harmonized with the practices of modern agriculture, the graduates do not have the experience desired by employers, and the specializations are not correlated with the current market requirements. For employers in agriculture, there are three levels of qualifications, which must be approached differently, basic personnel (agricultural worker/fish farmer, vegetable grower, animal breeder, tractor driver, agricultural mechanic, etc.) can be qualified at the workplace or following short courses (2-4 months); migration is high, also seasonality, and without these qualifications the activity cannot evolve; personnel with higher training (agronomist engineer), for whom there are agencies specialized in employment in agriculture, which can provide the right candidates. However, the availability is low, and a solution can be the identification of Agronomy students who live in the employer's region and who can be motivated to return home for a guaranteed job; for the level of agricultural management, it is preferable to find experienced people, who should be provided with relocation or commuting facilities depending on the situation. The training cycle of such a person is long, and there is not always the necessary time. In all cases, government or local programs run through various financing lines or through the representatives of the National Employment and Vocational Training Agency must also be checked. In agriculture, human resources are limited, which still does not prevent the development of the field. However, attracting qualified people can have a major effect on improving the quality of the activity, productivity and implicitly, profitability (Gupta, 2014).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The key research methods employed were analysis and synthesis, analogy, and graphics to resemble the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Currently, the Romanian economy is facing serious problems in the field of labor force utilization in agriculture, with a series of distortions on the labor market, which translate into the coexistence of a labor force deficit, in certain economic branches, with poor utilization of it as a whole. The employment rate at the national level is still low, and unemployment is significant, although its rate is lower than the European average. That is why the programs/measures in the field of labor in Romania must focus on attracting and maintaining more people in work, by making contractual provisions more flexible, and developing the educational and professional training system. In recent years, however, a labor force deficit has appeared in Romania, affecting development and the economic growth of some sectors: it is about construction, services, new industry and agriculture, but also education, health and public administration. The system of social assistance in Romania, promoted with generosity, generated the situation of not being able to find people for employment. In this way, the labor force crisis in Romania is acutely felt in agriculture as well. Unlike other sectors of the economy, the agricultural workforce has a high level of aging and a low level of professional training.

Figure. 1. Distribution of employed population by economic activities, years 2021-2022

From the distribution of employed persons by economic activity, it follows that 181.2 thousand persons or 21.5% of the total number of employed persons were active in the agricultural sector, their number increasing by

3.0% compared to the level of the previous year (in 2021 - 175, 9 thousand and 21.1%), as shown in the figure below. From the data obtained for the years 2021-2022, there are no large discrepancies between the number of women and men working in agriculture. Significant differences are registered between the urban and rural environments, the inhabitants of the rural environment being significantly more involved in agricultural activities. The available active population consists of people who declare in the census that they exercise a professional activity or who, without working, declare that they are looking for a job. The available active population constitutes the workforce resources, the potential workforce. The volume of the active population is influenced by a whole series of structural and conjunctural factors. Among the structural factors we mention: the duration of schooling, the retirement age, the degree of use of the female labor force. Conjunctural factors are represented by the participation in the economic activity of young people, the elderly and women.

Figure. 2. Distribution of the employed population in agriculture, forestry, phishing by gender and medium, 2022

In the graphic below, it is resembled the fact that the highest employment percentage involved in agriculture is registered in the North-East region, with 20.25% and the lowest percentage is registered in Bucharest-Ilfov region. 1.51. An important aspect in this case is the geographical position.

Figure. 3. The share of Romania's employment in agriculture by development regions, 2021-2022 (%)

Work in agriculture represents the determining element for the value of the resources in this branch, represented by the land capital and the exploitation capital, decisively influencing the production results.

Many agrarian economists recognize the economic importance of work in agriculture through the lens of the large weight in the structure of the production expenses of those related to the labor force. This weight is estimated between 30-60% of the total expenses, depending on the type of exploitation, the intensive or extensive production systems that are practiced. Although agriculture, with 20% of GDP and 35% of the employed population, it is the second largest sector in the Romanian economy, the real performances of this branch are far from the pedoclimatic potential of the country, far from the agricultural vocation of our nation. Labor productivity remains very low in the agricultural sector and the food industry, although the share of the private sector in agricultural production was 86% in 2022. The development of the private sector in agriculture (and agriculture in general) is hindered by the low degree of capitalization of agricultural holdings (of peasant households), the low degree of mechanization, the lack of support services (technical, financial, managerial) but also the professional knowledge of the Romanian peasant.

CONCLUSIONS

Agriculture is the main economic activity in most rural areas in Romania. However, many farmers practice additional activities, such as processing of agricultural products. The diversification of the rural economy is a source of vitality that Romania should also support encourage it through its rural development programs. Without agriculture, there would be few elements that to maintain the vitality and unity of many communities rural. If agriculture were to disappear, in many areas the land would be abandoned. Farmers play a very important economic role in rural areas, which the EU cannot afford to lose. It is necessary a common agricultural policy to support young people to start in agriculture, giving them funds to buy land, machinery and agricultural equipment. This provides, also grants for training young people farmers, as well as those with experience, in view using the latest production methods and techniques. Encouraging young farmers and ensuring continuity from one generation to another it

should be true challenge for rural development in Romania. In some regions of the country, the practice of agriculture is particularly difficult – for example, in hilly areas and mountainous and remote regions. It is important to the vitality of these communities is maintained regions. A common agricultural policy provides funds to ensure that these communities, located in vulnerable rural regions, have a good economic situation and do not gradually disappear.

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STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE PERIOD OF ESTABLISHMENT OF THE AUTUMN CROP IN CHINESE CABBAGE GROWN IN GREENHOUSES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Chinese cabbage is an annual plant, but in Romanian climatic conditions it is grown as a biennial plant. It has two types, Pe Tsai and Pak choi. It is native to Eastern Asia; China and Japan are the biggest growers. Chinese cabbage has a high content of vitamins, minerals and active principles. The calcium included in Chinese cabbage is bioavailable to the human body and is found in sufficient quantities. For the fall crop, the period of crop establishment influences the emergence of flowering stems and total production. Of the two varieties, Pak choi is more sensitive to the emission of flowering stems.

Keywords: Chinese cabbage, pak choi, pe tsai, flowering stems

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INTRODUCTION

Chinese cabbage is a biennial plant, but due to the short vegetation period, it behaves like an annual species. Chinese cabbage is present in culture under two varieties: *Brassica campestris* var. *pekinensis* (Pe tsai) and *Brassica campestris* var. *chinensis* (Pak choi).

The origin of this species is in Eastern Asia, in China it has been cultivated since the 10th century. On the European continent it appears in the century. the 18th century, but only in the 20th century does the species show interest, both in Europe and America. Being native to Asia, the highest consumption is found in China and Japan, in fact cabbage occupies the largest areas in Asia. In Romania, Chinese cabbage is cultivated sporadically on small areas, most of the production found on the market comes from imports. The consumption trend is increasing.

The two varieties of Chinese cabbage are eaten either raw in the form of salads, in association with other greens, it has a pleasant sweet-sour, slightly spicy taste, or cooked in various forms. In China, it is widely consumed in lacto-fermented form, especially the Pe tsai variety.

The consumption of Chinese cabbage is recommended, not only for the taste and finesse

of culinary preparations, but for the wealth of vitamins, minerals and active principles. Food Data Central presents the nutritional values for 100g Chinese cabbage: Water 96.3g, Energy 12 kcal, Protein 1.1g, Total lipid (fat) 0.17g, Ash 0.17g, Carbohydrate by difference 2.23g, Calcium, Ca 29mg, Iron, Fe 0.74 mg, Magnesium, Mg 8mg, Phosphorus, P 19 mg, Potassium, K 87 mg, Sodium, Na 11 mg, Zinc, Zn 0.14 mg, Manganese, Mn, 0.203 mg, Vitamin C, total ascorbic acid 3.2 mg, Vitamin B- 6 0.037 mg, Vitamin B-6 0.037mg, Vitamin A, RAE 13 µg, Carotenes, beta 133 µg, Vitamin A, IU 263 IU.

When it comes to cruciferous vegetables (broccoli, cauliflower, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, etc.), research shows that regular consumption may help prevent several types of cancer, such as lung, pancreatic, ovarian, and kidney cancers (Brennan et al, 2005).

However, it seems that this protective effect would not be the same in all individuals due to genetic factors (. Lampe JW, Peterson S.). In addition, a study showed a link between frequent consumption of cruciferous vegetables (more than 30 times per month) and a lower concentration of homocysteine in the blood (Ganji, Kafai, 2004). High blood homocysteine concentrations have been associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (Guthikonda, Haynes, 2006). In a large study

(over 100,000 subjects), individuals who consumed Chinese cabbage almost every day had a 50% lower risk of urinary tract cancer than those who consumed it less than once or twice a month (Sakauchi, et al, 2005). A similar trend is seen in other studies evaluating the consumption of Chinese cabbage and the incidence of various types of cancer (prostate, gastrointestinal, brain) (Kristal, Lampe, 2002.).

Chinese cabbage contains glucosinolates, in smaller amounts than most other cruciferous vegetables. In addition, the variety Pak-choi (Bok choy) is said to contain about twice as much as Peking cabbage (Pe-tsai) (McNaughton Marks, 2003) Chinese radish contains considerable amounts of carotenoids, especially in the form of beta -carotene. Carotenoids are compounds that also have antioxidant properties (Stahl, Sies, 2005). Chinese cabbage is one of the vegetables that contains the most bioavailable calcium, meaning calcium that the body can absorb and use. The bioavailability of calcium from some vegetables (mainly green leafy vegetables) is variable. Bok choy contains a significant amount of calcium (84 mg per 125 ml serving) and is highly bioavailable (54% absorption rate) (Miller et al., 2001).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The current research aims to establish an optimal interval for the establishment of the culture that avoids the appearance of flowering stems, with direct effects on production. The research took place in a small ecological vegetable farm in the town of Husășău de Tinca,

located in NW of Romania, in the year 2021. To achieve the proposed objectives, two monofactorial experiments were established for each variety of Chinese cabbage. Each experiment had six variants in three repetitions.

Each variant had 50 plants. The biological material was represented by the type of cabbage pak choi and pe tsai. The arrangement of the variants was been done according to the method of subdivided blocks. The statistical processing of the experimental data was done by analysis of variance.

Experimental variants
 V1 Pc V1 Pt – sown 22.08
 V2Pc V2 Pt – sown 03.09
 V3 Pc V3 Pt – sown 12.09
 V4Pc V4 Pt – sown 26.09.
 V5 Pc V5 Pt – sown 03.10
 V6Pc V6 Pt – sown 14.10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For the production of seedlings, for both varieties, alveolar trays were used for seeding, at the corresponding dates from the proposed variants.

Seedlings were planted in all variants 30 days after emergence.

The first aspect pursued in the experiment was the identification of the plants that emitted flowering stems.

The data related to the emission of flowering stems was described in table no. 1.

Table 1

**Plants that did not produce flowering stems after planting
 Husășău de Tinca, 2021**

Cr. No.	Variant	Total of plants	Plants without strains (nr.)	Plants Without strains (%)	Cr. No.	Variant	Total of plants	Plants without strains (nr.)	Plants without strains (%)
1	V1 Pc	50	48	96	1	V1 Pt	50	49	98
2	V2 Pc	50	49	98	2	V2 Pt	50	50	100
3	V3 Pc	50	50	100	3	V3 Pt	50	50	100
4	V4 Pc	50	47	94	4	V4 Pt	50	50	100
5	V5 Pc	50	32	64	5	V5 Pt	50	48	96
6	V6 Pc	50	10	20	6	V6 Pt	50	21	42

In the Pak choi variety, it was noticed that only in the V3 Pc variant none of the 50 plants planted produced flowering stems. In the other variants, the percentage of plants that emitted flowering stems was 4% at V1 Pc and up to 80% at V6 Pc. Basically the late establishment of the culture determined the appearance of flower stalks.

In the other cabbage variety (Pe tsai), the variants V2 Pt, V3 Pt and V4 Pt had a normal growth so that no plant produced flower stalks. And in the case of this type of cabbage, the late establishment of the culture influenced the appearance of flowering stems in 29 plants out of the total of 50 (V6 Pt).

The appearance of flowering stems in Chinese cabbage varieties directly influences

the total production per unit area. In case of plants with flowering stems, a few leaves can be used in greens mixture for salads.

In the second part of the research, the influence of the culture establishment period on the production potential of the two types of Chinese cabbage was analyzed. The production of Chinese cabbage variety Pak choi was presented in table no. 2. Production data were processed statistically by analysis of variance.

For each variant, plants with flowering stems appearing before the harvest period negatively influence production per surface unit. In the case of the present experiment, the average of the variants was chosen as the control. The best production results were obtained with the V3 Pc variant with a production increase compared to the control of over 40%, the difference being statistically very significantly positive. Good results were also recorded with the V2 Pc variant from which they harvested 1.24 kg/m² more than the experience average.

The difference from this was ensured statistically positively very significant. Even if it was sown very early, the plants from the V1 Pc variant obtained results superior to the average of the experience, but with a somewhat reduced increase of 14.2% compared to the control. The difference was positively statistically significant. The V4 Pc variant, even if it recorded a production above the average of the experience, the difference did not exceed the p=5% threshold and was not statistically ensured.

The later establishment of V5 Pc and V6 Pc variants resulted in the emission of flowering stems in many plants, which greatly influenced production. Thus the V5 Pc obtained only 69.58% of the average production of the experience, respectively 38.07% in the case of the V6 Pc variant. In both variants, the difference compared to the control was statistically very significantly negative.

Table 2

**Production of chinese cabbage Pak choi
Husasău de Tinca, 2021**

Cr. no.	Variant	Absolute production of Pak choi kg/m ²	Relative production of Pak choi %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	V1 Pc	5.23	114.42	+0.66	X
2	V2 Pc	5.81	127.13	+1.24	XX
3	V3 Pc	6.72	141.47	+2.15	XXX
4	V4 Pc	4.75	104.59	+0.18	-
5	V5 Pc	3.18	69.58	-1.39	000
6	V6 Pc	1.74	38.07	-2.83	000
7	Mt. Average	4,57	100,00	0.00	-

LSD_{5%}=0.54 LSD_{1%}=0.88 LSD_{0,1%}=1.15

Table no. 3 shows the production data obtained for the 6 varieties of Chinese cabbage, the Pe tsai variety. In this case the witness was represented by the average of the experience.

Comparing the productions of the two types of Chinese cabbage as a whole, it can be noted that in the case of the Pe tsai variety, the productions were closer to the average of the experience compared to the Pak choi variety, where the differences from the average were much larger.

Analysis of production data from table no. 3 highlighted the V2 Pt variant which recorded an absolute production of 98.5 t/ha (a very good production) and a production increase compared to the average of 24.68%.

The difference from the control was statistically positively distinctly significant. The V3 variant obtained 1.34 kg/m² more than the control, the difference being statistically positively significant. Also, in the case of the Pe tsai variety, the late establishment of the crop caused the mass appearance of flowering stems. The phenomenon was observed in the V6 Pt variant, which obtained only 52.53% of the experience average. The difference from the control was statistically highly significant negative.

The other variants achieved production results close to the experience average, but did not exceed the p=5% threshold, so they were not statistically assured.

**Production of chinese cabbage Pe tsai
Husasău de Tinca, 2021**

Cr. no.	Variant	Absolute production of Pe tsai kg/m ²	Relative production of Pe tsai %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	V1 Pt	8.12	102.78	+0.22	-
2	V2 Pt	9.85	124.68	+1.95	XX
3	V3 Pt	9.24	116.96	+1.34	X
4	V4 Pt	8.71	110.25	+0.81	-
5	V5 Pt	7.36	93.16	-0.54	-
6	V6 Pt	4.15	52.53	-3.75	000
7	Mt. Average	7.90	100.00	0.00	-

LSD_{5%}=0.94 LSD_{1%}=1.54 LSD_{0.1%}=2.01

CONCLUSIONS

The research regarding the influence of the period of establishment of the Chinese cabbage culture led to several conclusions:

The sowing and planting period of the Chinese cabbage crop directly influences both the emergence of flowering stems and production.

For the fall crop of Chinese cabbage, both sowing in late August and mid-October had caused premature emergence of flowering stems.

The interval with the optimal sowing period is much narrower in the Pak choi variety compared to the Pe tsai variety.

In the case of the Pak choi variety, the V3 Pc variant sown on 12 September recorded the highest absolute production of 67.2 t/ha.

At the Pak choi variety, the V6 Pc variant sown on October 19, due to the premature appearance of the flower stalks, has determined a very low production of only 1.74 kg/m².

In the case of the Pe tsai variety, the V2 Pt variant sown at the beginning of September achieved the highest production. The production was 9.85 kg/m².

Sowing in the middle of October in the case of the V6 Pt variant caused the appearance of flowering stems in a fairly large number of plants, but less than in the Pak choi variety sown in the same period.

Comparing the production potential of the two types of Chinese cabbage, much higher productions were noticed in the Pe tsai variety.

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THE BEHAVIOR OF SOME APPLE VARIETIES IN BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The apple tree is a rustic species, very well adapted to the temperate climate; it withstands the winters characteristic of this climate better than any other tree species and behaves well on a wide range of soils. If superior agrotechnics are applied in orchards, the highest yields per hectare are obtained compared to other fruit tree species. The apple can be grown in very different pedoclimatic conditions and lends itself to any of the cultivation systems. In this study, we proposed the analysis of some apple varieties grown in the pedoclimatic conditions of Tăuteu commune, Bihor County. The main objectives of the study concerned the biometric characteristics of the fruits and the determination of dry matter and sugars. In order to fulfill our proposed objectives, we studied four varieties of apple: 'Remo', 'Relinda', 'Rewena' and 'Red Delcious'. Among the four apple varieties studied, the best results were obtained with the Remo variety.

Keywords: apple cv. 'Remo', cv. 'Relinda', cv. 'Rewena' și cv. 'Red Delcious'
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INTRODUCTION

The apple is the most well-known and widespread fruit crop of a temperate climate. It has been cultivated in Europe and Asia since ancient times. As for surface area, on the territory of Romania, the apple occupies over 50,000 ha, being the second most cultivated tree species after the plum (Iuga et al, 2022)

The wide geographical dissemination of this fruit tree species was possible due to its impressive genetic variety and adaptability. These characteristics allowed the selection of numerous varieties with great ecological plasticity, adapted to the most diverse cultivation areas around the globe (Chira & Pasca, 2008; Cociu et al, 1999;).

The share occupied by apple culture in the world economy of fruit production is primarily due to the role that apples play in human nutrition (Ilie & Stănică, 2012).

Apples contain a rich source of phytochemicals, which have properties in reducing the risk of certain types of cancer, cardiovascular disease, asthma and diabetes. There are also studies that have found that apples have a very strong antioxidant activity, inhibit the proliferation of cancer cells, decrease lipid oxidation and lower cholesterol. Apples contain a variety of phytochemicals, including

quercetin, catechin, phloridzin and chlorogenic acid, all of which are powerful antioxidants [Sesso et al, 2003; Boyer & Liu, 2004; Bondonno et al, 2017; Ferretti et al, 2014; Iordănescu et al, 2021].

In this work we have proposed the analysis of some apple varieties cultivated in the pedoclimatic conditions of Tăuteu commune, Bihor County, in the ecological/biological culture system. The main objectives of the study were the biometric characteristics of the fruit and the determination of dry matter and sugars.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to achieve our proposed objectives, we took into account four varieties of apple: three lesser-known varieties, namely 'Remo', 'Relinda', 'Rewena' and a variety more common in the 'Red Delcious' culture, hemmed in a family orchard in Tăuteu commune, Bihor County. The plantation is in year VII and its maintenance is carried out as ecologically as possible, in the sense that, except for winter treatments, no other control measures are applied of diseases and pests. In order to establish the biometric characteristics of the fruits, 15 apples (5 apples/repetition) were analyzed, on which measurements of their height, large meter and small diameter were

made, measurements made with the help of electronic screed. The determination of the mass was done by weighing with the electronic balance. The determination of the dry matter was carried out using the digital refractometer and the sugar content was calculated using the formula: $(N \times 4.25) / 4 - 2.5$ where N represent the dry matter content. As a control the average version of the experience was chosen. The data obtained were interpreted statistically using variance analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results obtained on the height of the fruit and the statistical analysis of the data (Table 1) lead to the conclusion that no semnification is recorded between the four varieties studied in relation to the control.

The small diameter of the fruits in the studied apple varieties is between 4.34 cm in the 'Red Delicious' variety and 4.82 cm in the 'Remo' variety with an average experience of 4.49 cm. Analyzing the behavior of the varieties in relation to the average of the experience it can be said that no semnification is recorded in relation to the control. (Table 2)

Table 1

The height of fruits in the studied apple varieties (2021)

Variety	The height of the fruit Cm	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	6.00	107.33	0.41	-
`Relinda`	5.00	89.45	-0.59	-
`Rewena`	5.54	99.11	-0.05	-
`Red Delicious`	5.82	104.11	0.23	-
Average of the varieties	5.59	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%			LD 1%	LD 0.1%
1.45 cm			1.96 cm	2.61 cm

Table 2

Small diameter of fruits in the studied apple varieties (2021)

Variety	Small diameter of fruits Cm	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	4.82	107.29	0.33	-
`Relinda`	4.45	99.05	-0.04	-
`Rewena`	4.36	97.05	-0.13	-
`Red Delicious`	4.34	96.61	-0.15	-
Average of the varieties	4.49	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%			LD 5%	LD 1%
1.40 cm			1.89	2.52

The large diameter of the fruits in the four varieties of apple studied is between 5.58 cm in the 'Rewena' variety and 6.48 cm in the 'Red Delicious' variety with an average experience of 6.00 cm. Analyzing the behaviour of the varieties, it appears that no significance is recorded in relation to the control. (Table 3)

The results of the measurements regarding the average mass of the fruits and the statistical analysis of the data lead to the conclusion that of the four varieties of apple

studied, three varieties show statistical differences compared to the average considered as a control.

As seen in Table 4, compared to the average, the variety 'Red Delicious' recorded very high values with a mass of 129.84 g being very significantly positive compared to the control, and the varieties 'Relinda' and 'Rewena' with a mass of 90.98 g and 88.67 g values below the average being very significantly negative to the control.

Table 3

Large diameter of fruits in the studied apple varieties (2021)

Variety	Large diameter of fruits Cm	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	5.94	99.00	-0.06	-
`Relinda`	6.00	100.00	0.00	-
`Rewena`	5.58	93.00	-0.42	-
`Red Delicious`	6.48	108.00	0.48	-
Average of the varieties	6.00	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%			LD 1%	LD 0.1%
0.85			1.14	1.52

Table 4

The mass of fruits in the studied apple varieties (2021)				
Variety	Fruit mass g	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	102.97	99.86	-0.15	-
`Relinda`	90.98	88.23	-12.14	000
`Rewena`	88.67	85.99	-14.45	000
`Red Delicious`	129.84	125.92	26.73	XXX
Average of the varieties	103.12	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%		LD 5%		LD 1%
1.38		1.86		2.48

Figure 1 The analyzed apple varieties

The dry matter content of the studied apple varieties was between 11.01 °Brix for the variety `Red Delicious` and 17.77 °Brix for the variety `Remo`. Compared to the control, the `Remo` variety recorded very high values, being very significantly positive, and the `Red Delicious` variety recorded values below the average being very significantly negative compared to the control. (Table 5)

The sugar content of the apple varieties studied was between 16.38 g/l in the `Remo`

variety and 9.20 g/l in the `Red Delicious` variety with an experience average of 13.00 g/l. Compared to the average, the `Remo` variety recorded higher values, being very significant positive compared to the control, and the `Red Delicious` variety recorded values below the average being very significantly negative compared to the control. The varieties `Relinda` and `Rewena` did not get meanings in comparison with the control.(Table 6)

Table 5

Dry matter content of fruits in studied apple varieties (2021)

Variety	Dry matter °Brix	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	17.77	121.80	3.18	XXX
`Relinda`	15.10	103.50	0.51	-
`Rewena`	14.48	99.25	-0.11	-
`Red Delicious`	11.01	75.46	-3.58	000
Average of the varieties	14.59	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%	0.80		LD 1%	LD 0.1%
			1.08	1.44

Table 6

Sugar content of fruits in the apple varieties studied (2021)

Variety	Sugars g/l	Relative value %	Difference from the control	Significance
`Remo`	16.38	125.98	3.38	XXX
`Relinda`	13.54	104.13	0.54	-
`Rewena`	12.89	99.13	-0.11	-
`Red Delicious`	9.20	70.76	-3.80	000
Average of the varieties	13.00	100.00	0.00	control
LD 5%	0.71		LD 1%	LD 0.1%
			0.96	1.28

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the analyses carried out, no significance was recorded in terms of the height of the fruit, the small diameter and the large diameter of the fruit.

The results obtained regarding the mass of the fruit indicate that the 'Red Delicious' variety is much higher compared to the 'Relinda' and 'Rewena' varieties, which recorded results well below the control average.

The dry matter content had very significantly positive values in the apple variety 'Remo', and the 'Red Delicious' variety recorded the lowest values.

In terms of sugar content, the highest values were recorded in the 'Remo' variety and in the 'Red Delicious' variety the lowest values.

In conclusion, among the four apple varieties studied in the pedoclimatic conditions of Tăuteu commune, Bihor County, the best results were obtained for the 'Remo' variety. This paragraph will briefly present the results of the research. Conclusions will be concise and clear, no hypothesis and probability. Each conclusion will start on a new row. The text will be edited not numbered or bullet lists. This section can be skipped, but should be added if the results and discussion part is long.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE EFFECT OF FERTILIZATION ON THE GROWTH OF BRANCHES OF PLUM SEEDLINGS IN THE SECOND FIELD

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Taking into account the demand of young plants for nutritional conditions, their relatively high density per surface unit, the need for their intense growth in a relatively short time, the rational application of fertilizers becomes a very important factor for increasing the yield and quality of the planting material. In modern fruit growing, fertilization is one of the most important technological links. Due to their specificity, fruit plants occupy the same area of land for a long period of time, develop their root system to a significant depth and due to the high productivity they achieve, they extract from the soil, with the harvest, appreciable quantities of nutrients. In these conditions, it is necessary to intervene every year, in several rounds, with fertilizations that ensure, on the one hand, the achievement of a certain level of production, and on the other hand, a certain level and ratio of nutritional elements through returning the quantities of easily accessible nutrients extracted with the harvest in order to be able to maintain, in this way, the fertility of the soil in accordance with the age of the plantation and the level of production. The present paper is a research regarding the effect of fertilization on the growth of branches of plum seedlings in the nursery, in the second field and it is analyzed the influence of fertilization treatment, variety and irrigations rate.

Keywords: orchard, planting material, fertilization
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INTRODUCTION

The fertilization system in the nursery includes, as a whole, long-term activities, intended to ensure the improvement of the physical and chemical properties of the soil and the increase of its fertility, the completion of the necessary assimilable nutrients according to the requirements of the species, rootstocks, variety/rootstock associations in relation to age and the vegetation phases of plants (Megh 2021). Among the main elements of the fertilization system in the modern fruit nursery are: the accumulation of organic matter in the soil through rotations and the incorporation of special plant residues for green fertilizers; administration of mineral fertilizers with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (Klock 2019). The doses, terms and methods of fertilizer application are established differently

for each sector of the nursery depending on the agrochemical properties of the soil and the requirements of the cultivated plants (Schmid 2019). The use of fertilizers in the cultivation of trees becomes necessary to renew the reserve of nutrients consumed by plants or leached in depth, then to improve the physical condition, the chemical composition and the state of fertilization as a whole of the soil. The most important principle of the efficiency of the fertilization system consists in the maximum utilization and the correct combination of fertilizers on horticultural lands. In the soil fertilization system, fertilizers are considered to be the most important element. They are the main source of ensuring plants with nutrients during the vegetation of horticultural plants. It must be taken into account that by applying fertilizers, it must not favor the decrease of the trees' resistance to critical natural factors (diseases, pests, winter conditions, etc.) or reduce the life span of the trees. Such an

orientation leads to the conclusion that fertilization must be done differentiated by species and variety, grafts, rootstocks or by groups of them, the ecoclimatic and pedological particularities of the area, the culture system, the age period and the physiological state of the plants, the productive and quality potential what is to be maintained or created. Thus, for a rational fertilization in fruit plantations, it is necessary to know the physical-chemical state of the soil in the plantations and the level of supply with nutrients easily accessible to the plants. At the same time, the specific consumption requirements for macro and microelements of trees, variable according to the influence of modifying factors, should be known (Prabhu 2020). In horticultural crops, in practice, the limiting factor is rarely the insufficient nutritional elements, but rather the nutritional imbalance, produced by the excess in some elements, as well as insufficient water supply or excess water. Insufficient water supply creates conditions of excessive salinity in the vicinity of the roots, which inhibit both the absorption of nutrients and water. Excess water, on the one hand, leads to the washing of nutrients outside the rhizosphere and, on the other hand, worsens the oxygen supply of the roots and thereby leads to a weaker absorption of nutrients. This interdependence between water supply and mineral nutrition highlights the role of simultaneous and balanced intake of water and fertilizers, which in practice led to fertilizing irrigation. In modern fruit growing, fertilization is one of the most important technological links (Megh 2018). Due to their specificity, fruit plants occupy the same area of land for a long period of time, develop their root system to a significant depth and due to the high productivity they achieve, they extract from the soil, with the harvest, appreciable quantities of nutrients. In these conditions, it is necessary to intervene every year, in several rounds, with fertilizations that ensure, on the one hand, the achievement of a certain level of production, and on the other hand, a certain level and ratio of nutritional elements through returning the quantities of easily accessible nutrients extracted with the harvest in order to be able to maintain, in this way, the fertility of the soil in accordance with the age of the plantation and the level of production (Riedel 2018). For the correct determination of the type and doses of fertilizers that must be applied per surface unit or per productive unit, the physical characteristics of the soil, the degree of supply

with nutrients easily accessible to plants and the state of fertility as a whole are taken into account. The physical features take into account the orography of the land, the useful edaphic volume, the depth of the water table, the texture, the structure and the water regime as a whole. The chemical composition refers to the pH or salinity, the content of organic matter, the cation exchange capacity, the degree of saturation in bases, the content of macro and micro elements in forms accessible to plants (Guy 2021). The microbiological activity in the soil is important for the disaggregation of complex organic substances in simple forms, accessible to plants and even for mediating more complex chemical transformations. Vegetative state expressed by the growth vigor of one-year branches, etc. The knowledge so far has proven that when applying fertilization, the soil conditions, species, variety, rootstock, density, forecasted production, etc. must be taken into account. Establishing the optimal doses for each situation in the field must be done after analyzing a series of soil properties, knowing the requirements imposed by the culture and those related to ensuring a certain quantitative and qualitative level of production. Due to the great diversity of conditions and situations, fertilization works in orchards must offer practical solutions for each individual case. Experiments with fertilizers, whether they are carried out in the plantations or in the greenhouse, aim to clarify the mechanisms that direct the mineral nutrition of the trees, to know the balance of nutrients in the plant and in the soil, the possibilities of enhancing the efficiency of fertilization and last but not least, the means to reduce the possible ecological impact of large doses of fertilizers on the fruit ecosystem (Balram 2020). The quantitative and qualitative knowledge of nutrients extracted by fruit plants from the surface unit is very important for the rational application of fertilizers. This knowledge presupposes prior information, based on laboratory chemical analyses, on the qualitative and quantitative presence of different nutrients in the soil. In the nursery, the lack of basic elements - nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium - causes serious deficiencies in the growth process of seedlings.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The key research methods employed were analysis and synthesis and analogy to resemble the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Under the effect of the different fertilization treatments, the growth of the canes showed an amplitude of variation of 33.12 cm, with values ranging between 169.88 cm on the unfertilized agricultural fund and 203 cm in the case of applying the dose of 24 kg of NPK, under the conditions of a variability of 8, 49% between treatments (table 18). The application of the fertilization variants with 16-24 kg NPK

determined the registration of significant increases in growth of 12.66-19.50% compared to the non-fertilized agricultural fund, instead the variant with 8 kg NPK showed a low and insignificant effect associated with an increase of only 1.84%. The addition of fertilization from 8 to 16 kg and respectively from 16 to 24 kg, was effectively utilized by the seedlings that achieved significant increases in growth of 6.07-10.62%.

Table 1

The average growth of branches in the second field under the effect of different fertilization treatments

NPK Dose	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/Significance
N ₈ P ₈ K ₈ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	173.00	169.88	101.84	3.12
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	191.38	169.88	112.66	21.50***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	203.00	169.88	119.50	33.12***
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	191.38	173.00	110.62	18.38***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	203.00	173.00	117.34	30.00***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	203.00	191.38	106.07	11.62***

LSD_{5%}=4.58 cm LSD_{1%}=6.07 cm LSD_{0,1%}=7.84 cm

Taking into account the effect of the interaction between varieties and irrigation on the growth of vines in seedlings from field II, table 19 shows that in the case of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, the three watering norms generated significant increases compared to the non-irrigated variant. Also, the seedlings of the

Stanley variety efficiently utilized only the norms of 20 and 30 mm which determined significant increases, while the effect of the norm of 10 mm was considerably less than in the Cacanska Lepotica variety.

Table 2

The effect of variety and irrigation on the growth of vines in seedlings from the second field

Variety	Irrigation rate				$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	S%
	0 mm	10 mm	20 mm	30 mm		
Stanley	z 178,50 a	yz 185,00 a	y 190,75 a	x 199,50 a	188,44±2,46	11,69
Cacanska Lepotica	z 162,25 b	y 175,75 a	y 182,25 a	x 200,50 a	180,19±2,86	14,19
$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	170.38±4.21	180.38±3.47	186.50±2.35	200.00±3.53	184.30±1.91	
S%	15.61	12.15	7.97	11.15	13.11	

Variety - LSD_{5%}=14.87 cm LSD_{1%}=21.62 cm LSD_{0,1%}=32.44 cm (a,b)
Irrigation - LSD_{5%}=8.52 cm LSD_{1%}=11.56 cm LSD_{0,1%}=15,46 cm (x, y,z)

Regarding the combined effect of the variety and fertilization on the growth of the seedlings, it is found that in both varieties the treatments with 16-24 kg of NPK and respectively the progressive increase of the doses showed significantly positive influences

on the growth of the seedlings, against the background of more raised in the Stanley variety.

Table 3

The effect of variety and fertilization on the growth of branches

Variety	NPK Dose				$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	S%
	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄		
Stanley	z 177.25 a	z 178.50 a	y 193.25 a	x 204.75 a	188.44±2.46	11.69
Cacanska Lepotica	z 162.50 b	z 167.50 a	y 189.50 a	x 201.25 a	180.19±2.86	14.19
$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	169.88±3.26	173.00±3.42	191.38±2.82	203.00±3.21	184.30±1.91	
S%	16.15		9.30	9.99	13.11	

Variety - LSD_{5%}=14.59 cm LSD_{1%}=21.83 cm LSD_{0,1%}=34,34 cm (a,b)
 Fertilizer - LSD_{5%}=6.48 cm LSD_{1%}=8.58 cm LSD_{0,1%}=11.25 cm (x, y)

Taking into account the effect of the variety on the growth of the shoots of the seedlings on different fertilization treatments, amplitudes are found from 3.5-3.75 cm for the variants with doses of 16-24 kg NPK up to 14.75 cm for the variant unfertilized. Against the background of these differences, it can be observed that the Stanley variety showed a

significantly higher growth of seedlings than the unfertilized version by 9.07%. The seedlings of the two varieties utilized the fertilization at a similar level, against the background of higher growth in the Stanley variety, but without the respective differences being statistically ensured.

Table 4

The effect of the variety on the growth of branches on different fertilizations

Varieties x N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
Cacanska Lepotica - Stanley	162.50	177.25	91.68	-14.75 ⁰
Varieties x N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
Cacanska Lepotica - Stanley	167,50	178,50	93,84	-11,00
Varieties x N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
Cacanska Lepotica - Stanley	189,50	193,25	98,06	-3,75
Varieties x N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
Cacanska Lepotica - Stanley	201.25	204.75	98.29	-3.50

LSD_{5%}=14.59 cm LSD_{1%}=21.83 cm LSD_{0,1%}=34.34 cm

Regarding the effect of fertilization on the growth of the stems for each variety, it can be observed that at Stanley the values were between 177.25 cm for the unfertilized variant and 204.75 cm in the case of applying the dose of 24 kg of NPK. Compared to the unfertilized version, only the doses of 8-16 kg had

significant effects of 9.03-15.51% on the growth of seedlings.

It is also found that the progressive increase by 8 kg of the applied dose was associated with a significant increase in the growth of the rods of 5.95-8.26 %.

Table 5

The effect of fertilization on the growth of branches in seedlings of different varieties

NPK Dose x Stanley	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
N ₈ P ₈ K ₈ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	178.50	177.25	100.71	1.25
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	193.25	177.25	109.03	16.00***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	204.75	177.25	115.51	27.50***
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	193.25	178.50	108.26	14.75***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	204.75	178.50	114.71	26.25***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	204.75	193.25	105.95	11.50***
NPK Dose x Cacanska Lepotica	Branches growth (cm)		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Significance
N ₈ P ₈ K ₈ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	167.50	162.50	103.08	5.00
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	189.50	162.50	116.62	27.00***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	201.25	162.50	123.85	38.75***
N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	189.50	167.50	113.13	22.00***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	201.25	167.50	120.15	33.75***
N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄ – N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	201.25	189.50	106.20	11.75***

LSD_{5%}=6.48 cm LSD_{1%}=8.58 cm LSD_{0,1%}=11.25 cm

From the point of view of the influence of fertilization on the growth of canes achieved on a certain watering rate, it can be observed that the highest amplitude of variation (47 cm) was recorded at the watering rate of 10 mm,

while in the case the norm of 20 mm. the amplitude between NPK doses was considerably smaller (17 cm).

Table 6

The effect of irrigation and fertilization on the growth of seedlings

Irrigation rate	NPK Dose				$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	S%
	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₈ P ₈ K ₈	N ₁₆ P ₁₆ K ₁₆	N ₂₄ P ₂₄ K ₂₄		
0 mm	148.50 b	153.50 d	191.50 ab	188.00 c	170.38±4.21	15.61
10 mm	174.50 a	163.00 c	174.00 c	210.00 b	180.38±3.47	12.15
20 mm	178.00 a	183.50 b	189.50 b	195.00 c	186.50±2.35	7.97
30 mm	178.50 a	192.00 a	210.50 a	219.00 a	200.00±3.53	11.15
$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	169.88±3.26	173.00±3.42	191.38±2.82	203.00±3.21	184.30±1.91	
S%	16.15	12.15	9.30	9.99	13.11	

Irrigation - LSD_{5%}=9,82 cm LSD_{1%}=12,99 cm LSD_{0,1%}=16,76 cm (a,b,c)
Fertilization - LSD_{5%}=9,17 cm LSD_{1%}=12,14 cm LSD_{0,1%}=15,68 cm (x, y)**CONCLUSIONS**

On the non-fertilized agricultural fund, the irrigation determined a significant growth of the seedlings of the Stanley variety by 27-33 cm, under the conditions of small and insignificant variations between the three watering norms. In the case of fertilization with 8 kg of NPK, a significant increase of 20-30 mm of irrigated seedlings is observed compared to the non-irrigated variant and the norm of 10 mm. Under the effect of fertilization with 16 kg of NPK, irrigation showed a higher influence on the growth of seedlings, associated with significant differences between the three watering norms. Under the conditions of application of the dose of 24 kg of NPK, a small

and irregular variation is observed between the effects of different watering norms on the growth of seedlings of this variety. For the unfertilized seedlings of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, the application of irrigation allowed the achievement of significant increases in growth with values of 19-33 cm, respectively a significantly higher efficiency than the norm of 30 mm compared to that of 10 mm. Under the effect of fertilization with 8 kg of NPK, the seedlings of this variety efficiently capitalized on irrigation by 20-30 mm, registering significant growth increments of 19-43 cm compared to the other variants. Against the background of fertilization with 16 kg of NPK, only irrigation with 30 mm allowed a significant growth of seedlings by 28 cm, against the

background of irregular variations under the effect of the other watering norms. Under the conditions of fertilization with 24 kg of NPK, the saplings efficiently capitalized on the irrigation, registering significant increases in the stems of 19-49 cm compared to the non-irrigated version.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE REGENERATIVE AND ORGANOGENIC CAPACITY OF *ECHINOCACTUS (PFIFF.) MIHANOVICHII* EXPLANTS, IN THE PRESENCE IN THE CULTURE MEDIUM OF 2.5 mg/l OF 3-INDOLYL BUTYRIC ACID (IBA) AND 2.5 mg/l OF 2,4-DICHLOROPHENOXYACETIC ACID (2,4D)

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Echinocactus mihanovichii, cactus with a red epidermis is part of the group of chlorophyll-deficient cacti, the result of a spontaneous mutation, it survives only grafted being unable to synthesize chlorophyll.

In order to establish the *in vitro* culture of *Echinocactus mihanovichii*, we took explants, mini-shoots (seedlings) from mother plants grown in the greenhouse. We inoculated the explants on a culture medium consisting of macroelements and Fe EDTA Murashige-Skoog (1962), microelements Heller (1953) representing the control sample V_0 and supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 3-indolyl butyric acid (IBA), variant V_1 and 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D variant V_2 .

The evolution of the explants was monitored for 90 days, after which we noticed that the response of the *Echinocactus mihanovichii* explants differed depending on the composition of the culture medium, as follows: the explants grown on medium without growth regulators (V_0) had an increase, at the increase in the diameter of the phytoinoculi, by 25% compared to the values of the same parameter recorded in the V_1 variant (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l IBA) and by 31% compared to the V_2 variant (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D). Caulogenesis was manifested only in the explants of the control group V_0 (medium without growth regulators) recording an average number of 0.5 buds/variant with an average basal diameter of them of 0.4 cm.

Callus generation was determined by the presence in the culture medium of both 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2) with 0.5 callus/variant and a 50% increase compared to the control group V_0 (phytoinoculi grown on medium without growth regulators) and an average diameter of 2.0 cm which represents a 200% increase as well as 2.5 mg/l IBA (V_1) with 0.3 calluses/variant respectively a 30% increase and a diameter of 0.6 cm, so an increase of 60%.

It should be noted that, in this experiment, the rhizogenesis process did not occur in any variant.

Keywords: Explant, rhizogenesis, caulogenesis, callus, phytoinoculation.

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INTRODUCTION

Chlorophyll deficient cacti such as *Gymnocalycium mihanovichii* is a cactus with colored epidermis (fig.1), lacking the ability to synthesize chlorophyll due to the small number of chloroplasts, approximately 1/3 of all plastids (Shemorakov, 2003).

Figure.1. Image representing chlorophyll deficient cactus *Gymnocalycium mihanovichii*.

Pigmentation is caused by the spontaneous appearance of mutations in cultures largely influenced by temperature and

light (Shemorakov, 2003). According to Skulkin (2000), cacti kept at a lower than optimal temperature and in the shade develop such mutations less often or not at all.

The classification of chlorophyll-deficient cacti species was made according to the color of the epidermis (Shemorakov, 2003). According to Shemorakov (2001) the reversible mutation of plastids during meiosis keeps the generative reproduction of these species at a minimum level (Kornilova L.P., 2008) thus plants can keep their color only by cloning, a fact that determined the search for new and efficient methods of rapid multiplication and their economic (Son, 2000, Lee et al., 2003)

The aim of this experiment is to analyze the regenerative and organogenic capacity of the *Gymnocalycium mihanovichii* cactus grown in

in vitro on culture medium without growth regulators (V_0), but also in the presence of 2.5 mg/l 3-indolyl acid in the culture medium butyric (IBA) variant V_1 and of 2.5 mg/l 2,4 D, variant V_2 .

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material used in our experiments consisted of regenerated mini-cuttings (seedlings) on strains of *Gymnocalycium mihanovichii* (fig.2). The explants were about 1 cm long, 0.5 cm thick and 0.5-1.5 cm in diameter, depending on the area from which they were harvested (Fig. 2).

Figure.2. Schematic representation of the sampling of *Gymnocalycium mihanovichii* fragments that will be inoculated on aseptic media.

The vegetable material was aseptized by immersion, for one minute, in 96° ethyl alcohol, followed by its coating with 0,8% sodium hypochlorite solution, mixed with water in a ratio of 1:2; in the disinfectant solution was added - as a surfactant - three drops of Tween 20 each (Cachiță et al., 2004).

During aseptization, the vegetative material was stirred continuously (Cachiță et al., 2004). After 20 minutes, the disinfectant was removed and the plant material was washed with sterile distilled water, making five consecutive rinses, of five minutes each. Then, the vegetal material was deposited in aseptic conditions, in a hood with horizontal laminar flow, of sterile air, in operation, on the rounds of filter paper sterilized in the oven, introduced in aseptic Petri dishes. Subsequently, the necrotic parts of the future inocula were detached.

Culture medium used for growth explants consisted of: macro Murashige-Skoog EDTA and Fe (1962), Heller microelements (1953), mineral mixture to which was added vitamins: pyridoxine HCl, thiamine HCl and nicotinic acid (containing 1 mg/l each), m-Inositol - 100 mg/l, sucrose - 20 g/l and agar 7 g/l the pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.8, the first to autoclaving. In the basic medium (MB) we added 2.5 mg/l 3-indolyl butyric acid and 2.5 mg/l 2,4 D; obtaining the following experimental variants: V_0 - control variant,

medium without growth regulators, V_1 - 2.5 mg/l AIB and V_2 - 2.5 mg/l 2,4 D.

Culture medium thus obtained was placed in a glass vial with a capacity of 15 ml (each container was placed 5 ml of medium). Medium vials were sterilized by autoclaving for 30 minutes at a temperature of 121°C. After cooling media proceeded to inoculate explants, aseptic room operation performed in a laminar flow hood with sterile air. To obstruction fitoinoculi containers we used polyethylene, immobilized with elastic. Containers were inoculated Transferred to room for growth, under the following Conditions: temperature ranged from 24°C in the range of light and 20°C during the phase of darkness and light was the regime fotoperiodic 16 hours with light/24h, lighting Achieving cultures with the white light emitted by fluorescent lamps, the intensity of 1700 lux.

Explants and explants reaction progress was monitored for 90 days. In this time period were conducted periodic observations and readings every 30 days. Values thus obtained in the control group (V_0 , phyto inoculi grown on basic medium, without growth regulators) were considered the reference as 100% being reported - every trait - all readings averaged every experimental variant part.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After 90 days of culture in vitro, at the level of *Echinocactus mihanovichii* explants, it can be seen that the growth rate is different depending on the composition of the culture medium, thus the growth of the average basal diameter of the main stem was found to be much faster (1.6 cm) in the phytoinocula belonging to the control sample V_0 (medium without growth regulators) (Fig.4A), compared to those of the variant V_1 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l AIB) of 1.2 cm (Fig.4A) which represents a minus of 25% (Fig.5A) or 1.1 cm (Fig.) in the V_2 variant (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D), thus recording a deficit of 31% (Fig.5A).

These results, from a statistical point of view, are considered to be distinct significant (Table 1).

It is known that *Echinocactus mihanovichii* is a cactus that roots hard (Copăcescu V.S., 2001), although there are specimens that also live on their own roots; in the present experiment, it is noted that the phenomenon of rhizogenesis was not manifested in any variant studied, regardless of the composition of the

culture medium. These results are consistent with those obtained by Clayton et al. (1990), who, in a study of cockatiels of the genus *Mammillaria*, reported a complete lack of response to in vitro cultivation of *Mammillaria eichlamii* Quehl, a fact suggesting that each species of catfish may require a specific recipe vis-a-vis the composition of the culture medium (Johnson et al., 1981; Starling et al., 1983;

Vyskot et al., 1984, Martinez-Vázquez et al., 1989).

The experimental variant V_0 (medium without growth regulators) was the only sample in which the caulogenesis phenomenon was detected, recording an average number of 0.5 buds/variant (Fig. 4B), and an average basal diameter of them of 0.4 cm (Fig. 4C), the new buds keeping the red color of the initial explant (Fig. 3A).

Fig.3 . Inoculations of *Echinocactus* (Pfiiff.) *mihanovichii*, 90 days after inoculation of the explant "in vitro", where: A-on new modified basic medium without growth regulators (V_0); B,C-on basic medium with the addition of 2.5 mg/l AIB (V_1); C- D-on basic medium with the addition of 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D(V_2); (iiiv–initial viable inoculum; mc–culture medium; nc–caulinary neoformation; sp-thorns; ar-areola; cl–callus; zn-necrotic zone).

The presence in the culture medium of 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2) led to predictable results in terms of callus induction at the level of phytoinoculi grown on this nutrient substrate, thus a number of 0.5 calluses/variant (Fig. 4D), with an average diameter (measured in the widest area) of 2.0 cm (Fig. 4E), compared to 0.3 calluses/variant (Fig.4D) at inocula grown on culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l AIB (V_1) and an average diameter of 0.6

cm (Fig.4E). Percentage-wise, the data obtained show a 50% increase compared to the control in the number of calluses/variant in variant V_2 (the medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) and 30% in V_1 (the medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l AIB) there is also a 200% increase in the average callus diameter in V_2 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) and 60% in V_1 (medium supplemented with 2, 5 mg/l AIB

Table 1. The results of the biometric evaluations of the vitroplants of *Echinocactus mihanovichii*, performed 90 days after the inoculation of the explants on basic aseptic media (variant V₀) with the addition of 2.5 mg/l AIB (variant V₁) and 2.5 mg/l 2.4 D (variant V₂)

Parameter	The average length of the main stem		Significance	Average number of newly formed stems +/- Standard deviation		Significance	Average length of the largest newly formed stem +/- Standard deviation		Significance	Average number of new roots +/- Standard deviation		Significance	Average length of the largest newly formed root +/- Standard deviation		Significance	Average number of calluses +/- Standard deviation		Significance	The average diameter of calluses +/- Standard deviation		Significance
	Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance		Standard deviation	Significance	
Alternative																					
90 days																					
V ₀	1,10±0,31	0,0947	**	0	0		0	0		0	0		0	0		0	0		0	0	
V ₁	1,10±0,33	0,1084	**	0	0		0	0		0	0		0,30±0,26	0,0658	NS	0,60±0,38	0,1432	NS			
V ₂	1,10±0,24	0,0558	**	0	0		0	0		0	0		0,50±0,26	0,0658	***	2,00±0,84	0,7063				

Legend: *** very significant ** distinctly significant * significant NS insignificant

These results, from a statistical point of view, are considered to be distinct significant and very significant (Table 1).

Analyzing the images in figure 3, it can be seen that, after 90 days of in vitro culture, the *Echinocactus mihanovichii* inoculums, which remained alive, have grown and show well-developed areolae and spines, but the section

areas are necrotic, a phenomenon manifested by a change in color - these becoming brown. In the phytoinocules of the experimental variant V₀ (medium without growth regulators), the existence of some areas where their initial color has changed, from red turned to a brick, even orange with a yellow tinge, can be seen (Fig.3).

Fig. 4 Graphic presentation of the average values corresponding to the parameters read at the level of in vitro cultures of *Echinocactus mihanovichii*, on basic aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V₀) - with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB (variant V₁) and of 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (variant V₂), data expressed in absolute values; (where: A-average diameter of the main stem; B-average number of newly formed strains; C-average diameter of the largest newly formed stem; D-average number of calluses; E-average diameter of calluses).

It can be observed (fig.3) that the callus generated by the inocula grown on medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4 D (V_2) is located only on their surface, is white in color, and appears in the form of crystals, similarly, the total absence of thorns is seen, a fact probably due to the "defoliating" action of 2,4-D auxin (Vidican I.T., 2012).

At the level of explants grown on medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l AIB (V_1), both the absence of spines and a red callus can be noted (Fig.3). According to Cachiță et al, (2004), the red coloration or shades of red of the callus is

due to a very high content of anthocyanins, which accumulate in its cells due to its growth regime, species, origin and age; in the present case, this pigmentation may also be influenced by the red color of the epidermis of the chlorophyll-deficient cactus *Echinocactus mihanovichii* (Vidican, et al., 2018). A red, compact callus, formed on the cut surface of the explants, was also obtained in some species of *Mammillaria*, the color being due to the presence of beta alanine in its cells (Pérez et al., 2002).

Fig.4. The graphic presentation in percentages of the values corresponding to the monitored parameters at the level of vitro cultures of *Echinocactus mihanovichii*, on basic aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V_0) - with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB (variant V_1) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (variant V_2), data expressed as a percentage, obtained after reporting the analyzed values to the results recorded at the respective parameters read in the control group (V_0), without growth regulators, values considered to be 100%; (where: A- average diameter of the main stem; B - average number of newly formed strains; C- average diameter of the largest newly formed stem; D-average number of calluses; E-average diameter of calluses).

CONCLUSIONS

Following the reaction and evolution of *Echinocactus mihanovichii* phytoinoculi, for 90 days, from the values recorded both in the control batch V_0 (medium without growth regulators) and considered as reference, as regulators (V_0) with an absolute value of 1.6 cm compared to 1.2 cm in V_1 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l AIB) which represents a minus of 25% and 1.1 cm at V_2 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D), where a deficit of 31%

Caulogenesis was manifested only in the explants of the control group V_0 (medium without growth regulators).

Callus generation was determined by the presence in the culture medium of both 2.5 ml/l 2,4-D (V_2) with 0.5 callus/variant and a 50%

100%, as well as in the other experimental variants the existence of significant differences in their way of reaction was found.

A constant increase in the diameter of the inoculums was noted in the case of all the experimental variants, especially those cultivated on medium without growth increase compared to the control group V_0 (phytoinoculi grown on medium without growth regulators) and an average diameter of 2.0 cm, which represents a 200% increase as well as 2.5 mg/l AIB (V_1) with 0.3 calluses/variant, respectively, an increase of 30% and with a diameter of 0.6 cm, so an increase of 60%.

The phenomenon of rhizogenesis was not manifested in any of the studied experimental variants, within this experiment.

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ASPECTS REGARDING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ACACIA ON THE STERILE DUMPS FROM RECEA ȘUNCUIUȘ QUARRY, BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The ecological reconstruction of Recea Quarry will require great costs and efforts. In this paper, the success of the plantings in 2016 with acacia seedlings was analyzed. Thus, the survival rate of the seedlings planted six years ago was determined, their diameters and heights were measured by slope category, establishing twelve sample plots. Although it is observed that the diameters and heights are larger on the average slope compared to the flat and highly inclined terrain, from a statistical point of view the differences are insignificant. Regarding the survival rate of the planted seedlings, it has mean values of approx. 50%. The paper also shows the advantages of planting acacia species on these lands where the clay was extracted and recommendations are made to have better results in the future.

Keywords: (ecologic reconstruction, acacia, survival rate, seedlings, clay quarry)

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INTRODUCTION

Ecological reconstruction is the process by which a degraded, damaged or destroyed ecosystem is restored. Sometimes, it also involves the reintroduction of some new species. (<https://wwf.ro/ce-facem/apedulci/reconstructie-ecologica/>)

Such lands are also found in Șuncuiuș-Zece Hotare area where the clay ore extractive industry experienced a large scale development in the second half of the 20th century. In order to identify the clay deposits, drilling was carried out, and their exploitation was done in two ways: by practicing mining and in the quarry, on the surface, this method greatly affecting the environment. The production of refractory clay in the period 1949-1989 evolved from 43,000 tons in 1949 to 328,700 tons in 1989, in the following period having a downward evolution, reaching 100,000 tons in 1998.

Șuncuiuș refractory clay deposit is located in the northern part of Pădurea Craiului Mountains and the exploitation perimeter is divided into two sectors: Recea, with an area of 2.89 km² and Bălnaca, with an area of 0.75 km².

The dumping of the sterile material is done by tipping from the tipper truck onto the storage surface, in small, tangent piles with a height of 1-2 m, which are leveled and compacted with a bulldozer. A technological compaction is performed after the formation of the deposits with a thickness of 45 m.

The plan to restore the environment as a consequence of the refractory clay exploitation activity in Șuncuiuș perimeter requires the mechanized leveling of the land and the planting of forest seedlings.

At the request of S.C. Bega Minerale Industriale S.A., ICAS Brașov (Forest Research and Management Institute, Brașov) drew up a project for the arrangement and stabilization of some inactive landfills through forest phytoamelioration in 2006. Flowering ash and sycamore were proposed in the afforestation composition, which so far has proven to be an inappropriate choice because the seedlings planted in 2007 disappeared almost completely until now (***,2015). Scots pine and black pine seedlings were planted in 2008-2009 and were more successful.

The good percentage of gripping, the high ability to fix the land with a steep slope, the possibility of improving the soil through the

litter that decomposes easily, the possibility of retaining atmospheric nitrogen, but also thanks to the qualities of the wood, the high production of biomass led to the realization of this research study regarding the installation of acacia on these degraded lands from the clay quarry.

The main naturally regenerated tree species on the sterile dump are birch (*Betula pendula Roth.*), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), trembling poplar (*Populus tremula L.*), Silesian willow (*Salix silesiaca*), acacia (*Robinia pseudacacia L.*), wild apple (*Malus sylvestris Mill.*), wild pear (*Pyrus pyraster (L.) Burgsd.*) and among the shrubs the hairy brumble (*Rubus hirtus W. et K.*), the rose hip (*Rosa canina L.*), common hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna Jack.*) and common juniper (*Juniperus communis L.*).

From its beginnings, in Romania (1852), acacia proved to be a providential species for the afforestation of the shifting sands, fixing coasts and slopes and in plantations on degraded lands, and later, as the main species in the forest curtains in the steppe and silvo regions -steppe, for the protection of fields and in the snow curtains along roads and railways (Ciuvăț, 2013). It is also considered a tree of great value, used almost exclusively for ameliorative forest plantations on the sands and light, non-calcareous soils in the warm areas of the south of the country (Doniță and Radu, 2013; Amos News, 2003).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research and measurements took place between August and October 2022, in the perimeter of Recea Dump (2008), near the towns of Șuncuiș and Zece Hotare, from the commune of Șuncuiș, Bihor County, in the northern part of Pădurea Craiului Mountains.

In 2016, acacia seedlings were planted on 2008 dump and on the plateau, which proved to be quite a good option as they gripped in good proportion, problems existing only in the locations with excessive moisture.

Approximately 10,000 acacia seedlings were planted, from Carei, Satu Mare county. The planting scheme was 2 m between rows x 1 m between plants per row, a scheme recommended for pure acacia (Florescu, 1994). These plantings were carried out on previously unprepared soils, the size of the pit, type of soil, the method of making the pits, of course, also influencing the rate of gripped seedlings (Noja et al., 2015; Budău & Timofte, 2016).

The factor analyzed in this paper was the slope, denoted by:

- P1 the test surfaces located on the slope with a gradient below 5°;
- P2 the test surfaces located on the slope with a gradient between 5° și 15°;
- P3 the test surfaces located on the slope with a gradient above 15°.

Recea Dump has approx. 50ha, and the acacia seedlings were planted mainly in the northern part of the quarry.

For each category of slope (variant P1, P2, P3) 4 repetitions (S1-S4) were placed, resulting in 12 square-like test surfaces of 10m x 10m, located according to table no.1 and figure no.1.

In each sample plots, the entire trees were inventoried and measurements of the following characteristics were performed:

- the survival rate of seedlings at the age of 6, expressed in number of specimens and %;
- the height of the seedlings (m) from the ground level to the top of the axis or to the highest point of a frame;
- the diameter of the seedlings in the package (cm);
- other observations: the number of acacia sprouts and root-shoots, edaphic observations, the number of branches in the first 10 cm from the ground, other naturally installed species and the number of specimens.

The trunk diameter was measured with the electronic caliper (fig. 2a), and the height with the tape measure or with a graduated telescopic rod (fig. 2b).

Table 1

Location and elevation of sample plots			
SLOPE	Sample Plot Code	Coordinates, (Latitude, Longitude)	Altitude, m
P ₁ <5°	S ₁ P ₁	46°55'18.9" N 22°30'39.9" E	678
	S ₂ P ₁	46°55'10.5" N 22°30'35.7" E	721
	S ₃ P ₁	46°55'15.7" N 22°30'40.1" E	703
	S ₄ P ₁	46°55'24.9" N 22°30'40.4" E	664
P ₂ [5°, 15°)	S ₁ P ₂	46°55'20.3" N 22°30'39.4" E	671
	S ₂ P ₂	46°55'10.1" N 22°30'36.2" E	717
	S ₃ P ₂	46°55'16.8" N 22°30'39.4" E	698
	S ₄ P ₂	46°55'27.5" N 22°30'44.9" E	665
P ₃ ≥15°	S ₁ P ₃	46°55'20.7" N 22°30'40.6" E	676
	S ₂ P ₃	46°55'10.3" N 22°30'38.8" E	715
	S ₃ P ₃	46°55'16.5" N 22°30'40.1" E	694
	S ₄ P ₃	46°55'21.6" N 22°30'38.9" E	669

Figure 1 Location of the study and sample plots (<https://goo.gl/maps/aXgK5EUZ5b4BABbt5>)

Figure 2 Diameter measurement with a caliper (a) and of the tree height with a tape measure (b)

For the analyzed characters (maintenance degree, plant height, diameter in the package) the arithmetic mean was determined using the well-known formula $x = \Sigma x/N$.

To determine the survival rate after 6 years, the following formula was used:

$$G_m(\%) = \frac{P_{viab}}{P_{veg}} \cdot 100$$

in which: P_{veg} represents planted seedlings (50 pcs);

P_{viab} - existing seedlings after 6 years.

The results obtained following the performance of biometric determinations on the mentioned characters, were statistically processed through the analysis of variance, specific to the monofactorial experiments

performed in randomized blocks, the significance of the differences between the two tested varieties being established with the help of the LD test and the "t" test (Student), (Ardelean et al., 2002).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Regarding the survival rate six years after the planting of the acacia saplings under study, the data mentioned in table 2 show that out of 50 seedlings planted in 2016 per 100 square meters, only 22 survived in sample area S1P2 (the fewest) and 31 specimens in S1P3 (the most) the fall of 2022. Thus, the survival rate is between 44% and 62%.

Table 2
Number of plants and survival rate after 6 years after planting

Variant, (slope categories)	Number of plants/ survival rate for the sample plot			
	S1	S2	S3	S4
P1	24/48	24/48	22/44	23/46
P2	22/44	25/50	26/52	27/54
P3	31/62	24/48	26/52	25/50

According to figure 3, it can be seen that the survival rate of the planted seedlings increases linearly with the slope of the land, registering a percentage of 53% in the case of the lands with a steep slope of over 15°.

Figure 3 Representation of the means of the four repetitions in terms of the survival rate of the planted seedlings

These losses can be considered normal because, for acacia, in specialized works based on rigorous experiences (Costea et al., 1996), the survival rate in the first years after planting in the field varied between 19% and 94%, the values obtained in the study carried out falling between the respective limits.

If we also take into account the sprouts and root-shoots that appeared during the six years on the twelve sample areas, the average number of acacia specimens becomes:

- on the small slope (P1): 27;
- on the small slope (P1): 31.25;
- on the small slope (P1): 27.75,

which implies a 7.5% increase in acacia specimens through sprouting and root-shooting.

Regarding their mean root neck, the measured values are centralized in Table 2. For the first three analyzed surfaces, the diameters were between:

- for S1P1: 1.9-8.0cm, with a coefficient of variability of this character of 36.3%, which

places the variability of that character in the "very high" class;

- for S1P2: 2.3- 6.2cm, s%= 27.1%) which falls into the "large" class of variability;

- for S1P3: 2.1-8.0cm, s%= 54.1%, which falls into the "very high" class of variability.

Table 3
Values of average diameters measured (diameter) after 6 years from planting

Variant, (slope categories)	Mean diameter for the sample plot..., in cm			
	S1	S2	S3	S4
P1	4.75	4.85	4.09	2.95
P2	4.15	5.48	3.79	4.38
P3	3.34	4.98	3.79	4.52

It can be observed that for all the three categories of slope, there is a large and very large variability in terms of the dimensions of the root neck, expressed by the values of the coefficients of variability.

The synthesis results regarding the differences between the mean root neck are presented in Table 4 and the differences between the average heights of the seedlings after 6 years from planting according to the three categories of slope on which they were planted, as well as the interpretation of these results separately for each slope category are presented in Table 6.

Table 4
Effects of the land slope on the mean root neck diameter of trees after six years of vegetation

Name of variant	Mean root neck Ø (cm)	% compared to P1	±d (cm)	Significance of difference
P1 - sample	4.16	100.0	-	-
P2	4.45	107.0	0.29	-
P3	4.16	100.0	0.00	-

DL/LSD 5 % = 1.1
DL/LSD 1 % = 1.7
DL/LSD 0.1 % = 2.8

Thus, although the root neck diameter values remain higher by 7% in option 2 (slope 5-15°) compared to those recorded in variants 1 and 3, statistically the differences between the three variants are insignificant.

Regarding the average height, the measured values are centralized in Table 5. For the first 3 analyzed surfaces, the variation amplitude (A) for the heights was:

- for S1P1: A=3.5m, with a variability coefficient for this character of 35.6%, which places the variability of that character in the "very high" class;

- for S1P2: A=3.4m, s%= 34.9%, which falls into the "very high" class of variability;
- for S1P3: A=3.4m, s%= 52.3%) which falls into the "very high" class of variability.

It can be observed that for all the three slope categories, there is a very large variability in terms of the value of tree heights, expressed by the values of the variability coefficients.

Table 5
Values of average heights measured (hm) after 6 years from planting

Variant, (slope categories)	Mean heights for the sample plot..., in m			
	S1	S2	S3	S4
P1	3.23	3.30	2.73	1.99
P2	2.69	3.56	3.37	2.88
P3	2.42	3.54	2.05	3.41

Table 6
Effect of the land slope on the tree heights after six years of vegetation

Name of variant	Mean heights	% compared to P1	±d (cm)	Significance of difference
P1 - sample	2.81	100.0	-	-
P2	3.12	111.1	0.31	-
P3	2.85	101.6	0.04	-

DL/LSD 5 % = 1.0
DL/LSD 1 % = 1.5
DL/LSD 0.1 % = 2.5

Thus, statistically, the differences between the three variants are insignificant, although the tree height values remain higher by 11.1% in variant 2 (slope 5-15°) compared to those recorded in variant 1.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the statistical analysis, it was found that the slope does not significantly influence the survival rate of the plants after 6 years, neither the diameter nor the height of the seedlings. However, it is observed that on the medium slope (5-15°) the diameters and heights of the seedlings are larger.

The ecological reconstruction of the degraded lands from Recea Quarry is a challenge because on the planted areas a reduction of surface and deep erosion processes was found.

Planting the areas that are not naturally regenerated is necessary and appropriate to restore the respective area, especially since a large part of these areas are located on very steep slopes exposed to erosion phenomena. On

such lands, the acacia gave results, but on flat lands with excess moisture it gave poor results, as was the case with sample plots S4P1 and S3P1. Excess moisture is the factor that most negatively influences the acacia cultures on the degraded lands from Recea quarry. An increased erosion and with less good results was found in S3P3, the average diameters and heights being smaller. From the analysis of the situation encountered in the sample plots, it follows that the slopes with sunny exposure are more favorable for acacia than the shaded ones (case S2P3).

Recommendations:

- Avoid planting acacia on lands with excess moisture;
- Creating terraces around the seedlings when they are planted on land located on a steep slope;
- Provision in the environmental restoration plan for the use of a layer of topsoil that must be set aside at the time of land-stripping;
- Application of the planting scheme in "chincons" (each seedling in a row is placed near the middle of the distance between two seedlings of the neighbouring row) on the sloping lands to reduce the erosion process on the surface and avoid the formation of drainage ditches

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COENOTAXONOMY AND CHOROLOGY OF THE STANDS DEVELOPED BY *THE PULMONARIO RUBRAE-FAGETUM, SYRINGETOSUM JOSIKAEAE* COMMUNITY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The tree stands with *Syringa josikaea* from the Apuseni Mountains were studied from the perspective of the floristic composition of the phytocenosis *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum Täuber 1987-syringetosum josikaeae*, Burescu L., 2018, which brings together a total of 91 cormophyte species in the synthetic association table.

The analysis of ecological categories by lifeforms highlights the share of hemicryptophyte elements (49.4%) followed by phanerophytes (22.8%), and geophytes (17.5%).

The analysis of the ecological categories by the genetic center of origin and the geographical area shows the dominance of Eurasian species (32.9%) followed by Circumpolar-Boreal (15.3%), European (15.3%), Central-European (10.9%), Carpathian, and Carpatho-Balkan (7.5%) species.

The tree stands with *Syringa josikaea* included in the *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum – syringetosum josikaeae* association have a high conservation value, bringing together rare, endangered, endemic, relict species, characteristic of an endemic habitat found only in the Apuseni Mountains.

Keywords: spruce-beech-fir forest, phytocenoses, ecological classification.

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INTRODUCTION

Among the 30 species of the *Syringa* genus spread today across Iran, Afghanistan, the Himalayas, China, Japan, and Eastern Europe, the tertiary relict *Syringa josikaea* an endemic species for the Western Carpathians in Romania and the Northern Carpathians in Ukraine is of interest.

The shrub *Syringa josikaea* J.Jack. ex Rchb.fil. also known as the Hungarian lilac, forms distinct thickets at the border of beech, and spruce-beech-fir forest stands on the upper course of the narrow mountain valleys in the Apuseni Mountains, Iadului Valley, Crișul Negru Valley, and Aries Valley. From the literature (Vlad et al. (2013)) the species could still be found either cultivated or spontaneous in the Crișul Repede river basin Ciucea, Negreni, Sacuieu Cluj County, Metaliferi Mountains (on Vulcan Mountain), which in fact was not confirmed in the field, the plant basic habitat consisting of Iadului Valley, Crișul Negru Valley, and Aries Valley.

In-depth research on the ecology, coenotaxonomy and chorology of the beech, and spruce-beech stands including and sheltering the *Syringa josikaea* thickets has not been done before except for flora and vegetation (Rațiu et al. 1984), to find and describe rare, endangered

forest ecosystems of high conservation values (Burescu L. 2015, 2018, 2021).

The goal of our research work is to carry out an integrated study of the forest areas in the Apuseni Mountains sheltering *Syringa josikaea* - a tertiary relict and endemic Carpathian species from a coenotaxonomic, ecological, eco-protective and chorological standpoint within the territory.

In order to achieve the proposed research goal, we set ourselves to attain the following objectives:

- Floristic inventory of forest areas - management units that include and protect the *Syringa josikaea* species,
- Study of the structure of the phytocenoses of *Syringa josikaea* stands and thickets with the inclusion of the species in the *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* association *Syringetosum josikaeae* subassociation by their belonging to the coenotaxa suballiance, alliance, order and vegetation class,
- Ecological characterization of the species found in terms of their distribution by the type of lifeform, and phytogeographical elements

- Sustainable management of *Syringa josikaea* shrublet forests by adopting appropriate forest management.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research material consists of the phytocoenoses of the association *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum*, Täuber 1987 – *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu L. 2018, which gathers the beech, and spruce-beech-fir forest stands with *Syringa josikaea* from the Iadului Valley river basin, Remeti forest district, Bihor County, Management unit IV Iadolina technically on the right bank of Forest compartment 93B Dealul Mare, area: 7.7 ha, altitude: 750m; Forest compartment 95A Iadolina Waterfall, area: 5.4 ha, altitude: 850m; Forest compartment 95B Dealul Mare Gorge, area: 13.9 ha, altitude: 860m; Forest compartment 96A Iadolina Waterfall, area: 1.3 ha, altitude: 880m; Forest compartment 108A Calea Laii, area: 22.7 ha, altitude: 900m; Forest compartment V Iadului Valley technically on the left bank; parcels of Forest compartment 66A Iadolina Waterfall; area: 8.7 ha, altitude: 750m; Forest compartment 70A Iadolina Waterfall, area: 3.0 ha, altitude: 710m; Forest compartment 74 Dealul Mare Hill opposite to the Rustic House Tourist Lodge, area: 37 ha, altitude: 640m; Forest compartment 78B Savoii, area: 4.0 ha, altitude: 610m; Forest compartment 82A Vâlcei sub Cruce, area: 8.8 ha, altitude: 590m.

Moreover, the biological material subjected to research consisted in the arboretum included in the *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987 cenosis, the sub-association *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu L. 2018, on the upper course of the Crisul Negru river, Sudrigiu Forest district, Bihor county, Management unit VI Poiana, Forest compartment 91A, area: 13.8 ha, altitude: 644m; Forest compartment 91B, area: 2.2ha, altitude: 684m; Forest compartment 95C, area: 27.2 ha, altitude: 626m; as well as the arboretum within the Aries Valley, Garda Forest district, Alba county, Management unit I Magura, Forest compartment 259A, area: 27.2 ha, altitude: 756m; Horea Apuseni Forest district, Management unit I Neagra, Forest compartment 370, area: 0.2 ha, altitude: 794m.

Phytocenological surveys were carried out in the forest compartments subjected to research, and the plant species found were inputted in a synthetic table of the association with the assessment of abundance-dominance

by coefficients according to the Braun-Blanquet scale (1964) which expresses the degree of soil cover and consistency coefficients (K) expressing the frequency of species throughout the territory (see Table 1).

According to the scientific data from the synthetic table of association, the tree stands (beech, beech-spruce, spruce-beech-beech stands) with *Syringa josikaea* were analysed ecologically, cenotaxonomically, bioeconomically and ecoprotectively, while highlighting the distribution of phytocenosis species by life forms, the type of geoelement with the presentation of the results in the form of spectra in histograms. The classification of species by the type of life forms was done according to the system developed by Raunkiaer (1937) and subsequently improved by Braun-Blanquet (1964) and with regard the types of geoelements according to the classification adopted by Meusel et Jäger (1992).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tree stands with *Syringa josikaea* thickets grow on various rocks, conglomerates, crystalline schists, especially flysch, on phreatic-moist meso-eubasic soils with a Ph ranging between 5.8-7.5.

They colonize limited areas of forests, in sites at altitudes of 626-684m, on Crisul Negru Valley, at 756-794m on Aries Valley, at 750-900m on Iadului Valley, being characterized by a temperate-montane climate (average annual temperatures of 7°C in Crisul Negru Valley, 6°C in Aries Valley, and 5.5° in Iadului Valley), and average annual precipitation of 800-1,000mm.

The floristic inventory of *Syringa josikaea* stands totals 91 cormophyte species, which means a high biodiversity considering the environmental conditions present in the sites of the mountain-boreal floor of the Western Carpathians.

With regard the coenotaxonomic classification of the species in the stands with *Syringa josikaea* in the community *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987 – *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu L. 2018, the author of the sub-association reviewed the scientific works published in Romania by the authors Boşcaiu et al. 1982, Coldea 1991, Sanda et al. 1999, Donita et al. 2005, Sanda et al. 2007, 2008, Chifu et al. 2014, which he compared with those published in Europe by Klika 1936, Tüxen 1955, Jurko 1964, Mayer 1974, Oberdorfer 1992, Mucina et al. 1993, Pott 1995, Mucina 1997, Rodwell et al.

2002, Borhidi 2003 and came to the conclusion that the phytocoenoses of the association from the Carpathians of Romania cannot be included in similar phytocoenoses from the Western Carpathians of Europe, due to the differences in terms of structure and floristic composition, as is the case with the species characteristic of the South-east Carpathian spruce, beech and fir forests with *Syringa josikaea* growing in Romania.

The characteristic species of *Syringa josikaea* tree stands such as *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Symphytum cordatum*, *Dentaria glandulosa*, *Hieracium transsylvanicum*, *Leucanthemum waldsteinii*, *Euphorbia carniolica*, *Campanula abietina* led the author to describe the Carpathian association *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987, the regional sub-association *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu L. 2018 which is specific to the Western Carpathians. The *syringetosum josikaeae* sub-association has in its floristic composition a strong core made of 14 species (i.e. *Syringa josikaea*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Abies alba*, *Picea abies*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Hieracium transsylvanicum*, *Leucanthemum waldsteinii*, *Silene heuffelii*, *Symphytum cordatum*, *Dentaria glandulosa*) characteristic and differentiated for coenotaxa **Symphyto-Fagenion**, **Symphyto cordati-Fagion** (see Table 1). Along these latter species, the floristic composition of the association includes 22 species characteristic to the order **Fagetalia sylvaticae** (i.e. *Rubus hirtus*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Galium odoratum*, *Calamagrostis arundinacea*), 18 species characteristic to the class **Querco-Fagetea** (i.e. *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Corylus avellana*, *Ulmus glabra*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Spiraea chamaedryfolia*, *Betula pendula*, *Salix capraea*, *Poa nemoralis*, *Galium schultesii*, *Doronicum austriacum*, *Filipendula*

ulmaria) as well as transgressive species belonging to other vegetation classes i.e. **Betulo-Adenostyletea** (10 species), **Vaccinio-Piceetea** (nine species), **Epilobietea angustifolii**, **Asplenietea trichomanis**.

The layer of trees with a general coverage of 64% is dominated by *Fagus sylvatica*, *Picea abies*, *Abies alba* in which *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Ulmus glabra*, *Carpinus betulus*, in which *Sorbus aucuparia* also participate. The compaction degree of the tree crown ranges between 0.6-0.7, the diameters of the tree trunks between 30-80 cm, and the height between 18-24m

The bush layer is dominated by *Syringa josikaea* with an overall coverage of 5.6%, accompanied by *Corylus avellana*, *Spiraea chamaedryfolia*, *Salix capraea*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Sambucus racemosa*, *Lonicera nigra*, *Lonicera xylosteum*, *Rosa pendulina*, *Daphne mezereum*, and *Clematis alpina*.

The grass layer with a general coverage of 26% consists of 69 species among which we mention *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Polystichum aculeatum*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Galium odoratum*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Luzula luzuloides*, *Gentiana asclepiadea*, *Galeopsis tetrahit* (see Table 1).

Analysis of the phytocenosis of *Syringa josikaea* stands shows us that in the spectrum of eco-diversity of life forms hemicryptophytes are dominant (49.4%) followed by phanerophytes (23.8%) of which (MPh=10.9%, mPh=7.6%, nPh=4.3%, l-nPh=1%), geophytes (17.5%), chamaephytes (3.2%) as ecological categories best adapted to a temperate-continental excessively mountainous climate (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The spectrum of lifeforms from the association *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987- *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu, L. 2018

Table 1

**Coenotaxonomic diversity and ecology of forests developed by *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987-
syringetosum josikaeae Burescu L., 2018, in Apuseni Mountains**

Bio	E.f.	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Compartments			93B	95A	95B	96A	108A	66A	70A	74	78B	82A	91A	91B	95C
Management units			Management unit IV Iadolina					Management unit V Iadului Valley					Management unit VI Poiana		
		Altitude (mamsl)	750	850	860	880	900	750	710	640	610	590	644	684	626
		Exposure	V	V	SV	V	V	E	E	E	NE	E	N	N	N
		Slope (°)	38	45	40	45	46	45	45	33	41	40	28	45	45
		Tree height (m)	18	25	24	25	26	28	18	25	18	18	18	20	22
		Tree diameter (m)	60	80	80	60	80	50	60	60	80	100	30	34	42
		Canopy density degree	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.9	0.8	0.7
		Grass layer (%)	35	20	40	20	40	30	40	50	40	35	20	40	45
		Area (ha)	7.7	5.4	13.9	1.3	22.7	8.7	3.0	37	4.0	8.8	13.8	2.2	27.2
MPh	E	<i>As. Fagus sylvatica</i>	4	2	3	3	3	3	2	5	4	3	3	3	4
MPh	Ec	<i>As. Abies alba</i>	+	3	2	1	2	+	2	.	.	.	+	.	+
H	Carp-B	<i>As. Pulmonaria rubra</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	+	+	+
mPh	End	<i>Subas. Syringa josikaeae</i>	+	1	1	+	1	1	1	+	+	2	1	2	1
Symphyto-Fagenion, Symphyto cordati-Fagenion															
MPh	Ec	<i>Acer psedoplatanus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	1	+
G(H)	E-M	<i>Festuca drymeja</i>	2	+	2	.	2	.	.	+	+	+	+	+	2
H	E	<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	.	1	.	.	.	+	+	+
H	Carp-B	<i>Hieracium transsylvanicum</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	+
G	End	<i>Dentaria glanduligera</i>	.	.	+	.	+
H(G)	End	<i>Symphytum cordatum</i>	.	.	+	.	+
H	Carp	<i>Leucanthemum waldsteini</i>	.	+	.	.	+	.	+
H	Ec	<i>Veronica urticifolia</i>	+	+	.	.	+
Ch	Alp-E	<i>Saxifraga cuneifolia</i>	+	1	+	.	+
H	Ec	<i>Aconitum vulparia ssp. lasianthum</i>	.	+	.	+	.	.	+
H	Alp-Carp-B	<i>Euphorbia carniolica</i>	+	+
TH	Carp-B	<i>Silene heuffelii</i>	.	.	+	.	+
G	Cp	<i>Phyllitis scolopendrium</i>	+	+	.
Fagetalia sylvaticae															
nPh	Eua	<i>Rubus hirtus</i>	+	+	+	+	1	1	3	.	+	+	+	+	+
H(G)	Eua	<i>Asarum europaeum</i>	+	+	1	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	+
H(G)	Cp	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	+
G(H)	E	<i>Mercurialis perennis</i>	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	+	+
H(Ch)	Ec	<i>Lamium galeobdolon</i>	+	+	1	1	+	+	.	.	.	+	+	+	+
H	Eua	<i>Senecio germanicus</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.
G	Eua	<i>Galium odoratum</i>	+	+	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	+	+	.	.
Th-TH	Cosm	<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	+	+
H	E	<i>Stellaria nemorum</i>	+	+	+
H	Eua(C)	<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i>	.	+	+	.	+	1	+	.	.	2	+	.	1
Th	E	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i>	.	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	+
G	Ec	<i>Symphytum tuberosum</i>	+	.	.	.	+
H	Eua	<i>Sanicula europaea</i>	.	+	+

Table 1 - Continuation

Bio	E.f.	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
H	Eua	<i>Epilobium montanum</i>	.	+	+
H	Eua	<i>Salvia glutinosa</i>	.	+	+
H	Eua	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	.	+	+	.	.	.	+
Th	Eua	<i>Impatiens noli-tangere</i>	+	+	.	.	.
H	Cp	<i>Milium effusum</i>	+	.	+
G	Eua	<i>Lilium martagon</i>	+
G	Cp	<i>Gymnocarpium dryopteris</i>	.	.	.	+	+
G	Eua	<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i>	.	.	.	+	+
nPh	Eua	<i>Daphne mezereum</i>	+
Quercio-Fagetea															
H	Cosm	<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	+	.	.	.
mPh	Balc	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	+	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	1	1	+	.	+
H	Cosm	<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>	1	+	+	1	1	+	+	.	.	+	+	+	+
MPh	Eua	<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	+	+	+	+	+	1	.	+
mPh	Eua	<i>Spiraea chamaedrifolia</i>	.	+	.	+	.	+	+	.	2	1	.	.	.
MPh	E	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	+	.	+	+	1	+	2	2	+
MPh	Eua	<i>Betula pendula</i>	.	+	.	+	.	+
nPh	Ec	<i>Rosa pendulina</i>	+	.	.	+	+	+	.	+	.
mPh	Eua	<i>Salix capraea</i>	.	+	+	.	+
H	Cp	<i>Poa nemoralis</i>	.	+	+	.	1	1	+	.	+
H(G)	Eua	<i>Melica nutans</i>	+	+	+
H	Eua	<i>Campanula persicifolia</i>	.	+	+	.	+
G	Ec	<i>Galium schultesii</i>	.	+	+	.	+
H	Eua	<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	.	.
G	E	<i>Doronicum austriacum</i>	+	+	+
mPh	Eua	<i>Lonicera xylosteum</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+
H	E	<i>Pulmonaria officinalis</i>	+	+	.	.	.
H	Eua(C)	<i>Sedum telephium ssp. maxima</i>	+	+	.	.	.
Vaccinio-Piceetea															
MPh	E	<i>Picea abies</i>	.	1	+	2	1	+	1	.	1	+	1	+	2
H	E	<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	+	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	+	.	.	.	2
MPh	E	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	.	+	.	+	+	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	.
MPh	Eua	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	.	+	.	+	.	+	+
mPh	Alp(E)	<i>Lonicera nigra</i>	.	+	.	+	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.
Ch	Cp	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	+	1
l-nPh	Act-Alp-E	<i>Clematis alpina</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+
H	Cp	<i>Dryopteris dilatata</i>	+	.	1
H	Cp	<i>Campanula abietina</i>
Betulo-Adenostyletea															
G	Alp-Carp-B	<i>Doronicum columnae</i>	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	.
H	Ec	<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	.
G	Eua	<i>Petasites hybridus</i>	.	+	+	.	+
H	Carp-B-Cauc-Anat	<i>Telekia speciosa</i>	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	+
H	Eua	<i>Heracleum sphondylium</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+
H	Ec	<i>Digitalis grandiflora</i>	.	+	+
TH-H	Eua(Bor)	<i>Angelica archangelica</i>	+
H	Carp-B	<i>Trollius europaeus</i>	+
H	Alp-Carp-B	<i>Achillea distans</i>	+
nPh	Cp	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	+	.	.	.	+	+	+	.	+
Asplenietea trichomanis															
H	Cosm	<i>Asplenium trichomanes</i>	.	+	+	.	+
H	Carp	<i>Campanula kladniana</i>	.	+	+	.	+
G	Cp	<i>Polypodium vulgare</i>	.	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	+	+	+
Alnetea glutinosae															
H	Cp	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	+	+	.	.	+	.	+	.
Ch	Eua	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i>	+	.	.	.
(nPh)															
Epilobietea angustifolii															
mPh	Cp	<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	.	+	+
MPh	E	<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	1	+	+	+	.
H	Cp	<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	.	+	+	.	+
H	Cosm	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	1	+	+
Variae syntaxa															
G	Eua	<i>Polygonatum odoratum</i>	+	+	+	+	.	.	.
H	Eua	<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	.	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.
G	Cp	<i>Equisetum telmateia</i>	+	.	+
H	Eua	<i>Ranunculus repens</i>	+	+
H	E	<i>Lunaria rediviva</i>	.	.	+	+	.
H	End	<i>Phyteuma tetramerum</i>	.	+

The following were included in a single survey: *Hypericum montanum* (1, Compartment 93B), *Aconitum callibotrio* (1, Compartment 93B), *Carex brizoides* (1, Compartment 93B), *Fraxinus excelsior* (1, Compartment 93B), *Angelica sylvestris* (1, Compartment 93B), *Lamium maculatum* (1, Compartment 93B), *Molinia caerulea* (1, Compartment 93B), *Mycelis muralis* (3, Compartment 85B), *Melittis melissophyllum* (5, Compartment 108A), *Senecio doria* (6, Compartment 66A), *Luzula sylvatica* (10, Compartment 82A), *Salix eleagnos* (10, Compartment 82A), *Lamium purpureum* (11, Compartment 91A), *Vaccinium vitis idaea* (4, Compartment 259A). Location and date of surveying: 1-5 Iadului Valley, right bank, Management unit IV Iadolina Remeți Forestry district, Bihor County (04.09.2022), 6-10 Iadului Valley, left bank, Management unit V Iadului Valley, Remeți Forest district, Bihor County (06.05.2021), 11-13 Crișul Negru Valley, upstream towards the springs, Management unit VI Poiana, Sudrigiu Forest district, Bihor County (27.10.2022), 14 – Aries Valley, Garda de Sus commune, Management unit I Magura, Garda Forest district, Alba County (28.10.2022), 15 – Ariesul Valley, Arieseni commune, Management unit I Neagra, Horea Apuseni Forest district, Alba County (31.10.2022).

The analysis by the genetic center of origin and the current geographical area (see Figure 2) shows that the spectrum of phytogeographical elements is dominated by *Eurasian species* (32.9%) followed by *circumpolar species* (15.3%), on a par with European ones (15.3%), followed by Central European species (10.9%), and Carpathian and Carpathian-Balkan (7.5%) species. Stenochore species are rare and occur in small percentages such as endemic (4.3%), Alpine-Carpatho-Balkan (3.2%), Alpine-European (2.1%), Arctic-Alpine (1%), and Balkan (1%).

Spruce (*Picea abies*), beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), fir (*Abies alba*) and *Pulmonaria rubra* forests with thickets of *Syringa josikaea* are rare in Romania, being included according to the Habitats' Directive 92/49/EEC in the natural habitat of community interest NATURA2000: 91V0 Dacian Beech forests (**Symphyto-Fagion**)

(Burescu L. 2018), according to Law 49 of April 7th, 2011 and the Emergency Ordinance of the Government of Romania no. 57 of 2007, regulating the regime of protected natural areas, any kind of felling is prohibited, the main objectives of the management plan being the conservation of biodiversity, and of the rare, endangered, endemic, relict species and ensuring the stability of rare or endangered forest ecosystems.

since it contains species at risk of extinction, which is why they must be protected in special protected areas.

The stands of *Syringa josikaea* from the Apuseni Mountains are centuries-old virgin forests included in Group I, Forest vegetation with special protective functions, subgroup 1-5 Forests with scientific importance for the protection of forest gene pool and ecological diversity 1.5c, 1.5f, 1.5i, 1.5e; sub-group 1-2 Soil protection forests from categories 1.2a Forests located on cliffs, gullies, lands with large slopes prone to erosion.

Although the forest species in the stands surveyed are relevant for the wood industry, in the forests with *Syringa josikaea* declared natural protected areas and containing high conservation values, VRC 1.1., VRC 1.2., VRC 1.3.

Figure 2. The spectrum of phytogeographical elements of the association *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987- *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu, L. 2018

CONCLUSIONS

The floristic inventory of *Syringa josikaea* stands gathered in the association *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* Täuber 1987 – *syringetosum josikaeae* Burescu L. 2018, totals 91 cormophyte species, which shows a high biodiversity.

Based on a strong nucleus consisting of 14 boreal, Carpathian species that grow alongside *Syringa josikaea* on narrow mountain valleys, in microthermal climate, on moist soils with a weakly acid-neutrophilic to slightly basic Ph, we differentiated the sub-association *syringetosum josikaeae* subordinated floristically, coenotaxonomically and ecologically at the *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* base association.

The trees of the phytocenoses with *Syringa josikaea* are dominated by hemicryptophytes (49.4%) followed by phanerophytes (22.8%) and geophytes (17.5%), a consequence of the surveyed territory belonging to the temperate continental climate of the Apuseni Mountains.

Analysis of the distribution of species according to the occupied geographical area shows the predominance of Eurasian species (32.9%) followed by circumpolar boreal (15.3%) at par with European species (15.3%)

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***Legea 49 din 7 aprilie 2011 pentru aprobarea Ordonanței de Urgență a Guvernului nr. 57 din

2007 privind regimul ariilor naturale protejate, conservarea habitatelor naturale a florei și faunei sălbatice.

POSSIBLE REGULATORY DEFICIENCIES OF THE INCRIMINATION METHODS OF FOREST CRIMES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

4 years after assuming the revision desideratum of the legislative framework in the forestry field, there are still some aspects that I consider to be deficient in terms of the criminalization of forestry crimes.

Keywords: regulation, incrimination, theft, forest crimes

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INTRODUCTION

In 2017, the Ministry of Waters and Forests elaborated the National Forestry Strategy 2018-2027

(http://www.mmediu.ro/app/webroot/uploads/files/2017-10-27/Strategia_forestiera_2017.pdf),

which contains a series of strategic objectives in the forestry field. The first of these is the one regarding the Efficiency of the institutional and regulatory framework of forestry activities. The main aspect assumed within this objective was the revision of the existing legislative framework. 4 years after assuming this desideratum, there are several aspects that I consider to be deficient in terms of the criminalization of forestry crimes. A first possible regulatory problem can be found in the case of breaking, destroying, degrading infractions or uprooting, without right, trees, saplings or sprouts from the national forest fund, respectively theft of saplings or sprouts that have been cut or uprooted. In the case of both previously mentioned infractions, the legislator opted for the inclusion in the sphere of the objective side of the variant in which the act generated minimal damage that can be cumulated arithmetically by adding the damages caused by all the acts committed within a year.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used in writing this paper are composed of legislation and websites. The methods used are legal, namely the formal

method, the comparative method, the logical and the analytical method. The use of these methods has the role of performing a systematic analysis of the information from the studied sources in order to elaborate the points of view and the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In concrete terms:

- **Art. 107, para. (1)** (Law 46/2008 republished in M. Of. 611 of 12.08.2015) Breaking, destroying, degrading or uprooting, without right, trees, saplings or sprouts from the national forest fund, regardless of the form of ownership, constitutes a forestry crime and is punished as follows: *b) with imprisonment from 6 months to 3 years or with a fine, if the value of the damage caused does not exceed the limit provided for in letter a), but the act was committed at least twice within a year, and the cumulative value of the damage caused exceeds the limit provided for in letter a);*

- **Art. 109 para. (1)** Theft of saplings or sprouts that have been cut or removed from the roots, from forests, protective forest curtains, from degraded lands that have been improved through afforestation works constitutes a crime and is punished as follows:

b) with imprisonment from 6 months to 3 years or with a fine, if the act was committed at least twice within a year, and the cumulative value of the wood material exceeds the value provided for in letter a);

Such a regulatory manner can be of a nature to generate numerous inconveniences for the authorities with responsibilities in

establishing and carrying out criminal prosecution, in light of the fact that exactly the same acts, if they do not exceed the minimum threshold value for the act to become a crime, are regulated as contraventions.

Specifically, if for such an act with a damage lower than the minimum threshold value, a record of finding and sanctioning the contravention has been drawn up (based on the provisions of art. 8 par. 1. letter a) or c) of Law 171 /2010), the same act can no longer be taken into account for the retention of the forestry offense if, after its sanctioning as a contravention but within the 1-year term, the author commits another act whose damage, combined with the first, would exceed the minimum amount threshold necessary for the act to be criminalized.

Article 4 of Protocol 7 of the Convention enshrines "the right not to be judged or punished twice", known by the traditional name of "ne bis in idem": "*No one may be prosecuted or punished criminally by the jurisdictions of the same State for committing the offense for which he has already been acquitted or convicted by a final judgment according to the law and criminal procedure of this State. (...)*"

The contraventional sanction applied to the person for the first act of breaking, destroying, degrading trees or stealing saplings/sprouts, according to art. 8 para. 1 lit. a), b) from Law no. 171/2010, can therefore be circumscribed to the notion of criminal accusation, since the act for which he was sanctioned can be considered to have a criminal character in the autonomous sense, which the European Convention on Human Rights gives to this notion, considering that, on the one hand, the prohibition established by art. 4 of Protocol 7 to the Convention is addressed to all persons and that, on the other hand, the purpose of the sanction is to punish and prevent the commission of similar acts in the future (the case of *Anghel v. Romania*, 2007), the social values protected in the contraventional law and in the criminal one are the same, and the first material act component of the offense was separately sanctioned with a contravention fine, which became final in the sense of art. 4 of Protocol no. 7 to the European Convention, prior to the initiation of criminal proceedings against the defendant.

The manner of regulation of the offenses provided for by art. 107 para. 1 and art. 109 para. 1 of the Forestry Code therefore raises a constitutionality issue, from the perspective of the *ne bis in idem* principle.

Another possible regulatory problem is found in the case of the illegal cutting crimes and trees theft.

In concrete terms:

- **Art. 107(1¹)** Unauthorized cutting of trees from the national forest fund, regardless of the form of ownership, constitutes a forestry crime and is punished as follows:

- a) with imprisonment from 6 months to one year or with a fine, if the value of the damage caused is up to 5 times the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act;**
- b) with imprisonment from one year to 3 years, if the value of the damage caused is included between the limit provided for in letter a) and at most 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act;**
- c) with imprisonment from 2 to 7 years, if the value of the damage caused is at least 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wooden mass per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act.**

- **Art.109 (1¹)** Theft of felled or broken trees by natural phenomena or of trees that were cut or removed from the roots, from forests, protective forest curtains, from degraded lands that were improved through afforestation works and from the forestry vegetation outside the national forest fund, as well as any other specific products of the national forest fund constitutes a crime and is punished as follows:

- a) with imprisonment from 6 months to one year or with a fine, if the value of the damage caused is up to 5 times the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act;**
- b) with imprisonment from one year to 3 years, if the value of the damage caused is included between the

limit provided for in letter a) and at most 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act;**

c) with imprisonment from 2 to 7 years, if the value of the damage caused is at least 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wooden mass per foot **on the date of ascertainment of the act.**

The use of the phrase "*on the date of ascertainment of the act*" for the calculation of the damage (and implicitly the aggravating variants) generates a possible unconstitutionality through the prism of reporting at a time after the commission of the act. In concrete terms, there is a possibility that reported to the time of the commission of such a crime, the act may generate a prejudice likely to attract the simple option, but if the moment of ascertainment is later and in the meantime the price of the cubic meter has increased, it may impose an aggravating factor. As a consequence, the regulatory manner can generate particular situations in which the sanction applied is different not depending on the act or damage, but on the moment of its ascertainment by the authorities.

A third potential regulatory problem is found in the case of the crime of using special marking devices without the right.

In concrete terms:

Art. 107¹(1) The use of special marking devices provided for in art. 63 without right or **with non-compliance with the specific regulations in force** constitutes a forestry crime and is punishable by imprisonment from 6 months to 3 years or a fine.

The method of incrimination, through references to legal (Law 24/2000 regarding legislative technical norms for the elaboration of normative acts - republished M.Of. 260 of 02.04.2010) texts not specifically indicated, clearly violates the legal provisions related to the rules of legislative technique, according to which "The reference in a normative act to another normative act is made by specifying its legal category, its number, the title and the date of publication of that act or only the legal category and the number, if thus any confusion is excluded".

A fourth and last potential problem identified is related to the manner in which, in order to punish the theft of specific products of

the forest fund, the legislator chose to refer to the value of the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot.

CONCLUSIONS

It is at least debatable the way of quantifying the prejudice in the case of the theft of products specific to the forest fund (mushrooms, berries, etc.) by referring to the value of the wood mass.

Equally debatable and uninspired was the option to regulate the theft of specific products of the forest fund together with the theft of trees, given that the material object protected by the law is completely different.

I appreciate that in the case of the crime of theft of the forest fund specific products, separate criminalization should have been imposed, with the possible imposition of a fixed value threshold or determinable based on different criteria than the value of the wood mass.

Theft of felled or broken trees by natural phenomena or of trees that were cut or removed from the roots, from forests, protective forest curtains, from degraded lands that were improved through afforestation works and from the forestry vegetation outside the national forest fund, as well as any other specific products of the national forest fund constitutes a crime and is punished as follows:

a) with imprisonment from 6 months to one year or with a fine, if the value of the damage caused is up to 5 times the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot on the date of ascertainment of the act

b) with imprisonment from one year to 3 years, if the value of the damage caused is included between the limit provided for in letter a) and at most 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wood per foot on the date of ascertainment of the act

c) with imprisonment from 2 to 7 years, if the value of the damage caused is at least 20 times higher than the average price of a cubic meter of wooden mass per foot on the date of ascertainment of the act

Four years after assuming the desideratum revision of the legislative framework in the forestry field, there are possible constitutionality problems concerning the criminalization of forestry crimes and a certain violation of the legal provisions regarding the legislative technical

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DIFFERENTIATED USE OF CARTOGRAPHIC MATERIAL IN THE FORESTRY SECTOR, IN THE PLAIN AREA

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Abstract

The use of cartographic material in the various activities within the forestry sector can currently be done in a different format, depending on the existing logistical base and, respectively, the needs and specifics of the activities. Forest maps in analog format have been used for over six decades, but the working accuracy is relatively low. Currently, forest maps can be used in digital format, after completing some stages specific to digital cartography, and appropriate logistics are also required for the respective activities. The orientation of forest maps in the national reference system can be achieved through special transformations, using known coordinate points in the two coordinate systems for this purpose. The case study was carried out using the common points, with known coordinates in the national reference system STEREO1970, which were identified on the orthophoto plane, in the work area. The precision and respective accuracy with which the forest map was georeferenced is satisfactory for the study carried out, and for the application in other locations, it is necessary to respect the consecrated work stages, to identify precisely the points in the two work systems, as well as to accurately determine of the coordinates of common points, in the national reference system.

Keywords: Forest map, raster, digital map, vector, orthophoto plan, forest sector.

INTRODUCTION

The activities carried out within the forestry sector often require the use of a specific cartographic material, namely forest maps. These have been used over time in analog format, on paper and/or canvas, as the case may be, usually at a scale of 1:20000 (Crainic, 2011).

Currently, forest maps are still sporadically used in analogue format, at a scale of 1: 20000, with the possibility of using them in rasterized - digital format, with the help of specialized geomatics applications (Boș, 2011), on electronic computers, tablets, mobile phones, (on different types of gadgets).

Maps, as conventional graphic representations of the terrain, on a scale, on considerable surfaces, take into account the curvature of the earth and, respectively, the atmospheric refraction. Their content elements depend on their specificity and, respectively, on the activity sector for which they were drawn up.

Forestry maps have a content specific to the activities in the forestry sector, consisting of graphic elements - the contours of plots and

subplots, production units, enclaves, etc., and a series of attributes related to the characteristics of stands, to the silvotechnical interventions proposed through forest management in vigor, etc. (Boș, 2011; Crainic, 2011)

The accuracy of exploitation of the cartographic material related to the forestry sector, in analogue format P_g , is directly correlated with the scale at which the forest map was prepared - N , and respectively with the graphic error e_g , which depends on the normal acuity of the human eye, which is approximate 0.2 mm (Crainic, 2022).

As a result, the accuracy of working with cartographic material in analog format, related to the forestry sector, presents the following mathematical expression (Crainic, 2022; Sabău, 2010):

$$P_g = N \times e_g .$$

P_g - map precision;

N -the denominator of the analog map scale;

e_g - graphical approximation error.

In digital - rasterized format, the cartographic material can be exploited (used) differently (Petrița et al, 2010), depending on

the particularities of the scanning process (resolution, colors, etc.) and respectively on the aspects related to georeferencing (scale, coordinate system, common points in the system of reference, transformation parameters, etc.).

In order to use the coordinates of the various characteristic points of detail, which can be found on the forest maps, in the national reference system, it is necessary to georeference them, in the STEREO-1970 system. As a result, through georeferencing, the rasterized forest map is associated with a coordinate system, related to a clearly defined geodetic datum.

The necessary elements for the georeferencing of the raster related to the forest map, in the national reference system, are represented by: the type of ellipsoid, the fundamental point, the type of cartographic projection adopted, the coordinates of the center of the coordinate system, the direction of the coordinate axes, the coordinates of common points in the two systems of coordinates, specialized program (digital cartography) that will be used to create the application, qualified personnel for the respective activity (Bodog&Crainic, 2016; Crainic et al 2021; Crainic, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The case study was carried out in the forest fund of Maşloc, Timiș county - photo 1 and figure 1.

To carry out the case study, cartographic materials related to the forestry sector from the location where the research was carried out were used, respectively the forest map, in analogue and digital format - rasterized - figure 1.

Also, the orthophoto plan related to the location of the research was used - photo 1, the forest layout, and the MapSys 10.0 digital cartography program.

The research methods used are represented by: bibliographic documentation, experiment, comparison, simulation (Crainic, 2021).

For the orientation - respectively the georeferencing of the raster related to the forest map used, in the national reference system, the planimetric coordinates (in 2D space) of the characteristic points used, identified on the orthophoto plane, were used.

As a result, four common points were used, representative, respectively easy to identify, in the two working spaces (systems), represented by orthophotoplan and raster - table 1. Because, the parcel related to the forestry unit where the case study was carried out is mostly rectangular, it is relatively easy to identify the corners of the plots and the forest subplots, on the orthophoto plane (Crainic et. al. 2021, Crainic et. al. 2018).

In this context, forest plot 20 was analyzed, with the related forest subplots, respectively u.a. 20A, u.a. 20B, u.a. 20C, u.a. 20D, u.a.20E and u.a. 20F, and forest plot 19, with subplots u.a. 19A, u.a. 19B and u.a. 19C.

The transformation used was carried out in the 2D space - respectively in the plane, on common points, with five parameters, two rotations, two translations and respectively the scale factor (Damian&Crainic 2010, Damian&Crainic 2011; Marton 2007; Tămăioagă& Tămăioagă, 2007).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The use of common points for the georeferencing of the raster related to the forest map determined the achievement of some interesting results, which will be analyzed further.

The accuracy and precision of achieving the planar transformation depends directly on the precision with which the characteristic transformation points were materialized on the used orthophotoplan.

The work stages, which were completed for the georeferencing of the raster used, are the following (Crainic, 2011):

- establishing the raster scale;
- raster import;
- choosing the orientation method (georeferencing);
- establishing and materializing transformation points;
- determining the coordinates of the transformation points - tab.1;
- implementation of transformation points;
- the initiation of the transformation process;
- completion of the transformation process;

Photo 1 The orthophotoplan of the working area (obtained with the MapSys 10.0 program)

Figure 1 The forest map used

Figure 2 Location of plot 20 on the forest map

Figure 3 Initialization of the process of orientation (georeferencing) of the raster related to the forest map

Table 1

The coordinates of the characteristic transformation points, in the national reference system

No. crt.	No. point	X(m)	Y(m)	Code
1	1	505466.785	230174.550	1
2	2	506212.981	230230.481	1
3	3	506166.104	230983.355	1
4	4	505410.869	230915.393	1

Figure 4 Realization of the process of georeferencing the raster related to the forest map, using common points 1, 2, 3 and 4

Photo 2 Obtaining the related vector

Table 2

Comparative presentation of the values of the areas of the subplots according to the data from the forestry management and the respective ones obtained on the vector related to the forest map

No. crt.	Subplot (u.a.)				
	No.	Surface (ha)		The surface difference	
		from forest management	from the vector	(ha)	(%)
1	19A	5,00	4,74	0,26	5,2
2	19B	10,80	10,89	-0,09	-0,8
3	19C	0,50	0,56	-0,06	-12,0
4	Total plot 19	16,3	16,19	0,11	0,7

Table 3

Comparative presentation of the values of the areas of the subplots according to the data from the forestry management and the respective ones obtained on the vector related to the forest map

No. crt.	Subplot (u.a.)				
	No.	Surface (ha)		The surface difference	
		from forest management	from the vector	(ha)	(%)
1	20A	2,30	2,65	-0,35	-15,2
2	20B	14,20	14,37	-0,17	-1,2
3	20C	3,30	3,26	0,04	1,2
4	20D	25,60	24,75	0,85	3,3
5	20E	8,50	8,65	-0,15	-1,8
6	20F	2,30	2,26	0,04	1,7
7	Total plot 20	56,2	55,94	0,26	0,5

Photo 3 The vector of subplots on the orthophotoplan

Figure 5 Vector of subplots on the raster

Figure 6 Comparative presentation of the sub-plots' surfaces according to the values from the forestry management and those obtained on the vector related to the forest map

Figure 7 The difference between the area in the forest management and the one on the vector, expressed in hectares

Figure 8 The difference in percentages between the area in the forest management and the one on the vector

-checking the oriented raster.

These work steps that have been listed are presented synthetically in the related images, taken from the MapSys 10.0 program – fig.3, fig. 4 and photo. 2.

Through the vectorization process of the georeferenced raster, related to the forest map used, a vector (a digital copy of the raster) will be obtained that will overlap relatively faithfully over the orthophoto plane of the analyzed and studied location (in this case study, parcels 19 and 20 are analyzed in detail).

As a result, a series of aspects related to the delimitation of the stands can be analyzed under optimal conditions on the orthophotoplane, being materialized on the related raster vector (which overlaps the orthophotoplane) - photo. 3 and fig. 5.

In order to be able to analyze the accuracy and precision with which the process of orientation (georeferencing) of the raster related to the forest map was carried out, the

values of the areas of the subplots in the forest management were compared with those obtained from the vector related to the oriented raster.

Thus, the differences obtained vary between 0.11 ha for plot 19 - table 2 and respectively 0.26 ha for plot 20 - table 3, fig.6, fig. 7 and fig. 8.

If the differences obtained are related to the surfaces of the sub-plots (presented in the forest management), the percentage difference of these analyzed surfaces results, respectively 0.7% for plot 19 and 0.5% plot 20.

From the analysis of the values related to the surface differences, for the plots studied and analyzed, it is found that these differences are very small, consequently the georeferencing process was carried out with high precision and accuracy.

It can also be noted that the surface differences at the sub-plot level (u.a.) show significantly different values compared to those

at the plot level, an aspect that is due to the particularities of identifying and delimiting the stands (corresponding to the sub-plots) on the orthophoto plane (Curilă et al 2014).

CONCLUSIONS

The use of forest maps in analog and/or digital format, depending on the working conditions, offers the possibility to forest sector specialists to adopt effective technical solutions, for perspective strategies and respectively for various current activities in the forest sector.

Considering the facilities offered by modern technologies for the differentiated use of cartographic material, in the activities of the forestry sector, it is necessary to implement of specialized geomatics applications, regardless of the owner and administrator.

For the realization of some complex geomatic applications, related to forest management and management activities, the existence of an appropriate logistic base, namely the Hard base, the Soft base, and last but not least the existence of a specialized staff to serve them, is required.

The use of the orthophoto plan and forest maps in digital format facilitates the adoption of optimal solutions regarding the spatial location of various details in the forestry sector, related to the activities of culture, guarding and exploitation of the forest.

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VERTICAL DIFFERENTIATION INDEX AND THE POSSIBILITY OF WINDTHROWS APPEARANCE

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

The research that was the basis of this work is based on the four types of structures that the stands can have in relation to the ages of the trees that compose it. From field observations and the analysis of the areas affected by windthrows, it was found an increased incidence of this phenomenon in stands with simplified even-aged-type structure. The values of the percentages of the volume that are affected suggest the idea that the stands most stable to windthrows are the uneven aged stands. In the medium and long term, silvotechnical interventions will have to be imagined to lead to the establishment of uneven-aged stands with high stability to the action of disturbing factors. In stands with uneven-aged type structures, the percentages of affected wood are a maximum of 21%, while in even-aged stand structures the values exceed percentages between 60-70%. Increasing the degree of stability of the stands will be achieved by creating complex structures that are much more stable to the action of disturbing factors.

Keywords: vertical differentiation index, stand structure, disturbing factors, percentage of wood affected

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INTRODUCTION

The stability of stands in the current conditions of the manifestations of climate changes, the most resistant structures to the actions of disturbing factors as well as the conditions, the means and the ways to manage the forests in order to increase their stability are the most important things for forestry research and practice.

It has been proven in the last decades that the forest structures imagined a century ago will have to be rethought in accordance with the current challenges. Thus, the large-scale promotion of pure and even-aged stands will have to be replaced by mixed stands with vertical differentiation in order to increase the self-protection capacity of these forests and to increase the capacity to fulfill the assigned functions (Pastorella & Paletto, 2013).

The complex structures of the stands determine their high productivity and the fulfillment of ecoprotective functions (Bagnaresi et al, 2015). Also, the increase in the complexity of the structure determines the increase in ecosystem services and the reaction capacity of forests to pollutants and the action of disturbing factors caused by climate changes (Gao et al, 2014; Dănescu et al, 2016). The

diversified structures represented by stands with uneven aged structures proved to be much more stable under the action of disturbing factors (Joelsson et al, 2018).

In recent decades, there have been clearer signs that mention the danger of environmental degradation by decreasing the areas covered by natural forests with uneven aged structures (Duduman G., 2011) and the degradation of their structure mainly composed of spruce but also other forest ecosystems that were traditionally not affected by extreme weather events.

The aim of the work is to show the connection between the values of the vertical differentiation index and the stability of the stands under the action of the winds.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For each stand were measured thirty trees and were determined the approach neighbours in number of three to seven and for them were determined the heights. The analyzed trees were statistically randomly distributed so that any tree in the stand had the chance to be part of the analyzed survey. The neighbours of the trees were chosen based on the smallest distances from the tree who was chosen in the thirty.

The determination of the vertical differentiation index for each analyzed stand was made using the following relation (Ciubotaru & Păun, 2014, Keren et. Al., 2020):

$$DH_n = 1/N * \sum [1/n \sum (1 - X_{ijmin}/X_{ijmax})]$$

in which:

- DH_n is the vertical differentiation index;
- N - number of trees measured;
- n - the number of trees considered neighbors of the analyzed tree i ;
- X_{ijmin} - the lowest height in each group of trees analyzed,
- X_{ijmax} - the highest height in each group of trees analyzed.

After determining the vertical differentiation index, an analysis was carried out regarding the correlation between the values of this index and the possibility of the occurrence of disturbing factors caused by wind and respectively the intensity of the occurrence of such phenomena.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The percentage of wood affected by windthrows is between 63-74% in the even-aged stands, it decreases slightly in the relatively even-aged stands, the values being between 45-69%, in the relatively even-aged stands the values are between 19-44% and in the uneven-aged stands the values are relatively low 8-21% in uneven-aged stands (see figure 1).

It is worth noting that in the even-aged stands with simplified structures the maximum percentage of affected wood exceeds on average 70% of the stand volume, sometimes it can be close to 100%, which indicates the volume losses that could have been accumulated in these stands from the moment the appearance of the phenomenon until the stands would have reached the age of exploitability.

It should also be noted that in the uneven-aged stands the maximum percentage of affected wood does not exceed 20-21% of the total stand volume. This affected volume largely supports the ecosystem process of continuous regeneration, which supports the perpetuation of structurally diversified stands over time. In these situations, specific structural models capable of increasing the resistance of the stands to destabilizing factors can be imagined in specific areas in relation to the disturbing factors.

The values of the percentages of the volume that are affected suggest the idea that

the stands most stable to windthrows are the relatively uneven aged-stands and uneven aged-stands. In the medium and long term, silvotechnical interventions will have to be imagined to lead to the establishment of uneven-age stands with high stability to the action of disturbing factors.

The vertical differentiation index provides information on the stability of stands and their sustainability over time and also shows us the degree of complexity of the structures, when this index is close to the value one, we have strong stands in front of disturbing factors, while the index is closer to the value zero, the stands are extremely vulnerable.

The possibility of the occurrence of disturbing phenomena is favored by the stands conditions, the structure of the stands, the silvotechnical interventions applied over time, which most often lead to the simplification of the structure of the stands, which makes them extremely vulnerable.

In order to be able to reduce the unfavorable effects of climate change, stands with simplified structures should gradually be replaced by mixed stands with complex structures diversified horizontally and vertically. The management plans will have to be designed in such a way as to achieve the regeneration of stands over longer periods of time in order to obtain uneven-aged stands mixed with at least three to four stand elements.

The silvotechnical interventions proposed in the technical norms will have to take into account the current realities related to climate change and find effective solutions in terms of increasing the stability of the stands under the action of disturbing factors.

In this point we suggest extensive research to establish for various forest formations the ways forward in terms of the intensity of the interventions and finding effective ways to increase the stability of the stands. However, the ability of the stands to exercise their protective functions where the situations require them will also have to be monitored so that the protective side can be realized in the first place.

Table 1

The structural differentiation of stands in relation to the vertical differentiation index and the percentage of affected wood

Types of structure	Vertical differentiation index		Percentage of wood affected	
	Minim value	Maxim value	Minim value (%)	Maxim value (%)
Even aged stand forest	0,04	0,19	63	74
Relativ even aged stand forest	0,34	0,45	45	69
Relativ uneven aged forest	0,56	0,68	19	44
Uneven aged stand forest	0,76	0,87	8	21

Figure 1 The percentage of wood affected in relation to the type of structure

CONCLUSIONS

In the future it will be necessary extensive research on forest formations will be carried out in order to find the best ways to manage the stands so as to reduce the negative effects of climate change.

Variability of the vertical differentiation index in stands of all types of structures supports the idea that silvotechnical interventions influence the values of this index, which makes us argue that in cultivated forest the stability of stands can be directly influenced by the intensity and quality of silvotechnical interventions.

In the even-aged stands, there is a fairly high incidence of windthrows due mainly to simplified structures that are extremely vulnerable to the action of disturbing factors. What should be specified is the fact that these stands with a simplified structure have recently become vulnerable to wind and snow fall.

Increasing the degree of stability of the stands will be achieved by creating complex structures that are much more stable to the action of disturbing factors.

In the future, the transition from monocultures to mixed stands capable of performing multiple functions of great stability to the action of disturbing factors will also be encouraged.

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TESTING THE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF THE “SCA CHAIR” ASSEMBLY AT THE WEIGHT OF 120 KG. CASE STUDY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The paper presents the structural elements of the SCA chair, which is tested at a weight of 120 kg payload. The SCA chair is a folding chair that is a product made structurally in 3D with the help of SolidWorks Professional 2010 design software. The chair has mechanical strength and this information can be seen from the reports of resistance to different forces or weights subjected to the testing process.

Keywords: chair resistance tests, SolidWorks, design software, case study.

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INTRODUCTION

The SCA chair is an engineering concept that is designed in such a way that the wooden material used to create it is very easy to process, and the parts that make up this chair are designed in such a way that they must resist to certain mechanical stresses.

If specific dimensions of various benchmarks are not respected, they can be reused at another benchmark also within this chair. The program design helped to test the seat components.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

First of all, it was aimed to test the assembly at a pressure force of 120 kg perpendicular to the seat and backrest and with a fixation from the lower end of the front and rear legs, which comes positioned on a flat surface.

Using SOLIDWORKS software, designers were able to quickly design, check, and revise

assemblies, moving development forward at a rapid pace.

In any study done in SolidWorks Professional software we need fixing parts and constraints that we apply to the assembly - in this case the SCA chair.

The fixing parts in this case study were the four legs on which the chair rests in normal use.

The fixation was made on the rounded lower part of the legs on an invisible virtual surface, which allows the elements to move left-right front-back according to the resulting forces on the existing elements and constraints.

Table 1 show the method of fixing elements and the place where the forces were applied is presented in Table 2.

Table 1

Fixture	
Restraint name	Selection set
Roller/Slider-1 < Rear assembly -1/Mirror Leg rear-2, Rear assembly -1/Rear leg-1, Front assembly -2/Leg front element 1-1, Front assembly -2/Mirror Leg front element 1-2>	on 4 Face(s)Roller/Sliding

Table 2

Load system – place of the applied forces

Load name	Selection set
Force-2 < Upper backrest -1, Upper backrest -2>	on 2 Face(s) apply normal force 120 kgf using uniform distribution
Force-3 <Seated assembly -1/ Seated sticks -1, Seated assembly -1/Seated sticks-2, Seated assembly -1/ Seated sticks -3, Seated assembly -1/ Seated sticks -4, Seated assembly-1/ Seated sticks-5>	on 5 Face(s) apply normal force 120 kgf using uniform distribution

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Each component that makes up this assembly was active in the resistance study and effectively participated. Throughout this study, all the physical and thermal properties of the seat components were taken into account.

The area of application of the dispersed forces was disposed perpendicularly to the following surfaces: upper backrest, lower

backrest, the first four slats and the two struts, which are actually subjected to the pressure exerted by the weight of the human body.

The following table show us the connectors to which are part of this assembly.

Table 3

The list of the assembly connectors

Connector name	Selection set
Pin Connector-1 < Head bolt -2, Plate-3, Plate-7, Mirror Leg front element 2-2>	Pin Connectors on 4 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-2 < Head bolt -13, Mirror Leg front element 2-2>	Pin Connectors on 2 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-3 < Head bolt -4, Leg front element 2-1>	Pin Connectors on 2 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-4 <Leg front element 2-1, Head bolt -3, Plate-6>	Pin Connectors on 3 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-7 < Head bolt -5, Safety-1, Plate-7, Safety-2, Plate-3>	Pin Connectors on 5 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-11 <Plate-9, Safety-4, Plate-6, Safety-3, Head bolt -10>	Pin Connectors on 5 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-13 <Plate-9, Plate-6, Head bolt -15, Front assembly -2/Mirror Leg front element 1-2>	Pin Connectors on 4 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-14 <Plate-7, Head bolt -14, Plate-3, Front assembly -2/Leg front element 1-1>	Pin Connectors on 4 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-15 <Plate-9, Rear assembly -1/Mirror Rear Leg -2, Head bolt -17, Plate-6>	Pin Connectors on 4 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad
Pin Connector-16 <Plate-7, Rear assembly -1/Rear leg-1, Placuta-3, Head bolt -16>	Pin Connectors on 4 Face(s); no pin translation; with rotational stiffness of 0.00000 N-m/rad

Observations:

Other forces or constraints than those mentioned in the work were not applied, such as wind, temperature changes, vibrations, etc.

The report created by the Solidworks software showed us all the areas that have changed or moved, after or during the study,

and are marked from red to blue (Red the biggest changes and blue the smallest or none).

The table below describes the contacts between hardware, assembly and landmarks.

Table 4

The contacts between hardware, assembly and landmarks	
Contact Set-2	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of the Back assembly - 1/Link-2 and Seated assembly -1/MirrorLonjeron-3
Contact Set-3	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Bolt-1 and Back assembly -1/Back leg-1
Contact Set-4	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Bolt-2 and Back assembly -1/Mirror back leg-2
Contact Set-5	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Seated Assembly - 1/Lonjeron-1 and Head bolt-18
Contact Set-6	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Bolt cu cap-18 and Front Assembly-2/Leg front element 1-1
Contact Set-7	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Head bolt-19 and Seated assembly -1/MirrorLonjeron-3
Contact Set-8	No Penetration contact pair: Between selected entities of Head bolt-19 and Front assembly -2/Mirror Leg front element 1-2
Global Contact	Contact component: on <Leg front element 2>-<Fillet1>@Mirror leg front element 2-2@Resistance study
Component Contact-1	Contact component: on Cut-Extrude2@Safety-1@ Resistance study
Component Contact-2	Contact component: on Safety-4
Component Contact-5	Contact component: on Front Assembly -2/Leg front element 1-1
Component Contact-6	Contact component: on Back Assembly -1/Mirror Back Leg -2
Component Contact-7	Contact component: Bonded on Seated Assembly -1/Lonjeron-1

The tolerances defined in this study were 0.5 mm XYZ, which is the maximum tolerance allowed for this product. This is done in order to better highlight critical areas to fix in series production.

The table below shows the sum of the reaction forces that resulted from the tests.

Sum of the reaction forces that resulted from the tests.

Table 5

Selection set	Units	Sum X	Sum Y	Sum Z	Resultant
Entire Body	N	0	0	147.891	147.891

Free-Body Forces

Table 6

Selection set	Units	Sum X	Sum Y	Sum Z	Resultant
Entire Body	N	-0.0643309	-1629.52	-794.581	1812.93

Free-body Moments

Table 7

Selection set	Units	Sum X	Sum Y	Sum Z	Resultant
Entire Body	N-m	0	0	0	1e-033

The following table summarizes the final result of the strain and stress study.

Strain and stress elements

Table 8

Name	Type	Min	Location	Max
Stress1	VON: von Mises Stress 87.0004 N/m ² Node: 54988	(-210.586 mm, 559.292 mm, -77.4698 mm)	4.42131e+008 N/m ² Node: 72507	(222 mm, 584.987 mm, -45.9431 mm)
Displacement1	URES: Resultant Displacement 1.16728 mm Node: 2573	(213.975 mm, 0.659153 mm, 305.304 mm)	7.28994 mm Node: 73499	(5.44161 mm, 805.03 mm, -234.572 mm)
Strain1	ESTRN: Equivalent Strain 5.83671e-010 Element: 21674	(178.61 mm, 357.856 mm, -130.668 mm)	0.00318211 Element: 5861	(-197.22 mm, 373.512 mm, 76.403 mm)

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this chair project has successfully passed all the strength tests performed in the SolidWorks software at 120 kgf according to the above results.

The approximate deviation from reality is 8-10%, as the chair was tested with exact forces and at an exact weight applied to the selected landmarks.

The ratio may have small deviations that fall within the tolerated limits due to the quality of the wood and its drying method.

The images represent the final result of the deformation (Figure 1) and tension (Figure 2) study. A survey of displacement and also a study of strain.

Figure 1. The SCA chair. Component displacement study

Figure 2. Stress study of SCA chair components

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COMPARATIVE DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF WOODEN BEAMS AND METAL BEAMS SUBJECTED TO SHOCK

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The dynamic action of loads on structures is a particularly complex phenomenon. The complexity of the phenomenon is also given by the behavior of the material from which the structure is made up and which, in dynamic loads, presents very different properties compared to those in the case of static loads. There are numerous situations of action of external forces on various mechanical or civil structures, when during their application they change their module, meaning, direction or even their position. As a result of this mode of action of these forces, the structure will be in motion. Therefore, the movement that is imprinted on the structure will be accompanied by the accelerations of the various points that will not be neglected. The introduction of the kinematic parameter into the balance equations will be done by applying the inertial forces. The dynamic demand of wooden or metal structures is caused by several factors, namely: the vibratory action of various tools or machines, the fall of some bodies, the action of the wind with variable intensity, the action of hitting the structures or different structural component elements by other bodies. The present work presents a comparative study regarding the behavior under dynamic loads of wood and metal structures. The study presented in the work by the author wants to present and establish the limits of practical use for which using the same structure from the geometric point of view and the external dynamic loads but different materials, the metal can be replaced with the wooden material. For the case presented in the paper, the author considered the dynamic shock stress of the structures.

Keywords: parameters, displacements, dynamic, beams.

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INTRODUCTION

The static analysis of stress and deformation problems in mechanical or civil structures considered the progressive application of external loads from a zero value of their intensity to a final maximum value. In this case, it is known that the structure will pass with reduced speed from the undeformed form to the deformed form, so that the accelerations of its points are considered to be negligible. (Simopoulos, 1999).

The current work proposes the dynamic study of the shock stress of a bar made of two different materials, namely: wooden material and metal. The shock load of the bar-type structural element is given by its sudden contact with another body. The shock stress phenomenon of straight bars is complicated due to the fact that the inertial forces are different along the bars. Due to the complexity of the phenomenon in the present work, the author has limited himself to the case of shock stress which produces only elastic deformations when

the deformation process has propagated throughout the bar. As it is known, the assumptions that are the basis of the calculation for shock loads are approximate and do not give a rigorous representation of the phenomenon which is much more complex, even in the case of the behavior of the materials only in the elastic domain. If the shock is not imposed with a high speed, this being low in relation to the propagation speed of the deformation waves, the stress of the element being carried out in the elastic domain, the established analytical relations give satisfactory results. In the case of the vertical shock with a zero drop height ($h=0$), the dynamic coefficient is considered to be $\Psi=2$. The study was carried out considering the following working hypotheses:

1. The deformation of the bar from the external force applied by the shock propagated throughout the bar is governed by Hooke's law (Soare 1999);
2. The body that determines the shock stress is considered to be inelastic.

In the case studied in the paper, it was considered that the force acting on the

construction element determined by the fall of a body is $F=300[\text{daN}]$ falling from a height $h=10[\text{cm}]$. The structural elements taken into account are made of metal and wooden material (oak) with a length of $L=2[\text{m}]$. It is considered that the structural elements are simply supported on the ends. It was considered the most frequently encountered case in practice of dynamic stress with constant acceleration through transverse bending shock. In the known classical cases, there are two possibilities for the analysis of transverse or horizontal dynamic demands, namely:

- when the mass of the hit body is taken into account;
- when the mass of the hit body is not taken into account.

In the present case, the struck body was considered to be a wooden beam and a metal beam, both having identical geometric characteristics.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the case studied in the paper, it was considered that the force acting on the construction element is determined by the rapid action of the force acting on the beams at the maximum value of $F=300 [\text{daN}]$ due to a mass hitting the middle section of the beams from the height being $h=10 [\text{cm}]$. The structural elements taken into account are made of metal and wooden material (oak) with a length of $L=2[\text{m}]$. It is considered that the structural elements are simply supported on the ends. It was considered the most frequently encountered case in practice of dynamic stress with constant acceleration through transverse bending shock. In the known classical cases, there are two possibilities for the analysis of transverse or horizontal dynamic demands, namely:

- when the mass of the hit body is taken into account;
- when the mass of the hit body is not taken into account.

In the present case, the struck body was considered to be a wooden beam and a metal beam, both having identical geometric characteristics. In the present case, the mass of the hit body is taken into account as follows, for wooden and metal beams, the following geometric characteristics were considered:

- diameter $D=25[\text{cm}]=0.25[\text{m}]$;
- the lengths of the beams are $L=2[\text{m}]$.

For the case of the wooden material, the following physical-mechanical characteristics were considered

- $\rho =700 [\text{Kg}/\text{mc}]$ = oak density;
- $E=11500[\text{N}/\text{mm}^2]$ -modulus de elasticitate longitudinal;
- $\nu=0.372$ – Poisson's ratio.

For the steel material, they considered the following physical-mechanical characteristics

- $\rho =7860 [\text{Kg}/\text{mc}]$ = oak density;
- $E=210000[\text{N}/\text{mm}^2]$ - longitudinal modulus of elasticity;
- $\nu=0.3$ – Poisson's ratio.

The weight of the wooden and metal beams acts as a uniformly distributed force with the resulting values determined in the section in the center of the beams:

- for the wooden beam;

$$G_1 = m_1 g = \rho_1 V_1 g = 686.8[\text{N}].$$

- For the steel beam:

$$G_2 = m_2 g = \rho_2 V_2 g = 7712.6[\text{N}]$$

The axial moments of inertia are given by the relation (Martian 1999):

$$I = \frac{\pi D^4}{64} = 0.000191[\text{m}^4]$$

As is known, the static displacements for the wooden and metal beams are given by the relations:

- For the wooden beam (Barsan 2003)

$$\Delta_{st1} = \frac{FL^3}{48E_1 I}$$

- For steel beam (Barsan 2003)

$$\Delta_{st2} = \frac{FL^3}{48E_2 I}$$

The notations are made:

K_1 - it is called the mass reduction coefficient for the movement of the weight and the beam at the point of contact. (Bors 2005)

$$K_1 = \frac{5}{8}$$

K_2 - it is called the mass reduction coefficient for the kinetic energy of the weight and the beam at the point of contact (Bors 2005) (Ille 1977)

$$K_2 = \frac{17}{35}$$

Ψ - dynamic coefficient or impact multiplier (Ille 2004), (Ille 1977)

$$\Psi = 1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{2h(1 + K_2 \frac{G}{F})}{\Delta_{ST}(1 + K_1 \frac{G}{F})^2}}$$

Having the calculated dynamic coefficient, it will be possible to determine the maximum dynamic load, the maximum dynamic displacement and the maximum tension in the joists subjected to the shock.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the numerical calculation program Lisa (Ghinea 2004), the 2 beams were modeled in a 2D graphic representation, namely the metal beam whose graphic representations of the values of acceleration, speed and displacements in the direction of the Y coordinate axis are represented in figures 1,2 and 3.

Regarding the modeling and presentation of deformations and kinematic parameters for the wooden beam, figures 3, 4 and 5 are presented.

For an overview of the values obtained for the kinematic parameters, table 1 shows the values corresponding to node 3 located in the middle of the opening of the metal bar with length $L=2$ [m].

Table 2 shows the same kinematic parameters but for the wooden bar. From the analysis carried out on the basis of the obtained data, the following relevant aspects regarding the dynamic shock behavior of the two beams emerge.

Regarding the dynamic stress, it is considered for the calculation that the acceleration of the body's weight at the contact point located at the middle of the opening is constant for the same force, being 11.4 times

higher in the case of the wooden beam compared to the metal one.

Regarding the speed at the point of contact (node 3), it is found that for an interval of 3 seconds for which the determination of the kinematic parameters was initially set, it will have a much higher value in the case of the wooden beam, it is approximately 11.24 times higher than in the case of the wooden beam for each time considered and presented in tables 1 and 2.

Regarding the displacements of the points on the metal bar, they are between 0.1 [mm] and 0.9 [mm], and on the wooden bar they are between 4 [cm] and 9 [cm]. Therefore, the stiffness conditions for the dynamic action will not be met for the bar made of wooden material.

Using the relationship

$$\Psi = 1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{2h(1 + K_2 \frac{G}{F})}{\Delta_{ST}(1 + K_1 \frac{G}{F})^2}}$$

the dynamic multiplication coefficient for the metal beam is obtained:

$$\Psi = 2.82$$

Therefore the maximum dynamic force will be (Ille 2004), (Ille 1977)

$$F_{DIN} = \Psi F = 846 \text{ [N]}$$

The maximum dynamic displacement will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{DIN} &= \Psi \Delta_{ST} \\ \Delta_{ST \text{ MAX}} &= 0.9 \text{ [mm]} \\ \Delta_{DIN} &= 2.538 \text{ [mm]} \end{aligned}$$

Regarding the wooden beam, the dynamic parameters show that they do not allow the fulfillment of the resistance and rigidity conditions of the bar

Figure 1. The acceleration by the Y coordinate for steel beam

Figure 2. The velocity by the Y coordinate for steel beam

Figure 3. The displacements in Y for steel beam

Table 1

The kinematic parameters of the metal structure recorded in node no. 3 of the force with dynamic action

For Node 3	Time step 0	Time step 1	Time step 2	Time step 3	Time step 4	Time step 5
	Time 0	Time 0.005	Time 0.01	Time 0.015	Time 0.02	Time 0.025
Acceleration	30.534	30.534	30.534	30.534	30.534	30.534
Velocity	0	0.152	0.305	0.458	0.610	0.763
Displacements	0	0.00003	0.00015	0.00034	0.00061	0.000954

Figure 1. The acceleration by the Y coordinate for wood beam

Figure 2. The velocity by the Y coordinate for wood beam

Figure 2. The displacements in Y for wood beam

Table 2

The kinematic parameters of the wooden structure recorded in node no. 3 of the force with dynamic action

For Node 3	Time step 0 Time 0	Time step 1 Time 0.005	Time step 2 Time 0.01	Time step 3 Time 0.015	Time step 4 Time 0.02	Time step 5 Time 0.025
Acceleration	342.85	342.85	342.85	342.85	342.85	342.85
Velocity	0	1.714	3.428	5.142	6.857	8.571
Displacements	0	0.000428	0.00171	0.00385	0.00685	0.00914

CONCLUSIONS

As a first conclusion that emerges from the dynamic analysis performed on the two types of bars is the fact that the use of wooden beams for the case of dynamic shock actions is only recommended in the case of an extremely short time of their manifestation and for force intensities what they are depending on the location where the respective structure will be used. Therefore, from the performed calculations, it is found that with the static reduction of the forces, we can be sure of the correct functioning of the structure. When applying the determined dynamic multiplication coefficient, it was found that only the metallic bar still fulfills the conditions of operation in dynamic mode. For a correct and safe use of the wooden bar, the dimensions of the transverse sections must be changed in the

sense of oversizing it, which leads to an additional consumption of material.

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ANALYSIS OF THE LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION-RELATED PROBLEMS REGARDING THE INDUSTRIAL USE OF THE BIOMASS FROM FORESTRY AND RELATED INDUSTRIES

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

This document analyzes the impact of legislative changes on the issuance of certificates of origin, documents that represent the basis for the issuance of green certificates, within the support scheme for the energy production from renewable energy sources. The biomass coming from forestry and related industries is an important source of energy. Its use in the process of producing electricity and thermal energy requires, on the one hand, caution in order to maintain a balance between economic benefits and ecological impact, and, on the other hand, careful monitoring in order to prevent fraud.

Keywords: biomass from forestry and related industries, forestry, renewable energy, energy legislation, certificates of origin

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INTRODUCTION

Time and evolution have shown that existence depends on the ability to use renewable energy sources, especially since the current context, generated by climate change and the increase in the carbon dioxide content of the atmosphere, causes a general state of concern among decision-makers and calls imperatively finding alternative sources of energy production, while maintaining a balance between economic development and environmental costs. The first combustible material used by man to produce energy was wood. It seems that humanity cannot give up wood, as a material used for energy production, but on the contrary is returning to it, this time trying a rational and efficient use of this precious resource. In recent years there has been an increasing interest in the use of biomass from forestry, for the production of electricity and thermal energy.

Since the 1990s, at the European level, the public policy documents (e.g. White Paper - An energy policy for European Union- 1995) emphasize investments in the research on the use of renewable energy sources. The directions of action from the public policy documents of the European Union are transposed into a series

of normative acts that aim to regulate the production, use and increase of efficiency in the field of energy from renewable sources. In the last 20 years, at least 5 European directives aimed at promoting energy produced from renewable sources have been identified. The renewable energy sources have gained major importance based on the increasing phenomenon of climate change and the development of technology.

Thus, at the level of 2018, the climate and energy policy program had in view to achieve some objectives regarding:

- reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% compared to the levels in 1990;
- an increase of 32% in the share of renewable energies in energy consumption;
- an improvement of 32.5% in energy efficiency;
- interconnection of at least 15% of the EU electricity systems.

(<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/rsheet/68/politica-energetica-principii-generale>)

Thus, the FIT FOR 55 legislative package, promoted by the European Union in 2021, aims at the EU objective of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The proposed package has in view to align EU legislation with the 2030 objective

(<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/green-deal/fit-for-55-the-eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/>). As part of this legislative package, the target for energy consumption from renewable sources is changed from 32% to 40%.

The objective promoted by this legislative package must be transposed in all Member States' National Climate and Energy Plans (NCEPs).

Figure 1. **The renewable energy growth plan related to the FIT FOR 55 package**
(<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/fit-for-55-how-the-eu-plans-to-boost-renewable-energy/>)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Since 2008, Romania, as a member state of the European Union, proceeded to the implementation of the European directives by establishing a system that promotes the production of energy from renewable sources. The first normative act adopted in this sense, Law no. 220 of 2008 for the establishment of the system that promotes the energy production from renewable energy sources (RES), was the one that created the general legal framework in the field.

The legislative mechanism for implementing the system that promotes the energy production from renewable energy sources.

WHY?

- Law no. 220 of October 27, 2008 for the establishment of the system that promotes the energy production from renewable energy sources, with subsequent amendments and additions (18 amendments)

HOW?

- Order no. 44 of October 20, 2011 for the approval of the Regulation on the organization and operation of the green certificate market (2 amendments)
 - Order no. 43 of October 20, 2011 for the approval of the Regulation on issuing green certificates (1 amendment)
 - Order no. 46 of March 5, 2012 regarding the approval of the Procedure for issuing the origin certificate for the biomass from agriculture and related industries, used as fuel or raw material for the production of electricity (1 amendment)
 - Order no. 1341 of May 3, 2012 regarding the approval of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries (3 amendments)
- WHO?
- Order no. 42 of October 20, 2011 regarding the approval of the Accreditation Regulation of the electricity producers from renewable energy sources for the application of the promotion system through green certificates (7 amendments)

A primary analysis of the content and evolution of the normative acts in the field of energy production from renewable sources generates the following findings:

- The normative act of the highest rank (the law), which establishes the general framework, is the one that has undergone the most changes (more than one a year!)

- The second normative act in terms of number of amendments is the act that defines the main actors of the promotion system - Order no. 42 of October 20, 2011 regarding the approval of the Regulation on the accreditation of electricity producers from renewable energy sources for the application of the promotion system through green certificates (approximately one change every year and a half)

- The third normative act in terms of number of amendments is the one that presents the procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries (Order No. 1341 of May 3, 2012 on the approval of the Procedure for issuing origin certificates for the biomass from forestry and related industries).

The novelty of the field addressed, the number of interested factors, as well as the impact generated in economic, ecological and even social terms, can constitute plausible explanations of these legislative fluctuations.

In 2020, Romania adopted the Integrated National Plan in the field of Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030, a plan through which revises the level of ambition regarding the share of energy from renewable sources compared to the updated version of National Plan Integrated in the Field of Energy and Climatic Changes (NPIECC), from an initially proposed quota of 27.9%, to a quota of 30.7%. (https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-04/ro_final_necp_main_ro_0.pdf)

Biomass is defined by using three notions:

- The bios
- Mass (physical size)
- Energy (physical quantity)

According to DEX

(<https://dexonline.ro/definitie/biomas%C4%83>).

1. The total mass of plant and animal micro- and macro-organisms, living on a certain unit of surface or in a certain volume of air or water.
2. Biological matter.

Another definition of biomass, related to energy, is the following:

Biomass is a form of solar energy storage through the process of photosynthesis. Biomass is a generic term that refers to any kind of plant matter that produces thermal energy through direct combustion. (<https://despretot.info/biomasa-definitie/>)

At European level, Directive 2018/2001/EC defines biomass as the *biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues of biological origin from agriculture, including plant and animal substances, from forestry and related industries, including fishing and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of waste, including industrial and municipal waste of biological origin*; (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001&from=es>)

The national legislation, by art. 2, letter b from Law no. 220 of October 27, 2008 for the establishment of the system that promotes the energy production from renewable energy sources, with subsequent amendments and additions, defines biomass as the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues of biological origin from agriculture (including plant and animal substances), forestry and related industries, including fishing and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste, codified according to the legal provisions.

The regulations of the system that promotes the energy from renewable sources in the field of forestry were directly implemented by the Order of the Minister of Environment and Forests no. 1341 of May 3, 2012 regarding the approval of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries.

This regulation was modified by the Order of the Minister of Environment and Climate Change no. 85 of January 28, 2013 regarding the modification and completion of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries, approved by Order of the Minister of Environment and Forests no. 1341/2012. On July 28, 2016, Order no. 1534 is released regarding the approval of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass originating from forestry and related industries and used in the production of electricity from renewable energy sources, which repeals the Order of the Minister of Environment and Forests no. 1341 of May 3, 2012 regarding the approval of the Procedure for issuing

certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries. Later, as a result of the changes made to Law no. 46/2008-Forestry Code, the procedure for issuing certificates of origin is changed by Order no. 2303 of December 18, 2020 regarding the amendment and completion of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass coming from forestry and related industries and used in the production of electricity from renewable energy sources, approved by Order of the Minister of Environment, Water and Forests no. 1.534/2016, a normative act in force on this date.

Indirectly, the implementation of the regulations regarding the system for promoting the production of energy from renewable sources was achieved through a series of normative acts, among which there are listed:

- Law no. 46/2008-Forestry Code (has an impact by defining wood materials, control competences, ways of producing biomass and how to use it)
- Decision no. 497 of June 25, 2020 for the approval of the Norms relating to the origin, circulation and trade of wood materials, to the regime of storage spaces for wood materials and round wood processing facilities, as well as those regarding the origin and circulation of wood materials intended for the owner's own consumption and of measures to apply the provisions of Regulation (EU) no. 995/2010 of the European Parliament and Council of October 20, 2010 establishing the obligations of operators who introduce wood and wood

products to the market (has an impact by defining the obligations of economic operators active in the field of acquisition, storage and processing of wood materials, defining SUMAL 2.0 as a monitoring and control tool)

- Emergency ordinance no. 77 of June 30, 2021 regarding the establishment of the National Forestry Guard
- Decision no. 43 of January 16, 2020 regarding the organization and operation of the Ministry of Environment, Water and Forests, with subsequent amendments and additions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The legislation that directly ensures the implementation of the system for promoting the production of energy from biomass coming from forestry and related industries has undergone changes in the last 10 years. The analysis of these changes will be carried out taking into account 4 aspects:

- a) the evolution of the definitions of the biomass from forestry and related industries;
- b) the evolution of the way of drawing up the documentation requested and submitted by the producers of electricity from renewable sources;
- c) the evolution of the document verification procedure;
- d) identification and development of the modalities for correcting the non-conformities identified after issuing the notices related to the certificates of origin.

Figure 2. **Flow chart of the procedure, competent authorities and documents related to the issuance of the certificate of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries**

a) The adoption of a definition of the biomass from forestry and related industries generated divergent positions during the elaboration of the normative acts, which were based on the interests of the involved factors. The RES electricity producers, respectively biomass, requested as the definition of the term to comply with the following requirements:

- legislative consistency

- the most diversified resource that allows the business to adapt to possible fluctuations in the wood market (wood or wood products that come directly from exploitation activities, from processing, sorting activities, wood that comes from recycling, and even imported biomass),

- eligible biomass, which, according to the definition, generates minimal acquisition costs,
- clear legal provisions, which do not generate interpretations, regarding the

traceability documents for the eligible biomass categories.

At the same time, the authority responsible for forestry had to take into account, in the elaboration of the normative act, the social component - providing the necessary firewood

for the population, the ecological component - sustainable management of forests and the economic component- the optimal usage of wood, and, last but not least, the requests of economic operators in the wood industry.

Table 1

Categories of biomass from forestry and eligible related industries, according to the renewable energy promotion system

Law 220/2008	MO no. 1341/2012	MO no. 85/2013	MO no. 1534/2016	MO no. 2303/2020
the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues of biological origin from agriculture (including plant and animal substances), forestry and related industries, including fishing and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste, codified according to legal provisions.	a) firewood from branches; b) firewood resulting from logging activities c) firewood from round wood; d) sawdust; e) waste from primary wood processing; f) wood chips.	a) firewood from branches; b) firewood resulting from logging activities; c) firewood from round wood; d) sawdust; e) waste from primary and secondary wood processing f) wood chips.	a) the biodegradable fraction of the products resulting from the primary and secondary processing of wood on the territory of Romania - bark, sawdust, chips resulting from processing, wood ends, chippings from profiling lines, wood scraps, resulting from the processing or recycling of wood material and/or of wood products, including imports, which do not fall into the category of wood materials, according to the legal provisions in force, as well as wood material downgraded in its premises as a result of the technological process of wood material processing; b) wood chips, originating only from the categories included in letter a).	a) the biodegradable fraction of the products resulting from the primary and secondary processing on the territory of Romania of wood harvested from the national territory or from import/intra-community exchanges - bark, sawdust, wood in the form of chips or particles, wood shavings from profiling lines, wood ends and the flanks of the logs, wood scraps, resulting from the processing or recycling of wood materials, as well as wood materials degraded in the own premises as a result of the technological process of processing wood materials; b) wood chips, originating only from the categories included in letter a).

Although the definition of biomass in Law no. 220/2008 is the most comprehensive and has the widest applicability, the content of normative administrative acts, respectively subsequent ministerial orders, elaborated by the central public authority responsible for forestry, presents particularized definitions with a high degree of variability.

M.O. no. 1341/ 2012 defines biomass using the criterion regarding the activity from which it originates. Art.1 of the Procedure of May 3, 2012 for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass originating from forestry and related industries classifies two major categories of biomass: that originating from the phase of exploitation of wood mass and eventual sorting (letters a, b, and c of art. 1 of the PROCEDURE of May 3, 2012) and that derived from wood processing activities (letters d, e, and f of art. 1 of the PROCEDURE of May 3, 2012). The definition of the category of biomass coming from the wood mass exploitation and

sorting phase met many of the requirements of RES energy producers, especially those that did not also own wood processing units, by the existence of this category on the market with low costs in terms of acquisition, collection and transport.

In 2013, the biomass users for energy production requested the completion of the existing normative act and thus M.O. no. 85/ 2013 introduces a new type of biomass from industrialization, through the phrase *secondary processing at point e of art. 1 of the procedure – primary and secondary processing waste*.

In 2016, as a result of the experience gained during the 4 years of application of M.O. no. 1341/2012 and the changes that occurred on the wood market, a new normative act was developed to regulate the procedure for issuing certificates of origin.

The new normative act majorly modifies the previous provisions, by redefining biomass, by priority reporting on the provision of

firewood for the population, respectively the principle of cascade use of biomass. According to the European Commission (European Commission, Guidelines on biomass cascading, with a selection of examples of good practices in woody biomass, 2019) "woody biomass cascading refers to the circular economy commitment (1) COM(2015) 614 final. to "promote the efficient use of bioresources by disseminating best practices of biomass cascading and support innovation in the bioeconomy." The main effect of the new approach was the elimination of the first category of biomass promoted by M.O. no. 1341/ 2012, respectively that of firewood from exploitation residues and that of round wood. The new regulation also brings a delimitation of the meaning of biomass, by introducing the criterion regarding the place of its production, limiting biomass to what is produced strictly on the territory of Romania, an aspect not regulated by previous orders issued in 2012 and 2013. The direct consequence, for the users of biomass, of the two essential changes was the need to identify new sources of supply and the focus on economic operators that process wood materials.

Through the emergence of Law no. 197 of September 7, 2020 for the amendment and completion of Law no. 46/2008 - The Forestry Code changes the definition of wood materials (Annex 1, point 23 of Law no. 46/2008-Forestry Code), which indirectly influences the procedure for issuing certificates of origin approved by OM no. 1534/2016.

The amendments to the Forestry Code include in the category of wood materials wood in the form of chips or particles, sawdust, wood shavings, tree bark and wood scraps

The definition of biomass ("bark, sawdust, chips resulting from processing, ends, chippings from profiling lines, wood scraps, results from the processing or recycling of wood material and/or wood products, including imports, **which do not fall under category of woody materials**"), prior to the amendments introduced by Law 197/2020, explicitly excluded any woody material from the biomass categories eligible for obtaining certificates of origin.

In this context, the competent authority in issuing the notices - the Forest Guard - implemented the new regulation, the direct result being the refusal to approve significant quantities of biomass. The legislative inconsistency has had a major negative impact on RES energy producers.

Approximately three months after the appearance of the previously mentioned normative act, the Order of the Minister of Environment, Water and Forests no. 2303 of December 18, 2020 regarding the amendment and completion of the Procedure for issuing certificates of origin for biomass originating from forestry and related industries and used in the production of electricity from renewable energy sources, approved by Order of the Minister of Environment, Water and Forests no. 1,534/2016. By issuing this regulation, the central authority responsible for forestry correlated the two normative acts, redefining biomass as the biodegradable fraction of the products resulting from the primary and secondary processing on the territory of Romania of wood harvested from the national territory or from import/intra-community exchanges - bark , sawdust, wood in the form of chips or particles, chippings from profiling lines, ends and sides of logs, wood scraps, resulting from the processing or recycling of wood materials.

- b) The evolution of the way of drawing up the documentation requested and submitted by the producers of electricity from renewable sources; From the content viewpoint, the documentation submitted by the producers of electricity from renewable sources has changed over time, the main reasons being:
- The need to check the legality and eligibility of the quantities of biomass proposed for approval
 - Legislative changes in the field of movement of wood materials and their definition
 - Streamlining the approval process and digitizing the activity.

Table 2

Comparative presentation of the regulations regarding the content of the documentation required for issuing the opinion related to the certificates of origin

M.O. no. 1341/2012	M. O. no. 85/2013	M.O. no. 1534/2016	M.O. no. 2303/2020
<p>a) request, with nomination of the attached documents;</p> <p>b) the slip of the accompanying notices of the wooden materials that constituted a resource for the production of electricity, as well as the copies of the respective accompanying notices.</p> <p>(2) In the case of the use of waste from the processing of wood materials in their own premises, without transporting them on public roads, the requests of the producers of electricity from renewable energy sources are accompanied by the minutes of sawing or any other documents from which they result with certainty the amount of resulting waste, in copy</p>	<p>a) request, with the nomination of the attached documents;</p> <p>b) the slip and notice copies of the wooden materials accompanying notices with receipts made or, as the case may be, the slip and copies of the goods accompanying notices with receipts made, for the biomass from forestry and related industries that constituted a resource for the production of electricity</p> <p>(2) In the case of the use of the biomass from the processing of wood materials in their own premises within the work points belonging to electricity producers from renewable energy sources, without this biomass requiring transport on public roads, the requests of the respective producers are accompanied by copies of the sawing/transformation/shredding reports or any other document, as the case may be, from which the amount of resulting biomass can be seen, specifying the forest species used and the humidity of the resulting biomass</p>	<p>a) request, whose model is foreseen in annex no. 2;</p> <p>b) copy of the administrative act issued by the national regulatory authority in the field of energy, proving that the applicant is a producer of electricity from renewable energy sources; this is submitted on the date of the first request and whenever there are changes to it;</p> <p>c) the slip of the accompanying goods notices and receipts made according to the model provided in annex no. 3; it is presented in written and electronic format that allows tabular calculation;</p> <p>d) copies of the notices accompanying the goods, as well as of all the documents drawn up on the occasion of reception</p> <p>- the receipt note and/or the weight slip - for the biomass from forestry and related industries purchased for the production of electricity;</p> <p>e) the slip of the internal documents and those generated from SUMAL: - the sorting report/declassification report/production report/transformation report/grinding report/shredding report, regarding the biomass production, according to the model provided in annex no. 4, which includes the documents underlying the production of biomass defined in art. 1 paragraph (1) in own production; it is presented in an electronic format that allows the tabular calculation; the situation of the log and timber warehouse, consumption receipts/outgoing documents, related to the period for which the approval is requested;</p> <p>f) situation plan of the biomass deposit in stereo coordinates 1970, according to the obligation provided for in art. 1 paragraph (2); this is submitted on the date of the first request and whenever there are changes to it.</p> <p>(2) In order to make clear possible inconsistencies regarding the quantities and documents presented, the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry may request any other document it considers relevant or may carry out checks.</p> <p>(3) The documents provided for in paragraph (1) letter a), c), e) and f) must be registered and appropriated by the applicant's legal representative.</p>	-

The first regulation in the field – M.O. no. 1341/ 2012 – required a documentation certifying the provenance and quantity of biomass used for the issuance of the approval necessary to obtain the certificate of origin. Its content stipulated the existence of the following documents: the application, the bill of approvals accompanying the wood materials, the copies of these approvals, as well as the minutes of the wood mass declassification in its own premises. In the case of the biomass coming from wood processing (according to art. 1 letters d, e, and f of the PROCEDURE of May 3, 2012 for issuing certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries), the documents certifying the origin were the accompanying notices of the goods, which is why, by M.O. no. 85/ 2013, it is required to integrate the wooden material accompanying notices and the goods accompanying notices into the slips, with the mention of the related receptions carried out. M.O. 85/2013 also brings a new element, namely the request that the notices to mention

the reception carried out. The purpose of the change had a just cause, to introduce a verification key between the content of the document issued by the supplier and the quantity received by the user.

The first regulation in the field – M.O. no. 1341/ 2012 – required a documentation certifying the provenance and quantity of biomass used for the issuance of the approval necessary to obtain the certificate of origin. Its content stipulated the existence of the following documents: the application, the bill of approvals accompanying the wood materials, the copies of these approvals, as well as the minutes of declassification of the wood mass in its own premises. In the case of biomass from wood processing (according to art. 1 letters d, e, and f of the PROCEDURE of May 3, 2012 for issuing certificates of origin for biomass from forestry and related industries), the documents certifying the origin were the accompanying notices of the goods, which is why, by OM no. 85/ 2013, it is required to integrate the wooden material accompanying notices and the goods

accompanying notices into the slips, with the mention of the related receptions carried out. OM 85/2013 also brings a new element, namely the request that the notices mention the reception carried out. The purpose of the change had a just cause, to introduce a verification key between the content of the document issued by the supplier and the quantity received by the user.

The third normative act that regulated the procedure - M.O. no. 1534/ 2016 - completed the initial list of documents requested for approval, with three other documents: copy of the administrative act issued by the national authority for regulation in the field of energy, situation plan of the biomass deposit in stereo coordinates 1970, as well as the records from SUMAL regarding the situation of the log warehouse. This regulation brings something new in terms of the documentation submission format and regulates the digital submission of slips related to accompanying notices for data processing and storage. The situations identified in practice, but also the need to avoid the access of the competent authority to the relevant

documents, led to a timely completion of the normative act, namely the stipulation of the possibility of requesting any relevant documents by the advising entity.

The last amendment to the procedure, carried out by M.O. no. 2303/2020, did not generate changes regarding the content of the documentation.

In conclusion, there is an increase in the number of documents requested in the approval procedure, an aspect motivated by:

- The practical experience gained in the approval procedure
 - The need to verify the provenance for all categories and the entire amount of biomass used
 - Digitization of the approval and control process
- c) Evolution of the documentation verification procedure

The procedure underwent changes in terms of verification deadlines, remediation of the submitted documentation, but also in terms of the quality assessment of the biomass subject to approval.

Table 3

Comparative presentation of the regulations regarding the verification of the necessary documentation for the issuance of opinions related to certificates of origin

MO no. 1341/2012	MO no. 85/2013	MO no. 1534/2016	MO no. 2303/2020
Deadline for document verification			
10 days	10 days/ 5 days deadline for the communication of the need to complete or correct the documentation	20 days/ 20 days deadline for communicating the need to complete or correct the documentation/ 10 days deadline for correction/ 20 days deadline for extending the checks subject to notifying the applicant within 15 days of the date of documentation receipt	
Qualitative assessment of biomass			
(2) In situations where the elements that influence the calorific value of the biomass from the forestry and related industries are not known or cannot be determined, the calorific value corresponding to 30% humidity will be used	3) In the event of the absence of the exact mention of the forest species in the delivery note accompanying the wooden materials or, as the case may be, in the notice accompanying the goods, the quantity corresponding to the species with the lowest calorific value will be endorsed. 4) In the case of mention in the wooden material's accompanying notice or, as the case may be, in the goods accompanying notice, of groups of forest species under "species", the species within the respective group with the lowest calorific value will be taken into account	(2) In situations where the elements that influence the calorific value of biomass from forestry and related industries are not known or cannot be determined, the calorific value corresponding to 30% humidity will be used. (3) In the event of the absence of the exact mention of the forest species in the goods accompanying notice, the quantity corresponding to the species with the lowest calorific value, corresponding to the humidity of 30%, will be approved. (4) In the event that groups of forest species are mentioned in the goods accompanying notice as "species", the species within the respective group with the lowest calorific value, corresponding to 30% humidity, will be taken into account.	(4) In the case of mention in the wooden materials accompanying notice/goods accompanying notice of groups of forest species under "species", the species within the respective group with the lowest calorific value, corresponding to the humidity of 30 %.

The evolution of the regulations related to the deadline for the verification of documentation concerned:

- increasing the time interval related to carrying out checks,

- creating the possibility to remedy the submitted documentation,
- creating the possibility of extending the deadline for the verification of the documentation.

In terms of the quality assessment of the biomass, the changes aimed at:

- Regulation of aspects encountered in practice that were not legally resolved
- Correlation of notions with the changes made to the Forestry Code and the way to use SUMAL.

d) Methods of correcting the non-conformities identified after issuing the notices related to the certificates of origin.

During the issuance of permits for the biomass from forestry and related industries, the issuing entity - the Forest Guard - identified non-conformities or was obliged, as a result of court rulings, to modify, cancel or issue new permits. The unregulated or insufficiently regulated aspects generated divergent points of view, both between the applicant and the advising entity, as well as within the authority.

Table 4

Comparative presentation of the regulations regarding the ways of correcting the non-conformities identified after issuing the notices related to the certificates of origin

MO no. 1341/2012	MO no. 85/2013	MO no. 1534/2016	MO no. 2303/2020
In situations where, after the issuance of the certificate of origin, inadvertences or certain elements of non-compliance with reality are found regarding the legal provenance of biomass from forestry and related industries, the head of the issuing structure cancels the respective certificate of origin and communicates it to the National Energy Regulatory Authority about it within 5 working days from the date of cancellation.		<p>The permit for the biomass from forestry and related industries issued by the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry is canceled by its head by decision, in the following situations:</p> <p>a) inadvertences or certain elements of non-compliance with reality regarding the legal provenance of the biomass from forestry and related industries;</p> <p>b) inadvertences or certain elements of non-conformity with reality regarding the inclusion in the types of biomass foreseen in art. 1;</p> <p>c) in the case of final and irrevocable decisions issued by the courts;</p> <p>d) modification of the accreditation conditions of the electricity producers from renewable energy sources, if they concern the processing capacity, not communicated to the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry;</p> <p>e) at the justified request of the central public authority responsible for forestry.</p> <p>(2) In the event of cancellation of the approval for the biomass from forestry and related industries, the head of the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry communicates this to the central public authority responsible for forestry within 5 working days from the date of cancellation.</p> <p>3) The certificate of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries is canceled by the head of the central public authority responsible for forestry by administrative act, in the following situations:</p> <p>a) inadvertences or certain elements of non-compliance with reality regarding the legal provenance of the biomass from forestry and related industries;</p> <p>b) inadvertences or certain elements of non-conformity with reality regarding the inclusion in the types of biomass foreseen in art. 1;</p> <p>c) in the case of final and irrevocable decisions issued by the courts;</p> <p>d) modification of the accreditation conditions of electricity producers from renewable energy sources, if they concern the processing capacity, not communicated to the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry;</p> <p>e) in case of cancellation of the approval for biomass from forestry and related industries issued by the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry, which was the basis for issuing the certificate of origin for biomass from forestry and related industries.</p> <p>(4) In the event of the cancellation of the certificate of origin for biomass from forestry and related industries, the head of the central public authority responsible for forestry communicates this to the National Energy Regulatory Authority and the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry, within 5 working days from the date of cancellation.</p> <p>(5) The cancellation of the permit for the biomass from forestry and related industries, as well as the related certificate of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries, will be carried out for the quantities for which inconsistencies with reality were found, as defined in paragraph (1) and paragraph (3); for the quantities for which no non-conformities are found, the specialized territorial structure of the central public authority responsible for forestry issues a new permit, and the central public authority responsible for forestry issues a new certificate of origin.</p> <p>(6) Certificates of origin for the biomass from forestry and related industries for which cancellation was ordered shall be communicated to the National Energy Regulatory Authority, within a maximum of 5 working days from this date.</p>	

The method of identification and resolution of non-conformities provided by art. 8 of the PROCEDURE of May 3, 2012 for issuing

certificates of origin for biomass from forestry and related industries, approved by OM no. 1341/2012, was presented without specifying

the type of non-compliance or the reason that would generate the cancellation of the approval for biomass from forestry and related industries.

Following the situations encountered in practice, the requests of the courts, the legal provisions have acquired a specific aspect, directly identifying the situations that can lead to the cancellation or modification of the opinion or the certificate of origin, as well as the persons responsible and the terms in which they can operate changes.

CONCLUSIONS

The evolution of the legislation regarding the issuance of certificates of origin for biomass from forestry and related industries aimed at adapting the regulation to the need for higher utilization of wood, establishing an efficient and quick control procedure, correlation with other normative acts in forestry, as well as the way to correct some possible non-conformities identified after the biomass certification.

In the future, it is necessary to reanalyze the way of the system of promoting energy from renewable sources in correlation with: the real ecological impact of the use of biomass from forestry and related industries, ensuring the need for electricity and thermal energy for the population and optimizing energy production capacities.

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DESIGNING AND CREATING A RELATED DATABASE CURRENT ACTIVITIES IN THE FORESTRY SECTOR

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Field data related to current activities in the forestry sector are stored in a relational database, which contains several tables organized by well-defined themes in which the information is recorded and connected to each other through relationships. In order to manage the information in the database, form-type objects are defined for entering data, queries for summarizing and selecting the information of interest and reports for the statistical synthesis of the data and arranging them for printing. Taking into account the facilities offered by modern information gathering and processing technologies, it is necessary to implement IT systems in the management and management structures of the forest fund, regardless of the owner and administrator. It is also necessary to create complex databases relating to all aspects of the managed and managed forest fund, thus having full control over both technical decisions and the results of their application. It is recommended to update the databases whenever various interventions are completed in order to quantify the quantitative and qualitative aspects. This database represents one of the options currently possible. In the future, new tools can be used, and high-performance databases can be created, taking into account the current logistical possibilities, and respectively the upward trend in the IT field.

Keywords: relational database, forms, queries, reports, activities in the forestry sector

INTRODUCTION

The information is stored in an organized manner in a computerized database. The database file is a container that stores objects such as tables, forms, queries and reports. These objects are used to store, classify and manage the information stored in the database (Curilă M. et al, 2019).

A table in a database stores information in rows called records and columns called fields. A record in a table contains information about an item. The record is composed of information elements stored in fields, which follow each other in the same order in each record (Curilă M. et al, 2019).

In order to maximize the flexibility of the database, the information is organized in tables on different themes, well outlined, so that there are no redundancies. In order to share the information divided by themes, the tables are connected to each other by links.

Forms are graphical interfaces used to work with information in a database, to enter, view, or edit data in tables, and often contain

command buttons that perform various commands.

For this purpose, forms contain graphic elements called controls, which are associated with fields in database tables or various operations with it. A control is a graphical user interface object, such as a text box, check box, drop-down menu, or command button, that allows the user to control the program. Controls are used to display data or options, perform an action, or make the user interface more pleasant (Curilă M. et al, 2019).

Forms also allow you to control how users interact with the information in the database. Thus, the data is protected and it is ensured that the data is entered correctly.

Queries are questions asked of the database. Their most common function is to retrieve specific data from tables. Usually the data that you want to see is in several tables, and queries allow you to view it in a single data sheet. Additionally, if you don't want to see all the records at once, queries allow you to add criteria to filter the data and display only the records you want.

Queries are divided into two types: selection queries and action queries. A select query retrieves the data and makes it available for use. The results of a query can be viewed, or used as a record source for a form or report. An action query performs an activity with the data. Action queries can be used to create new tables, add data to existing tables, update data, or delete data.

Queries allow you to specify the table fields that appear in the query, as well as sorting and filtering criteria for those fields. The query can contain fields taken from one or more tables if there are links between them. Also, the query can contain calculated fields whose data source is an expression - a character string that can consist of operators, functions, field references, or constants (Jennings R., 2000).

Thus, when the query is run, the calculations defined by the expression are performed and the results are displayed.

Sorting is the process of ordering a set of records so that an ascending or descending order criterion is respected relative to a certain field. Sorting by more than one field can provide more accurate results.

The filter criteria identify the records that will be included in the query result, limiting the display to only those records that match the invoked conditions. A filter can be seen as a rule that is specified for a field. This identifies the values in the field that will be seen. Such a criterion is treated as an expression.

Reports are used to synthesize and present information from the database in the most readable way possible. A report consists of information extracted from underlying tables or queries called record sources and information stored with the design of the report, such as labels and graphics (Curilă M. et al, 2019).

Additionally, more complex reports contain a hierarchy of grouping and sorting levels or statistical summaries relative to the fields considered for the report.

To display information on its surface, the report uses graphic elements called controls, which are of three types: bound, unbound, and calculated. A control whose data source is a field in a table or query is a bound control. Bound controls are used to display values from database fields. A control that does not have a data source (a field or an expression) is an unbound control. Unbound controls are used to display information, lines, images, etc. A control whose data source is not a field but an

expression is a calculated control. You specify the value of the control by defining an expression as the data source for the control (Curilă M. et al, 2019).

An expression is a combination of operators, control names, field names, functions that return a value, and constants. The expression can use data from a field in the table or query underlying the report, or from a control in the report. The functions that can be used in an expression are those provided by the application and allow the calculation of the following statistics: Sum, Arithmetic Mean, Record Count, Value Count, Maximum, Minimum, Standard Deviation and Variance (Habracken J., 2002).

When a calculated control is placed in the group footer, the statistic is calculated from the current group's data and displayed below it. If the calculated control is placed in the footer of the report, the statistic is calculated from the data of the entire report and displayed at the end of the report.

Data collection from the field. Currently, in the forestry sector, the collection of data from the field is carried out by the technical and field staff mostly on analogue media (field records) and later they are sent to the secretariat of the bypass, sometimes through the departments of the forestry units .

The only data that are collected from the field and transmitted electronically are those that are made with the help of the SUMAL 2.0 platform, namely the inventory of wood products, the handing over of parcels (of the areas that have been exploited), the return of the parcels (of the areas that have been exploited), notices electronics related to the wooden material to be transported, minutes of sorting of the exploited wood (Matei L., 2022).

In the case of the inventory of wood products, the procedure is much simpler than the classic one - on analog support, because it makes work more efficient.

A series of changes are still expected for the handing over or taking back of parquets (the surfaces from which the wood products were exploited), aimed at simplifying the work procedure (currently their listing is done only by certain persons, an aspect that needs to be adjusted).

It is necessary that in the future all data from the field be collected and transmitted electronically by various means - applications, electronic forms, platforms, e-mails, etc.

The use of electronic forms is effective for the following reasons:

- allow the centralization of information automatically, in a spreadsheet, from where it can be easily processed;
- data are transmitted quickly without the need to transport documents;
- the data transmitted from the field can be effectively checked by the staff involved (field staff, technical staff, control staff);
- reduction of working time and necessary supplies;
- overall efficiency of field and office activities (Matei L., 2022).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The case study was carried out in the forestry fund of the Production Unit (U.P.) III Căiuți - fig. 1, Căiuți Forest District (O.S.), Bacău County, (Matei L., 2022).

The research and study methods that were used are: documentary information,

observation on the itinerary, observation in stationary, experimental, inventory, mathematical modeling, simulation, comparison, photography and digital recording of the objective reality in the field (Crainic G. C. et al, 2020).

To carry out this case study, the following logistical base was used: the forest management related to the Căiuți III production unit, forest plans and maps related to the Căiuți III production unit, cameras, GPS receivers, total station, scanner, programs for harvesting data from the field, programs for data transfer, programs for data processing, programs for archiving data and respectively obtaining and organizing the database, and implicitly the computer system, PCs for data processing, Excel program, peripherals for obtaining final products in analog format (Crainic G. C. et al, 2020; Matei L., 2022).

Figure 1-Location of the study on the forest map used

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the present case, the technical and field personnel who have duties within the UP III Caiuti area (District III Bogdana) only need access to the main platform and then select from the platform menu the ELECTRONIC DOCUMENTS page or the compartment where

they want to transmit a certain document - Photo 1, Photo 2.

After selecting the electronic documents (forms) page, we look for the type of document (report, verbal process, report, etc.), next to electronic document filing there is also a button where we find the brief summary.

Photo 1- QR Code Electronic documents

Photo 2 - Electronic documents page

RAPORT SAPTAMANAL/LUNAR

* Obligatorii

1. DATA RAPORT *

Vă rugăm să introduceți data (dd.MM.yyyy)

2. NUME SI PRENUME *

CIUBOTARU GHEORGHE

ROSCAN ION

CERCEL CONSTANTIN

TARTOACA NICOLAE

AVRAM ROBIN

Photo 3-Weekly report

Fisa G. OBSERVATII CERB

CERB COMUNI (BONCANT) 2022

* Obligatorii

1. FONDUL CINEGETIC

51 PRAIEA

49 BALCA

48 URECHISTI

47 BORZESTI

2. DATA *

Vă rugăm să introduceți data (dd.MM.yyyy)

3. Perioada din zi *

Selecționați răspunsul

Photo 4-Sheet G OBSERVATIONS DEER

4. INTENSITATEA BONCANTITULUI *

ZERO

FOARTE SLABA

SLABA

MEDIE

PUTERNICA

FOARTE PUTERNICA

5. Locul : UP / ux *

Introduceți răspunsul

6. Altitudinea: (minima/ maxima/medie) m *

Introduceți răspunsul

7. Expoziția : *

Introduceți răspunsul

Photo 5-Sheet G DEER OBSERVATIONS (continued)

Introduceți răspunsul

20. NUME SI PRENUME *

PAD. MATEI MARIUS

PAD. GHIONOIU MARIAN

PAD. CHETREANU VALERU

PAD. CIUBOTARU GHEORGHE

PAD. ROSCAN ION

PAD. TARTOACA NICOLAE

ING. MATEI LAURENTIU

ING. GHIONOIU CATALIN

ING. ANGHIELUTA NICOLAE

ING. CIORBA CRISTINEL

PAD. GABAR IONEL

21. ÎMPREUNA CU:

Introduceți răspunsul

Remitere

Photo 6-Sheet G DEER OBSERVATIONS (continued)

Weekly/monthly exploitation report.
We open the report (blue button).

We select the date, the name and all the information required by the form. If they are known (prepared), all the information is completed in a maximum of 40 seconds, otherwise it may take even more than a

minute. After checking all the information, send it by pressing the green button. When we want to check if the information has been transmitted safely, we go to the blue button where we have a summary of the information transmitted.

Photo 7-Sheet G DEER OBSERVATIONS - completion of data entry

Photo 8-Sheet G DEER OBSERVATIONS (final report with a synthetic presentation of the results obtained)

The detailed results in excel format are visible only to the person who deals with data processing, to check all the data before centralization, drawing up some tables, signing them, sending them to the hierarchically superior structures and their superintendence.

Observation sheet Common deer. We open File G, blue button in this case, but it can be opened from many places, hunting platform, district platform, WhatsApp Group, with the help of a QR code, Photo 1, Photo 2, Photo 3-Photo 7.

We select the number and name of the hunting fund, the date, the name, we fill in all the information required by the form.

After checking all the information, it is transmitted (send) by pressing the green button.

If all the information is known (prepared), the form can be completed in a maximum of 90 seconds, otherwise it may take a little longer.

When we want to check if the information has been transmitted safely, we go to the blue button where we have a summary of the type G file (Observe Deer) - Photo 8.

The detailed results in excel format are visible only to the person who deals with the data processing, to check all the information before centralization, drawing up some tables, signing them, sending them to the hierarchical bosses and their supervisors.

Patrol report. We open the Patrol Report, blue button in the present case but it can be opened from many places, hunting platform, district platform, WhatsApp group, with the help of a QR code.

After checking all the information, send it by pressing the green button.

When we want to check if the information has been transmitted safely, we go

to the blue button where we have a summary of the patrol reports.

Data centralization and processing.

Photo 9-Application interface for the centralization and processing of data recorded in the field, with the Excel program, in the location U.P. III Caiuți, O.S. Caiuți, D.S. Bacău

Photo 10-Initialization of the process of centralizing and processing data from the field

Photo 11-Visualization and analysis of data and information related to the wood exploitation process, within the U.P. III Caiuți, O.S. Caiuți, D.S. Bacău

In the previous chapter, we mentioned that the use of electronic forms gives us a particular advantage because the results

are automatically centralized in an EXCEL where they can be easily retrieved and also in

Excel, all the desired tables for reports and required situations can be loaded automatically.

UP III Caiuti and UP IV Bogdana together form District III Bogdana and all information from the field (for the most part) is first centralized at the district level and then transmitted to the surrounding area.

As the main point of departure, we have the district platform where we find everything about UP III Caiuti.

Data processing and storage at the district level is done in OneDrive for maximum security and the possibility of accessing the information of several people from several places, devices regardless of time, time.

Some examples: Record of exploited wood.

Management of timber exploitation by forestry personnel. Wood evaluation act no. 607.

In the activity of wood exploitation by the forestry staff, the manager of the wood assortments, must always have an up-to-date stock situation (MANAGEMENT BOOK) Using Excel for issuing slips and N.I.Rs, we have at our disposal a double control (the record cross) considering that the current situation can also be listed from the SUMAL 2.0 program. Using the Excel program, we have an electronic management book, with all up-to-date records. (stocks of wood material, notices, prices, types of wood and others).

The link from the district platform to the excel file of a wood exploitation and valorization act, by forestry personnel (act no. 607), N.I.R., document and money deposit slip, record of electronic notices.

Wood exploitation activity by economic agents. The link between the district database platform (with the Excel program) for an act of exploitation and valorization of wood by an economic agent (act no. 484), provides information about the exploitation process, carried out by the economic agent (with all the related particularities).

In the framework of the wood exploitation process by economic agents, the development of the exploitation and valorization process is followed very carefully, on relatively small, delimited areas, from a technical point of view, in order to comply with the forestry rules of exploitation in force, but also from the point of view from a financial point of view (the wood payment is usually made on these delimited surfaces).

CONCLUSIONS

Creating the database itself is useful, but the most important thing is how it is done, with the information received from the field. With the help of electronic forms, the data are entered in real time in an excel that are processed automatically and can create centralizing tables and reports necessary for the preparation of specific works for a certain department.

The use of the database is an effective way of realizing some situations related to the field activity, carried out within a UP, forestry canton, compartment in the center of the bypass.

From the analysis of the results of the present case study, it can be observed that a number of three online platforms have been created, in total with over 200 web pages that can be developed, modified at any time, a number of over 100 folders in OneDrive with content of 7,601 .753 KB. where you can find excel, word, pdf documents, maps, images.

The use of this database means the digitization of the forestry, forestry, hunting domain up to the forester, exploitation foreman, game warden.

This database can be redone, adaptable for other production units, districts, forest areas, hunting associations, exploitation companies...etc.

The database can be queried very simply from anywhere with the help of a personal password. The people who access this atabase can manage, modify, process certain files and documents depending on the permission received from the main administrator, creating a functional system that can be easily developed.

The advantages of collecting digital information is a real advantage because everything is saved in OneDrive and a unit connected to the Internet, we have a double save for safety. If by mistake or on purpose the database in the central unit is destroyed, it can

be restored relatively quickly in conditions of maximum efficiency without losing information.

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- *** Forest map of U.P. III Căiuți, O.S. Caiuți, D.S. Bacau;
- *** Excel program.

RESEARCH ON 5724 TURKEY OAK-SESSIL OAK WITH COMMON HORNBEAM MIXED STAND WITH *GLECHOMA-GEUM* (REGIONAL VARIANT WITH STAGNANT LUVOSOL OF A NEW TYPE) WITHIN THE SEGMENT OF LANDSCAPE SITUATED ON LOW WESTERN HILLS OF TINCA FOREST DISTRICT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Forest typology evolved from the necessity of differentiating management measures of the forests according to composition, structure, productivity, features of the stands, i.e. after their eco-systemic features (Doniță et al., 1990). In this type of forest ecosystem the nucleus of constant species consists of: *Quercus polycarpa*, *Q. cerris*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Geum urbanum*, *Glechoma hirsuta*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Galium schultesii*, *Ajuga reptans*, *Geranium robertianum*, *Stachys sylvatica*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Lapsana communis*, *Veronica officinalis*, *V. Chamaedrys*, *Festuca heterophylla*, *Poa nemoralis*, *Melica uniflora*

Keywords: forest ecosystems, geographical segment landscape, ecological landscape environment, sustainable forestry

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INTRODUCTION

The Low Hills, situated in the southwestern part of the study area, have average altitudes of 200-300 m, have reduced vertical fragmentation, with flat or slightly curved interfluves, elongated slopes and mid values inclinations. The valleys are rare, the clay deposits conditioning the formation of heavy soils, and on slopes the clay-loam deposits, with alternation of sand and gravel deposits, conditioning the formation of normal hydric soils.

The relief is fragmented by valleys, the slopes being the main relief form, but also extended plateaus. On slopes, the sedimentary formations of sand, loam, clay, gravel, caused the formation of basic stagnic luvisols, at most mid basic, with a well-balanced hydric regime and on few areas eutricambosols, more fertile and with a well-balanced hydric regime.

The aim of the study was to establish the main forest ecosystem type within Tinca Forest District and to establish the state of these ecosystems in order to find the best management solution for a sustainable use, preserving and conserving the optimum biodiversity of the forest. The aim of the research was also the scientific fundamentation,

very useful both in forest management and in applied forestry, in order to find the best management solutions for a sustainable use. The soil indicators herbaceous and shrub layer consists of: *Festuca drymeja*, *Carex pilosa*, *Asperula-Asarum-Stellaria*. These types characterize stationary low-hill ecosystems where there are also soils with higher trophic levels, with balanced hydric regime, due to richer precipitation and permeable soils. Also, in the western low hills we meet: *Genista-Glechoma-Geum* type. This characterizes the ecosystems on moderately acid - weakly acid soils, with more a medium trophicity and with a quasi-balanced water hydric regime.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The locations of the research are the forests administrated by Tinca Forest District; the study has started in 2021 and continued in 2022.

The forest ecosystems were analyzed according to **location** within the study area; **the features of the ecosystem type**: surface area, geographical parameters (average altitude, altitude range); relief forms: types, inclination of the slopes, slope exposition, lithology, soil types and subtypes, ecological limitative factors); the description of the stands, the

description of the herbaceous layer; the **correspondence with:** types of forests, types of stations, plant associations, types of habitat, **present state of the stands and management measures (particularities):** main features, distribution according to age classes, the source of main elements, natural regeneration, productivity classes, management measures, variability and succession tendency (forms of type, successional tendencies and forest facies).

The description of the forest ecosystem was made based on collected field data. In order to analyze the collected data were used different softwares, such as Excel, ArcGis.

After determining the types, they were mapped by researching all the planning units and classifying them into types, considering the composition of the trees, the type of grass-subshrub layer, the type of humus (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The delimitation method of the forest ecosystems had as base some typological schemes made for the study area (for ex forest corps) (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The landscaping units with non-native species cultures were classified into types based on the type of resort.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

TYPE OF ECOSYSTEM: 5724 Turkey oak-Sessil oak with common hornbeam mixed stand, high and medium productive on typical and stagnant luvosols, oligomesobasic, hydric quasi-balanced with *Glechoma-Geum* (regional variant with stagnant luvosol of a new type of ecosystem)

Subtypes:

57241 highly productive subtype

57242 mid productive subtype.

Dispersion: this type of forest ecosystem is distributed in the low hills within: U.P.II - Trup Coltău - Șirinca; U.P.III - Trup Pădurea Gorunului, Trup Gânteii; U.P.IV - Trup Tinca - Topile, Trup Cărânzăel, Trup Dumbrava, Trup Valea Mare, Trup Holod - Hodiș, Trup Cărândeni, Trup Bicăcel, Trup Miheleu - Topile; U.P.V - Trup Hodișel, Trup Măgura.

Characteristics of the type of ecosystem within the researched area:

a. Surface: 3357 ha.

b. Forest sites:

- average altitude 225 m (altitude variation 150-300 m);

- relief: by shape - middle and lower slope, less often upper slope and plateau; by slope: moderate and strong slopes, flat terrain; after the exhibition - mostly shady or partly sunny

slopes, rarely sunny;

- type of rock: sandy clays alternating with clays, sands, gravels

- types and subtypes of soil: Typical and stagnant Luvisol, rarely Eutricambosols;

- limiting ecological factors: soils with higher compactness in the Btw horizon, the decrease in soil moisture in the second part of summer, especially on sunny slopes, cely soil at low consistencies.

c. Compositions of the stands: in the dominant floor of *Quercus petraea ssp. polycarpa*, rarely and *Quercus petraea ssp. dalechampii*, *Quercus cerris*, in varying proportions, more rarely *Quercus robur*, *Quercus frainetto*, *Prunus avium*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*; in the dominated floor it is met *Carpinus betulus* on 10-60% of the surface, *Sorbus torminalis*, *Acer campestre*, *Acer tataricum*. *Quercus frainetto* achieves the facies proportion in some situations.

d. Compositions of the sub-stands: *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*; *Cornus mas*, *Rubus caesius* and *Rosa canina* it may occur with reduced frequency. Shrubs are generally variably developed and spread unevenly, in the portions with less hornbeam, covering 5% - 30% of the surface. *Carpinus betulus* it is also present in the subtree level, covering 5% - 50% of the surface, in some situations *Acer tataricum*, *Acer campestre* and *Quercus cerris* can still be found.

The subtree is variably developed, covering 10% - 50% of the surface, depending on the degree of illumination.

e. Composition of the herbaceous layer: *Geum urbanum*, *Glechoma hirsuta*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Galium schultesii*, *Ajuga reptans*, *Geranium robertianum*, *Stachys sylvatica*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Lapsana communis*, *Veronica officinalis*, *V. chamaedrys*, *Festuca heterophylla*, *Poa nemoralis*, *Hieracium umbellatum*, *Carex sylvatica*, *C. divulsa*, *Melica uniflora*, *Dactylis polygama*, *Potentilla micrantha*, *Lychnis coronaria*, *Lysimachia nummularia*, *L. vulgaris*, *Juncus effusus*, *Viola reichenbachiana*. In some surfaces with more clayey soils, the presence of the *Carex pilosa*, marks the middle productive subtype.

Among the sub-shrub species can be found *Chamaecytisus hirsutus* and *Cytisus nigricans*.

Among the lianas they can be found *Hedera helix* and *Tamus communis*.

The grassy layer is developed unevenly, in patches, with variable coverage of 10% - 50%

of the surface, depending on the degree of illumination.

Figure 1: Turkey oak-Sessile oak with common hornbeam mixed stand with Glechoma-Geum in u.a. 94E, U.P.IV Topile area, (photo - P.T. Moțiu)

Correspondence with:

- **Forest types²: 7115** - Sessile oak - *Quercus cerris* of superior productivity(s); **7511** – hill Șleao- *Quercus cerris* with Sessile oak (m) (situations without *Tilia*);

- **Resort types³: 6.3.1.1.** – Hilly oak (Sessile oak, *Quercus cerris* ± *Quercus frainetto*) Pm, luvosols, including whitish luvosols (± **hypostagnic**) medium edaphic, with mesoxerophyte grasses; **6.3.1.2.** - *Quercus frainetto* (*Quercus petraea*, *Quercus petraea* - elms, hilly elm with Sessile oak ± **Quercus cerris**, **Quercus frainetto**) Ps, luvosols (± **hypostagnic**), highly edaphic, with mesoxerophytic grasses and elements of mull flora;

- **Vegetable associations⁴: *Quercetum petraea - cerris*** Soó 57 (mostly);

- **Type of habitat⁵: R4132** - Pannonian-Balkan sessile oak forests (*Quercus petraea*) and Oak (*Quercus cerris*) (beech) (*Fagus sylvatica*) with *Melittis melissophyllum*.

The current state of stands and management measures (peculiarities):

f. The structure of the stands: Figure 2 shows the distribution of the number of trees by diameters, and Figure 3 shows the vertical and horizontal structure of a representative arboretum, inventoried in u.a.94E, U.P.IV. Composition of the tree: 3Go 3Ce 3Ca 1Fa, 95 years old, number of trees per hectare: gorun - 60, cer - 24, hornbeam - 200, beech - 28.

g. Distribution according to age intervals: 0-5 years old - 1%; 6-10 years old - 13%; 11-20 years old - 11%; 21-40 years old - 23%; 41-80 years old - 50%; over 80 years old - 6%.

h. The source of the main elements of the stand: sessile oak - natural sowing 25%, shoots 58%, plantation 17%; turkey oak - natural sowing 28%, shoots 66%; common hornbeam - natural sowing 25%, shoots 75%; common beech - natural sowing 100%.

²Forest types are cited from N. Doniță et al., 2005.

³Resort types are cited from F. Dănescu, C. Costăchescu, Elena Mihăil, 2010.

⁴Vegetal associations are cited from N. Doniță et al., 1990, and the types of new ecosystems, after V. Sanda, A. Popescu, D. I. Stanciu, 2001.

⁵The habitat types are cited from N. Doniță et al., 2005.

Figure 2: The distribution of tree numbers per hectare in stand, according to diameter categories and species in u.a. 94E, U.P.IV Topile area

Legend:

Quercus petraea

Quercus cerris

Carpinus betulus

Fagus sylvatica

Figure 3: The diagram of vertical structure (left) and plan projection of the canopy (right) for test plot of 1250 sqm, using SVS software, 3.36 version, in u.a. 94E, U.P.IV Topile area

i. Production classes of the main species of the stand: Go cl III/II; Ce cl III/II; Ca cl III/IV; Ca cl II.

j. Natural regeneration through seeding: active especially in case of *Quercus cerris*, but also in case of *Quercus petraea* and *Fagus sylvatica*, weak in case of *Quercus robur*, good in case of *Acer campestre*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Prunus avium*.

k. Indicated composition: 6Go 2Ce(St,Gâ) 2Ca,Sr,Ju,Ar,Pă.

l. Management measures on age intervals: 0-5 years - uncovering natural regenerations and/or plantations especially of species of the genus *Rubus*, complementing the regenerations with sessile oak plantations to increase the proportion of this species and with mixed species if needed; 6-10 years - removal of oaks, removal of Eurasian aspen and of goat willow; 11-20 years - proportioning the mixture, through cleanings, keeping enough species of the mixture in addition to the oak; 21-

40 years - choosing the trees of the future (come from the seed) and applying the first combined thinning around these trees; 41-80 years - continuing the combined thinning, proportioning the mixture to achieve the target composition; over 80 years - combined low-intensity thinning, if necessary, applying hygiene cuts and helping the natural regeneration of the main species by cutting the hornbeam sublevel and the too dense subtree.

m. Other management measures: the conversion of stands originating from shoots, either through natural regeneration, to fruiting, or through restoration; replacement of hornbeam and of stands with non-native species, stationary not indicated, with trees of native species.

n. Variability and successional trends (forms of type, successional tendencies and forest facies): within this type of forest ecosystem, the natural tendency is to eliminate sessile oak by the turkey oak and hornbeam, in

high quality resorts, with Eutricambosol soil (especially in the lower third of the slopes) producing the natural succession towards the type of ecosystem **7214** - Turkey oak with common hornbeam stand with *Arum-Brachypodium*. On sunny or partially sunny slopes, we find the transition form to the type **5524** - Turkey oak-Sessile oak with common hornbeam mixed stand with *Asperula-Asarum-Stellaria*, and on shaded slopes we meet the form of transition to the type **5225** - Sessile oak with common hornbeam stand with *Carex pilosa*. On flat places we find the form of transition to the form of a plateau with sessile oak within the type **7135** - Turkey oak stand with *Genista-Festuca heterophylla*. **Silvofacies:** with sycamore, Norway maple, cherry and wild service tree (mix in bouquets or groups with coverage up to 40% in the composition of the stand); with manna ash, with black alder - near the valleys, where the seasonal conditions are favorable for these species, they achieve the 2nd class of production.

o. Observations: In favorable conditions (with Eutricambosol soils), on high-quality resorts, hornbeam achieves the 2nd class of production.

Lower productivity on soils with a compacted B horizon (marked by the presence of the *Carex pilosa* species); the tendency of partial or total derivation through the elimination of sessile oak and replacement with hornbeam.

It is the stagnant luvisol regional variant of a new ecosystem type.

CONCLUSIONS

Knowing the physical-geographical conditions of the territory in which researches were carried out, are important for knowing the ecological complex of factors and determinants of the forest ecosystem biotope (forestry resort) (Chiriță et al., 1964; Chiriță et al., 1977). Therefore, it is evident that the regional variants of forest ecosystem types arise due to the influence of regional variants of climate and soil – pedogenetic sub-layers.

Regarding the regional particularities of ecosystem type

The regional variant of the turkey oak-sessile oak ecosystem type with hornbeam with *Glechoma-Geum*, is given by the formation on soils with greater compactness in the Btw horizon. Another characteristic of the soil types and subtypes is the decrease in soil moisture in the second part of the summer, especially on

sunny slopes, resulting in soil compaction at reduced stand densities.

The higher the proportion of hornbeam in the stand, the better the seasonal conditions, the type of ecosystem evolving, obtaining higher productivity.

Silvicultural recommendation

Keeping hornbeam regeneration under control, within the application of silvicultural treatments, to achieve the succession of stands in good conditions, with optimal compositions for the type of forest ecosystem. Treatments with repeated cuts and regeneration under the massif are recommended, and more precisely, the treatment of progressive cuts through which the mixture can be better proportioned in favoring the sessile oak instead of turkey oak. Preparatory cuts are mandatory to extract badly shaped hornbeam specimens with defects, especially those originating from shoots; thus avoiding the transmission of their genetic characteristics in the future tree, improving the gene pool of the hornbeam population and at the same time, maintaining the desired proportion of hornbeam.

This priority of this period is to establish types of forests ecosystems on small geographic units, at the level of landscapes, the typology having thus a strong regional feature.

We tried, as the research of this paper to establish ecosystem-based forest type principal existing in a territory smaller but representative low western hill within Tinca Forest District, to state the current status of types and propose appropriate management measures this state and designed to bring a type similar to the natural state.

Regarding forestry measures by type of forest culture have revealed that there were concerns relating to differentiating normal types but not the present state of the as result of more or less proper management methods. Forester practitioner is forced to differentiate on the basis of this action and the current state of forest types that manage them

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ASPECTS REGARDING THE PREVENTION OF THE LABOUR ACCIDENTS WHEN TREE CUTTING

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Operational health and safety are essential for maintaining a high degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations. This involves identifying workplace risks and taking measures to prevent accidents. In this paper, the risk factors in the case of chainsaw workers from the experimental bases belonging to the National Institute for Research and Development in Forestry "Marin Drăcea" were highlighted. Following the application of the calculation method, a global risk factor of 2.89 was obtained, a value that places the occupation of mechanical shaper in the category of medium-risk jobs. At the same time, the factors that exceed this value were identified and analysed. Also, the risk factors on the components of the working system were analysed, respectively the risk factors specific to the executor, the work environment, the factors required to the means of production and those specific to the work load. From the analysis of the Evaluation form, it is found that 25 of the identified risk factors (62.50%) can have irreversible consequences on the performer (disability or death). Compliance with occupational health and safety regulations is the way to minimize accidents or even eliminate them.

Keywords: chainsaw workers, mechanical shapers, risk factors, forestry sector, safety and health at work
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INTRODUCTION

In forestry activities, which are quite diverse and involve the usage of machinery from the simplest to the most complex, wood harvesters are exposed during the performance of their work tasks to many and varied risk factors. The choice of machines for felling trees is made according to their dimensions, terrain relief, etc. Because of these causes, within wood harvesting activities, work accidents occur frequently, and are generally very serious because the working conditions are difficult, also. Thus, the European Agency for Health and Safety at Work (EU-OHSAS - European Agency for Safety and Health at Work) shows that the number of accidents and occupational diseases encountered in forestry workers far exceeds those in other sectors of activity (***, 2020; Iftime, 2020). The high rate of bodily injuries, occupational diseases and fatal accidents is produced by repeated exposure to an unfavourable environment (Tsioras et al, 2014; Laschi et al, 2016).

The operation of felling trees is considered the most dangerous from the point of view of worker safety, but also the one that produces the greatest damage, through the impact that the felled tree has on other trees

when it falls (Timofte et al, 2017). When the tree felling operation is carried out, all its stages must be in a visible frame to ensure protection for the workers, but also to realize the direction of the tree fall in the desired direction in safe conditions (Timofte et al, 2017).

Mechanical shapers represent the category of forest workers involved in most of work accidents because the working conditions are difficult and the effort made by them is intense. Such conditions also determine a classification of the difficulty of work taking into account energy consumption, identifying categories of hard and very hard work (Grzywinski et al, 2016). The activity of mechanical shapers is accompanied by exposure to carbon monoxide, noise, vibrations, etc. The effect of these factors manifests itself differently from one worker to another and depends on the level and time of exposure, pre-existing conditions and whether they wear protective equipment or not (Ulutasdemir et al, 2015; Dabrowski, 2015; Iftime, 2020). Moreover, the environmental, physical and physiological factors in which the mechanical shapers work determine the appearance of conditions located at the level of the vascular, nervous, muco-skeletal and auditory systems (Fonseca et al, 2015; Iftime, 2020).

Exposure to carbon monoxide from power saws causes the health of the workers to deteriorate over time. The high level of noise and vibration leads to the occurrence of Raynaud's syndrome and bilateral hearing loss which are occupational diseases (Malinowska-Borowska et al, 2012; Iftime, 2020). The vibrations to which mechanical shapers are exposed on a daily basis have the effect of numbness, tingling in the fingers, which shows vascular and neurological damage (Su et al, 2014).

Environmental factors in which mechanical shapers work such as terrain characteristics, weather conditions, etc. cause an additional physical effort with different intensity. The action of external factors on the mechanical shapers can influence his performance, his physical condition and his working time (Câmpu & Robb, 2022). These factors, especially those related to the terrain characteristics, lead to the usage of difficult body positions during work, often forced, depending on the terrain conditions. Over a long period (20-25 years), due to difficult working positions such as bending the body, twisting the trunk, etc. there is an additional risk to the health of the mechanical shaper leading to musculoskeletal disorders. Added to these is the weight of the mechanical saw used.

The specialized literature (Gallis, 2006; Grzywnski et al, 2016) mentions the fact that the symptoms of musculoskeletal conditions are manifested in mechanical shapers in the area of shoulders, neck, back and knees. If the mechanical shaper has a precarious level of professional training, such symptoms are also amplified by the stress at work. Correct and timely training of the worker can reduce the negative effects on health and prevent an accident.

The working posture when felling trees can cause an additional physiological load on the mechanical shaper. Thus, it was found that a working posture with a bent back and semi-flexed legs leads to the highest physiological load and that with semi-flexed knees to the lowest (Grzywiński et al, 2017). The results of national (Cheța et al, 2018) and international (Sawastian et al, 2015) research show that osteomusculo-articular disorders occur due to faulty wood harvesting workstations.

Occupational health and safety is a priority concern at the level of any specialized institution, being an activity with a very high socio-economic impact. Ensuring adequate

protective measures and means has positive effects for the safe conduct of work processes by reducing exposures to risk factors, awareness of risky behaviours and prevention of premature wear of the body.

The objective of the research was the analysis of risk factors in the case of mechanical shapers within the experimental bases belonging to the National Institute for Research and Development in Forestry "Marin Drăcea" (INCDS). The paper takes into account the risks to which mechanical shapers are exposed, the calculation of the global risk level and the analysis of risk factors for each category in order to reduce them and prevent work accidents.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The method used in the risk assessment was the INCDPM Bucharest method, which consists in identifying all the risk factors that appear at the workplace and analysing them based on combinations of the frequency of occurrence and the severity of the maximum consequences on the human body. The application of this method is completed with the Job evaluation form in which the global risk levels for each job are given. The job evaluation form is the basis of the program for the prevention of work accidents and occupational diseases for each individual job (Darabont et al, 2001). The method is used for starting a new activity or a job but also for exploiting the existing job.

The stages that this method involves are the following: (1) establishing the evaluation committee; (2) defining the analysed system; (3) identification of all risk factors at the workplace; (4) identification of occupational risks and illness of staff risks; (5) the ranking of risks and the establishment of priorities for their prevention; (6) proposing measures to prevent risks found following their identification.

The work tools used in the risk assessment of a job are (Darabont et. al, 2001): (1) the risk identification list; (2) the list of possible consequences of the action of the risk factors on the human body; (3) rating scale of severity and likelihood of consequences; (4) risk assessment grid; (5) the scale of ranking risk and security levels; (6) job description; (7) the sheet of proposed measures.

The global risk level (N_g) at the workplace is calculated as a weighted average of the risk levels established for the identified risk factors. In order for the obtained result to reflect reality as accurately as possible, the rank of the risk factor is used as a weighting element, which is equal to the risk level (Moraru et al, 2002), according to the relationship:

$$N_g = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^n r_p \cdot N_{sp}}{\sum_{p=1}^n r_p}$$

where: r_p – job rank "p" (equal in value to the risk level of the job);

n – the number of analysed jobs;

N_{sp} – the average level of job security for job "p".

In order to establish the necessary measures to improve the security level of the analysed work system, it is necessary to take into account the hierarchy of risks evaluated according to the Scale of classification of levels risks/security of work in the order:

- 7 – 1 if operating with risk levels;
- 1 – 7 if operating with security levels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The global risk level (N_g) calculated following the application of the INCDPM Bucharest method for the job of mechanical shaper is 2.89, a value that places it in the category of jobs with a medium risk level, not exceeding the acceptable value (3.5) (Figure 1). The result is supported by the "Evaluation form" from which it can be seen that out of the total of 39 identified risk factors, 3 exceed, as a partial risk level, the value 3, falling into the category of high risk factors (partial risk level 4). The 3 risk factors that are in the unacceptable area are:

F.1. Functional movements of work equipment (organs of machines in motion): hitting, crushing, gripping;

F.10. Flames (faults in electrical installations, ignition of wood storage);

F.14. Dangerous plants and animals (vipers, dogs, bears, wolves, wasps, ticks).

The identified risk factors lower than the average value (2.89) are 12 in number, some of them being related to environmental conditions such as natural lighting, air currents, variable temperature, which can increase or decrease on the period of a working day etc. All these factors influence the performance of the activity but are not factors with a high level of risk.

Figure 1. Partial levels of risk presented by risk factors, for the chainsaw worker

By comparing the factor obtained for the experimental bases taken into account with other results derived from research also carried out for chainsaw workers (Iftime, 2020), which obtained a factor of 3.31, it is found that some results have differences of approximately 8%. The difference between the two assessments is

0.42%, which means that some risks have decreased or have been eliminated.

The analysis of risk factors on components of the work system shows some similarity with those obtained from the specialized literature (Figure 2). The executor's own risk factors calculated for the analysed experimental bases are 30.00% slightly higher

than those calculated in other researches which are 27.59% (Iftime, 2020). This shows that the performers, respectively the chainsaw workers, may have a lower qualification, may have a harder time adapting to work with new machines and technologies, or it is possible that

the implementation of safety and health at work is deficient. At the same time, the age of chainsaw workers can also contribute to the increase of this factor, which is quite high, on average around 52 years.

Figure 2. The proportion of risk factors on the components of the work system

The characteristic factors of the work environment resulting from the calculation for the experimental bases are represented in percentage of 20.00%. Compared to other studies (Iftime, 2020), where a factor of 27.59% was obtained, it can be concluded that within the experimental bases the works are carried out in better conditions for the exposed personnel, the work performed by the chainsaw workers and the working conditions are better and tree felling operations are in less dangerous areas and that do not require intense or great physical effort.

The factors due to the means of production obtained for the experimental bases are in percentage of 35.00%, quite high compared to other researches that obtained 27.59% (Iftime, 2022). This percentage may be due to the use of machines that do not have effective safety systems, are outdated or not properly used. Added to this, there is a weaker professional training of some chainsaw workers resulting in ignorance of the performance of the chainsaw. Related to the factors specific to the workload, they have a percentage of 15.00%, slightly lower than that presented in other studies (17.24%) (Iftime, 2020).

Based on the results obtained following the analysis, some measures can be adopted to reduce the identified risks that are high. To reduce or eliminate the 3 risk factors that are in

the unacceptable range (F1, F10, F14), the measures presented in the Form with the proposed measures are necessary. From the analysis of the Evaluation form, it is found that 25 of the risk factors (62.50%) identified can have irreversible consequences on the performer (disability or death). At the same time, a reduction of the other risk factors is required so that no more work accidents occur.

CONCLUSIONS

In the forestry sector, the work tasks for workers involve a great effort over a long period of time. Also, direct actions on workers' health are produced by environmental factors, bad postures during work and musculoskeletal conditions. For chainsaw workers the most common risks are high noise level, vibration, carbon monoxide exposure and work microclimate.

In order to reduce the risks of injury of chainsaw workers, it is necessary that the medical supervision of their health status to include several types of analyses and additional investigations, especially for workers who already have health problems. It is also required to equip them with high-quality protective equipment to ensure effective protection of workers against occupational risks. Clothing

must be comfortable, lightweight, yet allow the worker to perform their work tasks and provide increased protection at higher cutting speeds of the chainsaw. In order to avoid loud noises, protective audio systems equipped with radio communication systems must be used. Footwear must be moisture resistant and provided with metal protection. Gloves must be worn to limit vibrations.

In addition to wearing protective equipment, communication of any event related to occupational safety and health can be the boundary between life and death (Lesch, 2005). If events are communicated in time, risks and dangers can be reduced or even eliminated, thus avoiding both economic damage and injury to personnel and their capacity.

In our country there is a legal framework that regulates the field of safety and health at work. Among these can be mentioned: (1) Law no. 319/2006 on occupational safety, with subsequent amendments and additions, (2) Government Decision no. 1425/2006, for the approval of the Methodological Norms for the application of the provisions of the Labour Security Law no. 319/2006, with subsequent amendments and additions, and (3) Order no. 3/2007 regarding the approval of the Form for registering work accidents.

The minimum conditions that any entity that carries out activities that involve the use of human labour must comply with are provided in the following documents: (1) Government Decision no. 1091/2006 on minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace; (2) Government Decision no. 1146/2006 regarding the minimum safety and health requirements for the use of work equipment by workers; (3) Government Decision no. 1048/2006 on the minimum safety and health requirements for the use by workers of individual protective equipments at the workplace; (4) Government Decision no. 971/2006 regarding the minimum requirements for safety and/or health signalling at the workplace.

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FOREST EDUCATION PROGRAMMES PROPOSED BY THE NATIONAL FOREST ADMINISTRATION-ROMSILVA IN PARTNERSHIP WITH SPECIALIZED UNIVERSITIES AND OTHER STAKEHOLDERS (NGOS ETC) (PART 3)

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Maintaining and developing a permanent awareness policy of the young generation on the importance and way of sustainable management of forests, is one of the constant efforts that the National Forest Administration (NFA) Romsilva makes over time to ensure their continuity for the future generations.

The paper addresses one of the forestry education programs proposed by NFA-Romsilva, which is aimed especially at secondary school students, following four main themes.

Keywords: forestry education, awareness, sustainable management, forest fund, target group

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INTRODUCTION

The general purpose of this program: promoting the activity of NFA-Romsilva (the only administrator of the state forest fund in Romania) and the role of forestry personnel in ensuring the continuity and sustainable management of the national forest fund.

The activities proposed within the educational programs have a learning, information, skill acquisition, awareness, sensitization and involvement role.

The general objectives of the educational programs consist of: the transmission of information in order to acquire knowledge about the forest and its administration/management; the formation of a proactive attitude towards the forest as an ecosystem and the development of a responsible attitude of the civil society towards the environment; carrying out practical indoor and outdoor activities for setting the knowledge and developing the skills of the target audience; which are the species of flora and fauna that can be found in the forest fund, as well as ways to conserve biodiversity.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to implement these programs, it is necessary to go through the following stages:

the training of the staff within the forestry departments that connect to the target groups related to each educational program; signing partnerships with school inspectorates/schools/children's palaces, museums, local authorities, NGOs, etc.; establishing the topics to be developed.

The work methodology will take into account the following stages: drawing up a calendar of activities; contacting the target group; ensuring the logistics related to the activities; the preparation of the teaching materials (Daia, M., 2003; Hac, P.A., 2010; Nedelcu, G., 2003; Petrescu, D.C., 2009; Popovici, I., 1985; Zotta, M., 2005); indoor and outdoor activities (excursions on thematic routes, guided visits in the field, practical demonstrations, interactive actions, team games, workshops, therapeutic walks in the forest (forest bathing) etc.); involvement in volunteer actions on the ground alongside forestry specialists; monitoring quantifiable results from a quantitative (number of activities, meetings, etc.) as well as qualitative point of view (feed-back questionnaires); disseminating the results in the local media and social networks, as well as allocating a budget at the forestry directorate level in order to implement forestry-educational activities.

The results had in view following the application of this program are: the training of future generations who know general notions about forestry and understand the role of the forest and forester in ensuring the continuity of the forest; promoting the forestry profession and the fact that NFA-Romsilva is a reliable partner.

Below, it is presented in detail one of the educational programs aimed at students in secondary schools (Seghedin, G., 2019).

Name of the program: P3 - Discover the forest universe (presentation of the Romanian

Academy during the International Symposium - Forests and Education. The activity of foresters in the development and protection of forests - means of education in the spirit of respect for the forest, 2019, Bucharest)

Target group: children from secondary schools (V-VIII)

Main competences: learning, information, skill acquisition, awareness, sensitization, involvement, curiosity, practical application of theoretical knowledge, development of civic sense.

Table 1

P3 program - Secondary competences and themes addressed

Secondary competences			
What should the children feel?	What to do?		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - curiosity and interest in the forest; - respect and appreciation for the profession of forester; - the support of the forestry personnel, trust towards the forestry staff; - responsibility towards nature; - appropriate behavior towards the forest, the joy of being in the forest, freedom, harmony, empathy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to spend more time in the forest; - to get involved and participate in forestry-specific voluntary actions, in communication sessions, to plant correctly; - to become a volunteer forester/ranger for a day. <p>What to know?: what is a food web/chain, notions of forest regeneration, forest nursery = seedling reservoir for the forest, the role of the forest in people's lives, what does the forest provide? What is the role of the forester in sustainable forest management, why is it important to ensure the continuity of a forest and how is this achieved? Recognition of the profession (forester, ranger, engineer), notions about protected natural areas, to know the forests in the area etc.</p>		
Allocated time: maximum 50 minutes			
Themes addressed within the P3 program:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the forest? The role and functions of the forest; - Sustainable forest management and the role of the forester in the forest management; - Species of flora and fauna; - Conservation of biodiversity. Virgin forests. Protected species. Natural protected areas. 			
Location	Didactic methods	Suggestion of additional content	Allocated budget
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - county forest administrations; - forest districts; - forest nurseries; - administrations of national and natural parks; - secondary schools; - museums; - cultural and educational centers. 	content analysis, simulation, role play, case study, cooperative learning activities, discussions and debates through the use of interactive methods that can contribute to the practice of teamwork, cooperation and/or competition, to the development of communication skills, to demonstrate the critical, tolerant, open and creative spirit of the students, to involve the students in decision-making exercises, to propose strategies for solving problems in the group they belong to, in the school or in the community etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - activities for the benefit of the community; - worksheets; - additional bibliographic material; - audio-video materials, internet, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - infrastructure NFA-Romsilva; - a budget for the development of educational materials; - budget for travel, transport, meals, the salary of the staff involved, etc.; - the purchase of didactic and promotional materials.
Period	period of the school year, minimum 1 meeting/topic		
Recommendation:	A class of students should go through all the topics to achieve the goal of this program.		

Table 2

Topic 1. Sustainable forest management and the role of the forester in forest management

Specific competences	Abilities	Knowledge	Attitudes
1. Summing up the knowledge about forest	- understanding that the tree is the defining element of the forest as a complex ecosystem; - identification of a stand development stages; - identification of pioneer species.	- the developmental stages of the forest - from seed to exploitable stand; - the application of silvicultural measures for the sustainable management of forests.	- awareness of the fact that the forest is a complex universe with multiple interactions among the component elements; - adopting a responsible attitude towards the forest;
2. Who and how manages the forest?	- understanding the categories of forest managers (state and private); - awareness of the role of the forester in forest management; - understanding the reading of a forest management map and deciphering the conventional signs on the map in the field.	- administration of the forest fund through state and private forest districts; - foresters are a category of specialists and forestry is a science; - forest management = the forester's bible.	- adopting a friendly attitude towards forestry personnel; - awareness of the complexity of the forestry profession and the means necessary for its practice.
3. Role of the forester in each stage of the forest development	- getting familiar with the main types of forestry works.	- the forestry works foreseen in the forest management plans, depending on the age of the forest and its functional category.	- awareness of the complexity and importance of the forester profession as well as of the means necessary for its practice.
4. Harvesting of forest products (wood and non-wood)	- understanding the various types of forest products; - identification of marked trees; - identification of a felling area; - recognition of the field indices regarding the cleaning of the felling areas, the delimitation of access roads, warning panels; - places to collect forest fruits, medicinal plants.	- forest signs and markings, tools for marking; - notions related to the exploitation ages, an ABC of care works and treatments, exploitation technologies and equipment and soil protection measures.	- the development of a responsible attitude towards: foresters and other adjacent professional categories (planners, etc.).
5. What happens after the wood is harvested? Methods of forest regeneration: natural, artificial and mixed	- identification of a natural/artificial/mixed regeneration; - understanding the types of works to help natural regenerations and care for plantations; - identification of forest species by different types of fruits and seeds; - understanding how to produce forest saplings.	- wood harvesting - part of the forest regeneration process; - natural regeneration from seeds, shoots or suckers; - artificial regeneration: sowing, planting or propagation; - support of natural regeneration and maintenance works in the plantations; - knowledge of several types of fruits and seeds; - knowledge of the methods of producing seedlings in the nursery.	- the development of a positive attitude towards the forester's activity regarding the continuity of the forest.
Examples of activities			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Practical training/field trips to observe different aspects, for example: stands/forest of different ages, afforestation, plantations, natural forest regeneration, limits and symbols used in the field. 2. The management plan for a Production Unit as a tool for awareness and understanding of the works in a forest. 3. Example of a marking hammer, what a mark on the tree looks like, where it is located etc. 4. Evaluation of forest products and benefits, responsible consumption of forest resources. 5. Field trips to a forestry nursery. 			
<i>It is recommended to present curiosities from nature, legends and stories for each topic addressed in order to capture the children's attention.</i>			

Table 3

Topic 2: That is the forest? The role and functions of the forest

Specific competences	Abilities	Knowledge	Attitudes
1. What is the forest?	- differentiation of abiotic and biotic factors specific to the forest ecosystem (biotope and biocenosis); - understanding the principles according to which the forest ecosystem works.	- the forest is the living environment for various types of microorganisms, plants and animals; - geological, hydrological, pedological, climatic factors.	- adopting a positive attitude aimed at knowing the forest as an element of the ecosystem.
2. What is a forest made of?	- identification of some categories of forest plants and animals; - knowledge of the relationships established between living things and their living environment.	-forest flora and fauna; - the composition of the stands; - knowledge of the structure of the forest, the layers of vegetation (trees, shrubs, grassy soil cover).	- developing a positive attitude towards the flora and fauna of the forest.
3. The tree, the defining element of the forest	- the analysis of a basic cross section through the trunk of a tree (bark, sapwood, heartwood, pith, annual rings); -determining the age of a tree (annual growth rings); - measuring the height of a tree (height measuring instruments).	- knowledge of the wood structure through a cross section of the tree; -differences among wood essences; - knowledge of the main species of trees.	- awareness of the structural differences of wood, correlated with its various uses; - awareness of the role of the forester in the promotion of species with economic utility.
4. Forest resources and functions	- identification of wood and non-wood products of the forest; - knowledge of forest functions.	- the forest - renewable natural resource; - recognition of fruits from different species (of trees, plants), mushrooms, medicinal plants; - the functions of the forest (production and protection – balance between the two functions).	- the use of renewable natural resources for economic and social needs; - conservation of natural resources; - awareness and appreciation of the food and therapeutic value of non-wood forest products.
5. Distribution of forests at national level	-identification of different forest types (according to its layers and vegetation zones).	- knowledge of the different types of forest within the national forest fund.	- awareness of the correlations between environmental conditions and forest type.
6. Main dangers that threaten forests today	-identification of the main dangers that threaten forests today and ways to reduce or eliminate them.	- knowledge of the main dangers that threaten forests today and methods of reducing or eliminating them.	-becoming responsible as regards the indications of the presence of some dangers; - behaviors responsible for maintaining the natural balance of the forest; -adopting a responsible attitude towards the forest.
<p>Examples of activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presentation of a forest model (including animals, species). 2. Boards with the vertical structure of the stand: trees, shrubs, grassy soil cover. 3. Field trips, forest exploration activities (students discover in teams what the forest is made of, differences between deciduous and coniferous trees, what is a layer of vegetation, the distribution of forests in the world, workshops). 4. Listening to the sounds of the forest (sounds of animals, birds). 5. Using tools to measure the diameter, age and height of a tree, compass and map. 6. Human intervention – changes in the forest generated by human activities. <p><i>It is recommended to present curiosities from nature, legends and stories for each topic addressed in order to capture the children's attention.</i></p>			

Table 4

Topic 3: Species of flora and fauna			
Specific competences	Abilities	Knowledge	Attitudes
1. Wood and non-wood forest flora species	-identification of some species of trees, shrubs, herbaceous flora, mushrooms, mosses, lichens; -morphological differences at the level of leaves, buds, rhytidom/bark.	- knowledge of the main tree species in the country's forests; - flora in the forest (the characteristics of the flora determine the type of forest and the stand); - species of edible mushrooms vs. inedible; - species of medicinal plants from the forest.	- awakening interest in species identification methods; - developing a positive attitude towards forest fauna.
2. Species of animals/fauna in the forest	-identification of some species of animals/fauna in the forest; - morphological differences (anatomical peculiarities, traces, excrement); - determining the specific habitat for rodents, birds, small and large mammals etc.	- knowledge of the main fauna species in the forest by various categories (birds, mammals, fish).	- developing a positive attitude towards forest fauna; - arousing interest in species identification methods.
3. Food web and species relationships	- knowledge of natural balance; - identification of the links between species – producers, consumers, decomposers.	- the natural balance; - knowledge of trophic relationships/trophic pyramid; - silvicultural measures are applied in order to preserve the natural balance.	- the habit of not destroying the natural balance of plants and animals; - awareness of the importance and role of each species in its natural habitat.
4. The influence of environmental factors on the development and spread of organisms	- understanding the environmental factors that influence the biocenosis (e.g. drought, floods, use of chemical fertilizers in areas adjacent to the forest, noise pollution etc.); - awareness of the rights and obligations of the population over the flora and fauna in the forests (visiting routes, rules of behaviour).	- knowledge of the interdependencies between the environmental factors and the elements of the biocenosis; - listing the rights and obligations of communities/civil society in relation to the forest.	- appreciation of the correct human behavior in the relationship with the forest; - the analysis of the interdependence between the manifestation of personal rights and wishes and compliance the environment.
5. Rare protected/exotic plant species and animals. Their protection.	- identification of rare/protected/endemic/exotic plant and animal species and their location in the county; - awareness of the disappearance of rare/endemic species and the danger of invasion by other fast-growing species or with low economic value.	- information about the existence of lists of rare, endangered, vulnerable and endemic species; - informing about the current trends in the promotion of some species unsuitable for climatic and seasonal conditions.	- the ability to care for and protect plants and animals protected by law; - raising awareness related to maintaining the appropriate composition of the natural fundamental types of forest.
<p>Examples of activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Field trip in the field, in a forest or a park with the purpose of carrying out some practical activities. 2. Creation of sheets with the most common species of flora and fauna, and signs of the presence of fauna species. Age-appropriate determiners will be use. 3. Making games about species discovery. Competitions with prizes for the determination of species. 4. Making the food web game; food web sheets. 5. Highlighting sustainable behaviors in the relationship between man and nature through play. <p><i>It is recommended as the activities to have a practical part where the students, in teams, have direct experiences.</i> <i>It is recommended to present curiosities from nature, legends and stories for each topic addressed in order to capture the children's attention.</i></p>			

Table 5

Topic 4. Preservation of biodiversity (virgin forests, protected species and protected natural areas)

Specific competences	Abilities	Knowledge	Attitudes
1. What is biodiversity? Importance of nature/forest ecosystem conservation.	- understanding the environment suitable for the life of plants and animals; - understanding the interdependence of organisms and the consequences of the disappearance of some species.	- knowledge of the living environment of plants and animals; - awareness of the importance of biodiversity for continuous evolution, for the stability of the food chain and for human society.	- developing a responsible attitude towards the forest.
2. What are virgin forests? Why is it important to keep them?	- criteria and indicators for identifying virgin forests and their importance; - highlighting the differences between a cultivated forest and a virgin/quasi-virgin forest.	- knowledge of the characteristics of virgin and quasi-virgin forests; - the study of the ecosystem developed in natural conditions, without human intervention, can serve as a model for establishing optimal forest management solutions.	- developing a responsible attitude towards the virgin/quasi-virgin forest.
3. What are protected areas and what role do protected species play?	- awareness of the disasters that can be triggered by destroying the natural balance; - understanding the notion of protected natural areas, of a protected, rare species etc.- elementary notions - why we need protected natural areas	- knowing the natural balance; - knowledge of the classification of protected natural areas; - knowing the benefits of protected natural areas.	- learning not to destroy the natural balance of plants and animals; - learning not to destroy the protected plants and animals; - developing a responsible behavior towards nature in general and towards the forest in particular (including material recycling).
4. What are the nearest protected areas in the area?	- identification of the nearest protected areas; - identification of national and natural parks in Romania.	- knowledge of the protected areas in the area; - mention of the national and natural parks in Romania; - for the analyzed area, exemplification of some endangered plant and animal species.	- developing a responsible attitude towards the forest, observing and understanding nature.
5. Rules of behavior in a protected area and in general in the forest. Ecotourism	- learning the rules of behavior in a protected area and in the forest; - practicing responsible and forest-friendly tourism.	- knowledge of the rules of behavior in a protected area and in general in the forest.	
<p>Examples of activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Field trip in a protected area (the closest). It is recommended to invite some persons from the management team of a protected area. Use of a map with protected areas in Romania. Where possible, visiting a natural or national park in the area. Presentation of videos about protected areas. Plant and animal species. <p><i>It is recommended as the activities to have a practical part where the students, in teams, have direct experiences.</i> <i>It is recommended to present curiosities from nature, legends and stories for each topic addressed in order to capture the children's attention.</i></p>			

CONCLUSIONS

In the implementation of the themes presented above, an increased interest of the children in acquiring new knowledge in the forestry field was found, showing active involvement and showing an overflowing curiosity. Therefore, it has been proven that the educational program described above, addressed to the target group - secondary school students - has a positive impact in acquiring a long-term forestry awareness among the young generation, NFA-Romsilva demonstrating and wanting to maintain a permanent and transparent communication with all the factors interested in the implementation and development of these educational programs initiated by her.

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NEW PERSPECTIVES IN DEFINITION, CLASSIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION OF MOBILE SOIL PROTECTION APPLICATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Nowadays, almost all fields of activity are based on the use of information technologies and various devices (more or less mobile) with related applications. Soil monitoring and protection activities are no exception. Thus, both IT devices and systems and related mobile applications are of real interest in the development of sustainable and precision agriculture, as well as the development of the community as a whole. As such, through this paper, starting from classical computer systems, we aimed to define and classify, in association with them, both systems and mobile applications for monitoring and protection of soils. A new typology of mobile systems and applications with implications for soil monitoring and protection has resulted in these conditions, which can be agreed upon by the academic community and those with concerns in the field. Consequently, we should also adjust the community's perception of the implications of information systems, e-learning, and m-learning in Community agricultural practice and policies.

Keywords: soil protection, computer systems, mobile learning, dedicated mobile applications.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, almost all fields of activity are based on the use, to a greater or lesser extent, of information technology and various computing devices with related applications. Thus, the use of means and tools specific to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in carrying out various activities and making decisions has become ubiquitous (Cioruța et. al, 2018; Mesaroș et. al, 2018).

The availability of computers, in terms of cost and use, has allowed a steady evolution of Environmental Information Systems (EISs) and Environmental Informatics (EI), with the constant need to develop increasingly complex working tools compatible with the requirements of various environmental phenomena (Cioruța and Coman, 2011a).

Areas of activity related to soil protection are no exception. Thus, of real interest both for the general public and for the entities with concerns in the field, the classic computer systems have been replaced by EISs, the latter becoming more and more sought after and handy to use (Cioruța and Coman, 2011b; Cioruța et. al, 2013), as they provided an answer to the environmental problems as they need solutions appropriate to our days.

From applications and platforms that indicate in real-time the weather in a certain area to dedicated software that establishes various alternatives to work scenarios in terms of community-environment relationship, we are talking about a diversified range of EISs (Cioruța and Coman, 2019-2021). All are based on the configuration, structure, and properties of classical computer systems, facilitating

through the use of new technologies the intimate, direct, and immediate approach to user information (Cioruța et. al, 2012-2014).

Starting from the field situation, EISs end up acquiring, processing, storing, and disseminating data to serve the interests of users (more or less specialized) and the community. Thus, in this paper, we set out to discuss EISs (which include mobile applications dedicated to soil protection), thus trying, in relation to classical computer systems to define and classify them.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The first step in structuring our research was to consult the literature, where we identified numerous references to the definition and characterization of SIM (Avouris and Page, 1995; Hilty et al., 1995; Gunter, 1998; Cioruța and Coman, 2011a; Cioruța and Coman, 2012). In parallel with the information obtained, and by reference to classical computer systems, we defined and classified mobile applications for soil protection. Both the definition, especially the classification of mobile applications dedicated to soil protection, were milestones for us, given that in the literature we failed to identify such an approach.

In response, we analyzed and synthesized a series of subjective aspects, which naturally also found adequate graphic landmarks as we claim (Cioruța and Coman, 2021); in the first instance it includes the typology of the classification of mobile applications (see Fig. 1), to later emphasize the scope and reporting of information obtained from the field (see Fig. 2), and the role of applications in relation to the status and responsibilities of users (see Fig. 3).

For all three graphics, we referred to SmartArt graphics, trying to keep the explanations and details to a minimum. In fact, in order to remain consistent in reporting to computer systems, we also resorted to shortening the typology of mobile applications, thus facilitating the perception of readers and users on them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In general, EISs work with data that captures the attributes of the environment from which it was extracted. Data taken from the environment represent quantitative or qualitative attributes of a variable or set of variables (Cioruța and Coman, 2014; Cioruța and Coman, 2019); these are the result of measurements and can form the basis for the

creation of field observation sheets, graphs, and maps, or other forms of representation on the issues under investigation.

In order to become environmental information, the data subject to research must be processed in accordance with the requirements of the user and those imposed by the research (Hreniuc et. al, 2019); this involves collecting data from various sources, namely processing and distributing the results of processing to the user. Consequently, the objective of data processing is to convert environmental data into environmental information that underpins decisions.

The main differences between data and information are that data are primary attributes collected from various places, undefined or unorganized in a form that underpins decisions, while information is messages obtained through data processing, they must be concise, current, complete, and clear, so as to meet the demands of the research.

Today, environmental data is processed automatically, using electronic automatic processing equipment, also known as Automatic Data Processing Systems (ADPS). EISs, which include to some extent the ADPSs, as well as mobile applications with implications for soil protection, under the generic term of Soil Data Processing Systems (SDPSs), are classified according to several criteria (Kamran et. Al., 2016), so:

- 1) Depending on the field of use, computer applications may be:
 - a. for the management of economic and social activities in relation to land use and soil protection;
 - b. for the management of technological processes in relation to land use and soil protection;
 - c. for scientific research, technological design, and innovation in relation to soil protection.
- 2) Depending on the element under analysis, we are dealing with:
 - a. computer systems aimed at obtaining data and generating information and knowledge;
 - b. object-oriented computer systems;
 - c. function-oriented computer systems;
 - d. process-oriented computer systems.
- 3) According to the way of organizing the data with reference to the ground, we have:
 - a. file-based computer systems;

- b. computer systems based on hierarchical, network, relational, or object-oriented databases;
 - c. mixed computer systems.
- 4) According to the method used in the design of mobile applications dedicated to soil protection, we have:
- a. applications developed according to the systems method;
 - b. applications developed according to the classical life cycle method;
 - c. applications developed according to the structured method;
 - d. applications developed according to the object-oriented method;
 - e. applications developed by the fast method (RAD);
 - f. applications developed according to the mixed team's method;
 - g. applications developed according to the prototype method.

Figure 1. The first 6 classifications criteria for Soil Data Processing Systems (SDPSs)

Figure 2. The Soil Data Processing Systems (SDPSs) classification by data coverage area

- 5) According to the degree of centralization of the functionalities, we have:
- a. centralized applications/systems;
 - b. decentralized applications / systems.
- 6) According to the degree of dispersion of the computer system resources involved in the acquisition, processing, storage, and dissemination of data, we have:
- a. Local computer applications or systems (based on local area network, workstations);
 - b. Distributed computer applications or systems (distributed data).
- Because information on the protection of soil resources is needed both to answer critical questions on a global scale and to provide the global context for local decisions, a classification by centralized data and information is also required. Thus, in the 7th category, depending on the area of data and information that it centralizes, we have:
- a. Local Soil Information Systems (LSISs) aims to develop a spatial data infrastructure that brings together

soil data and information collected individually by entities;

- b. National Soil Information Systems (NSISs) aims to develop a spatial data infrastructure that brings together soil data and information collected by several different LSISs;
- c. Regional Soil Information Systems (RSISs) aims to develop a spatial data infrastructure that brings together soil data and information collected by several different NSISs;
- d. Global Soil Information Systems (GSISs) aims to develop a spatial data infrastructure that brings together soil data and information collected by several different NSISs and/or RSISs.

The latter systems (GSISs) are designed as a federation of information systems, which share interoperable data sets about the ground via web services. This approach empowers countries to develop their SPDSs as reference centers for soil information.

In fact, most entities that process information related to soil protection use up to 5 different SPDSs, each with functionalities that help manage a particular organizational unit. This is how SPDSs helps each department

manage and organize all of its data in a way that helps unit members achieve key objectives. If the data collected by an SPDSs is relevant and accurate, the organization may use it to streamline tasks, identify inefficiencies, and improve services for customers and/or users with concerns about land protection or land use. The use of all 5 SPDSs allows a company to maintain a competitive advantage, find growth opportunities and maintain an accurate audit trail of traded data and information. Below, we present an overview of the 5 SPDSs, their role, and how they work, thus delimiting the 8th category:

- a. Office Automation Systems (OASs) are a network of tools, technologies, and resources needed to perform office processing tasks. maintaining a calendar of activities and generating reports.

First of all, an office automation system helps to improve communication between different departments so that everyone can work together to complete a task. By using an office automation system, entities concerned with soil protection can improve communication between employees, streamline activities, and optimize the management of soil data and information.

Figure 3. The Soil Data Processing Systems (SDPSs) classification by system functionality

- b. Information Management Systems (IMS) store and retrieve information to help users improve their knowledge and optimize collaborative efforts to complete tasks.

These systems provide intuitive access to external information required by workers who need external knowledge to perform their roles.

- c. Knowledge Management Systems (SMCs) use transaction information, retrieve information, aggregate it, and

generate reports to help management know important situation details.

Summaries and comparisons are used to enable senior managers to optimize their decision-making process for better results.

- d. Decision Support Systems (DSSs) process information to help make decisions. Decision templates are programmed to analyze and summarize large amounts of information and put them into a picture that makes them easy to understand.

This provides the evidence needed for the average management to make the right choices to ensure that the company meets its objectives for the protection of soil resources, for example.

- e. Executive Support Systems (SSE) are similar to DSSs but are used by executives and owners to optimize decision-making.

Such systems help those interested to find answers to unusual questions so that they can make choices that improve the company's perspective and performance in relation to soil protection. Unlike a DSS, an executive support system offers better telecommunications functionality and greater computing functionality.

CONCLUSIONS

Environmental Information Systems, as well as mobile applications for soil protection, are tools that are gaining new value in the acquisition, processing, storage, and dissemination of information. I made a series of observations on them and made a review of a new typology.

The latter is shaped by the field of use, the element under analysis, the way data is organized, the method used in designing mobile applications, the degree of centralization of functionality, and the degree of dispersion of computer system resources. The typology is also completed with classification according to the area of coverage of the data and information they centralize, respectively according to the role and the way in which the applications themselves work.

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THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH SEDIMENT PARTICLES IN BIHOR COUNTY BETWEEN 2019 AND 2021

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Abstract

This paper studies the level of air pollution with sediment particles in the Bihor County area, between 2019 and 2021. The data used for this work were provided by the Environmental Protection Agency of Bihor Oradea. This agency deals with the monitoring of air pollution with sediment particles in Bihor County.

In Bihor County there are located 10 sampling points of sediment particles, strategically divided. Four sampling points are located in the industrial area around Aleșd, two sampling stations are located in Oradea (A.P.M. Headquarters and Meteorological Station), and the other 3 points are located in the industrial area of Oradea (Episcopia Bihor, Biharia, Sălard) and a sampling point in Băile 1 Mai.

Through these located points we can have a real image of the pollution with sediment particles in Bihor County, being able to take concrete measures in cases of pollution with sediment powders.

From the study carried out, it can be concluded that at Telechiu in 2021, the month of April was determined a concentration of 17,550 g/m², the maximum permissible concentration being exceeded (17 g/m²/month).

Keywords: maximum permissible concentration, monitoring, sampling points, sediment particles.

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INTRODUCTION

Air pollution with sediment particles is a very important problem, they are materials in the form of particles that can be solid or liquid. The particles have different forms such as: particles, smoke, soot, nitrates, asbestos, pesticides, bioaerosols. Sediment particles have an irritating action on the airways, and their specific action is related to their chemical composition, which can be toxic, fibrosing and allergenic (Pereș, 2011). In many cases these particles are of an anthropogenic nature by burning biomass, industrial processes, as well as road traffic. But they can be natural such as volcanic eruptions, sand and dust storms, natural fires of vegetation or forest (Köteles, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this study we used data from the Environmental Protection Agency of Bihor Oradea. This institution supervises the level of air pollution in Bihor County, through the 10 harvesting points (www.apmbh.ro). The harvesting points are: Telechiu, Chistag, Aleșd, Țețchea, Băile 1 Mai, Meteorological Station, A.P.M. Bihor, Biharia, Sălard and Episcopia Bihor (Köteles & Pereș, 2021). The analysis of the level of pollution with sediment particles

was carried out over a period of three years (2019, 2020, 2021) (Köteles & Pereș, 2019). The maximum permissible concentration for sediment particles is 17 g/m²/month (monthly harvesting frequency) (STAS 12574/1987, Order 592/25.06.2002).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Annual evolution of sediment particles

Following the analysis of sediment particles concentrations, for 2019 it was observed that the highest concentration was determined in Chistag with a value of 8.747 g/m². A close value was also recorded in Sălard of 8.114 g/m² and in Episcopia Bihor of 7.049 g/m². Cele mai mici valori sau înregistrat în Oradea la APM Bihor cu o valoare de 4.043 g/m² și la Stația Meteorologică de 4.171 g/m².

In 2020, the highest concentration was determined in Telechiu by 7.492 g/m², followed by Țețchea with a value of 7.261 g/m² and 7.172 g/m² measured in Episcopia Bihor. The lowest values were determined in Băile 1 Mai (3.679 g/m²), followed by Aleșd (4.116 g/m²). The reduced value was also determined in Oradea at APM Bihor (4.563 g/m²)

For 2021, the highest level of pollution with sediment particles was determined in Țețchea with a value of 9.748 g/m², followed by

Episcopia Bihor with 8.334 g/m² and Chistag 7.782 g/m².

From the evolution of the average concentrations for the years 2019 – 2021 it results that the maximum permissible concentration has not been exceeded (Figure 1).

Figure 1 The evolution of sediment particles average concentrations in Bihor county, 2019 – 2021

Following the analysis of the average of the three years taken into account, it results that the highest concentration was determined in Chistag being 8.403 g/m², followed by the Episcopia Bihor with a value of 7.518 g/m² and Țețchea with 7.493 g/m². Low values were recorded at the sampling points in Aleșd (4.241 g/m²), APM Oradea (4.260 g/m²) and Oradea Meteorological Station (4.421 g/m²) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Evolution of the multiannual average concentrations (2019 – 2021) of sediment particles at the 10 monitoring points in Bihor county

2. Monthly evolution of sediment particles

Following the analysis of the 10 sampling points, the highest average concentration for 2019 is recorded in May, 7.928 g/m², followed by July with a value of 7.106 g/m² and June of 7.030 g/m². In the case of 2020, the highest values were determined in January (8.353 g/m²), July (7.707 g/m²) and June (7.604 g/m²).

For 2021 the highest concentration was determined in July of 7.991 g/m², close values were determined and in September 7.754 g/m² and may 7.573 g/m², (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Monthly pattern of sediment particles in Bihor county (the average of the 10 sampling points)

In the analysis of the monthly evolution, for the three years studied from 2019 to 2021, the highest average was determined in July being 7.601 g/m², followed by 7.358 g/m² in May, and in June by 6.891 g/m².

The lowest concentrations following the analysis of the lunar evolution over the years studied were 4.439 g/m² in February, 4.562 g/m² in December and 4.916 g/m² in April (Figure 4).

Figure 4 The evolution of multiannual monthly average concentrations of sediment particles in Bihor (the average of the 10 sampling points)

3. Evolution of pollution by sediment particles at sampling points

At the monitoring point in Telechiu, for 2019 the highest concentration was recorded in July of 12.120 g/m², of 11.520 g/m² in June and 10.090 g/m² in March.

In 2020, the highest values were determined in January 16.310 g/m², in June 12.310 g/m², followed by November 11.250 g/m² (Figure 5).

The highest values for 2021 were recorded in April 17.550 g/m², when the maximum permissible concentration of sediment particles was exceeded, high values were also determined in September 16.880 g/m².

Figure 5. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point Telechiu

At the sampling point in Chistag for 2019, the highest measured value in July was 15.250 g/m², followed by June 13.49 g/m².

In 2020 the highest values were in January 16.120 g/m² and July 11.760 g/m². The highest value in 2021 was determined in September at 15.340 g/m²

Figure 6. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point Chistag

At the sampling point in Țețchea the highest value for 2019 was determined in March (11.490 g/m²), and in 2020 the highest value was 15.850 g/m². In 2021, the highest value was recorded in February of 15.980 g/m² (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point Țețchea

The highest value for the sampling station at The Meteorological Station Oradea was determined in January of 13.760 g/m² in 2020, followed by July in 2019 a value of 10.000 g/m² (Figure 8).

Fig.8. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point Meteorological Station Oradea

At the APM Bihor Oradea headquarters, the highest value of sediment particles was determined in August 2021 of 7.2700 g/m², followed by 6.790 g/m² in October 2019 (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point APM Bihor Oradea

The highest values recorded at the sampling station in Sălard, was determined in 2019, in May, a value of 16.320 g/m², followed by January 2020 of 15.820 g/m² (Figure 10).

Fig.10. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at sampling point Sălard

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the average of the 10 sampling points for the years 2019 - 2021 shows that the pollution level does not reach the maximum permissible concentration which is 17 g/m²/month.

However, from the analysis of each sampling point, we can see that in Telechiu locality the threshold of 17 g/m²/month, was exceeded in 2021, the month of April being of 17,550 g/m².

In the localities of Telechiu, Chistag, Aleşd and Țețchea, in the Aleşd industrial area, there is a more pronounced pollution, but it does not exceed the maximum permissible concentration, only in the case of accidents or weather conditions that favor the deposition of sediment particles and the lack of precipitation.

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FREQUENCY OF HAZARDOUS CLIMATIC PHENOMENA IN THE COLD SEASON OF THE YEAR IN THE AREA OF ORADEA, BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The research of long term climatic elements variation and, implicitly, of hazardous climatic phenomena are basic issues of climatology and this study focuses on them. Adverse weather conditions show great spatio-temporal variations, they can be dangerous and can seriously inflict all socio-economic sectors.

In our country, and implicitly in Oradea, due to the temperate continental climate with oceanic influences the most frequent hazardous climatic phenomena of the year's cold season are: hoarfrost, black ice, frost, snow gust, blizzard. This study was carried out using a rich amount of weather data recorded at the Oradea weather station over a long period of time, that is, 1970-2021.

Keywords: black ice, blizzard, frost, hoarfrost, snow gust.

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INTRODUCTION

One of the works on the climatic hazards of some phenomena in the area of Oradea is *Climatic Hazards in the Crișuri Hydrographic Basin*, in which Cristea, 2004, provides a study of climatic hazards in this area. In the paper *The Evolution Trend and the Probability of Frost in the Crișurilor Plain*, Dragotă, 1995, provides a study of frost.

Regional studies dealing with the area of Oradea have also been carried out by Dumiter, 2007, who provides a climatic monograph of Oradea. In the paper *The Climate and Air Pollution in the Crișul Repede Hidrographic Basin*, Moza, 2009, also includes aspects of the hazardous climatic phenomena, and in the paper *Aspects Related to the Risk Weather Phenomena from the Cold Season of the Year in Oradea Area*, Pereș, 2011, presents the hazardous phenomena in the area of Oradea.

The aim of this study is to analyse the aspects of climatic hazards in the area of Oradea, that is, we have tried to provide an analysis of their evolution, as well as of the factors which determine or generate them. The influence of the various physical-geographical conditions on the hazardous climatic phenomena in the area of Oradea was

highlighted along with that of the active surface structure, as well as the fact that Oradea is located at the contact point of low hills and plains climatic floors, being under the influence of the European continent's western and south-western climatic conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to present the aspects of climatic hazards in the area of Oradea, the data recorded at the Oradea weather station between 1970 and 2021 were used.

The analysis of hazardous climatic phenomena was carried out using data recorded in weather observation tables at the weather station included in the study. These data are kept in the archive of The National Meteorological Administration (A.N.M.) Bucharest. The study covered a period of 52 years.

The A.N.M. archive data were processed using statistical and mathematical methods. The results obtained were then graphed in order to clearly show the variation in time of hazardous climatic phenomena.

The purpose of using methods and means specific to climate research was to ensure an as

precise as possible processing of all data we had at our disposal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Hoarfrost

In certain weather conditions hoarfrost can become a climatic hazard due to the intensity of its coldness. Thus, it can occur in the transitional seasons, when cold air advections from the north alternate with warm air from the south (Mähăra, 2001).

The importance of studying this hydrometeor is given by the fact that late hoarfrost in spring and early in autumn has a negative effect on agriculture, which results in significant damage.

The multiannual average of hoarfrosty days in Oradea is 49.7 days/year, with variations between 17 days in 2010 and 93 days in 1998 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Annual variation of hoarfrosty days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

In some years, the number of hoarfrosty days was above the multiannual average, while in others it was below it. Thus, in 50% of the years included in the study there were fewer hoarfrosty days than the multiannual average, while in 50% of the years the deviation was positive (Figure 2).

Looking at the positive and negative deviations against the multiannual average, it can be seen that in the first half of the period included in the study, 1970-1989, the deviations were either negative or positive, which was followed by a period, 1991-2001, with only positive deviations. Between 2002 and 2008 there were both positive and negative deviations against the multiannual average (49.7).

Figure 2. Deviations of the annual numbers of hoarfrosty days from the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

In the last period, 2009-2021, the annual number of hoarfrosty days decreased and except for 2015 and 2020, when the deviations were positive, in the other years they were negative (Figure 2).

During the year, hoarfrost occurs between September and May. The highest numbers of hoarfrosty days are recorded in the winter months, with the highest number of days in January, when the average of such days is 10, followed by December, with an average of 9.4 hoarfrosty days. (Figure 3).

In February, the multiannual average of hoarfrosty days is 8.9, while in November and March there are approximately 8 such days (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Multiannual monthly averages of hoarfrosty days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

The lowest numbers of hoarfrosty days occur in the transition months, that is, the months which begin and close the cold season, with 0.1 and 0.2 days in May and in September respectively. Thus, the highest number of hoarfrost days are recorded in the winter months, when thermal inversions occur frequently, and the lower numbers in spring and autumn.

Black Ice

In the area of Oradea the multiannual average of black ice days is low, 2.8 days/year. This low figure is due to climatic influences from the west and south-west of the continent, which are rather strong in this part of the country.

In the 52 years included in the study the highest number of black ice days was recorded in 2002, when there were 13 such days altogether, 7 in December and 6 in January.

There were some years with no black ice at all, 1975, 1979, 1983, 1990, 1991, 1995, 2000, 2001, 2004, 2015, 2016, 2018 and 2020 (Figure 4), which means a frequency of 25% of the total number years included in the study.

Figure 4. Annual variation of black ice days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Figure 5. Deviations of the annual numbers of black

ice days from the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Looking at the deviations of the annual numbers of black ice days against the multiannual average, it can be seen that the positive deviations make up 48.1% (25 years), while the frequency of the negative ones is 51.9% (27 years) (Figure 5).

In the area of the study black ice occurs from November to March. The month with the highest multiannual average of black ice days is January, 1.4 days/month.

In December, the average is 0.8 days/month, while the lowest number of such days are recorded in the month at the end of the period when this phenomenon occurs, that is, March, when the average is 0.1 days, as well as in the month at the beginning of the period when it may occur, that is, November, 0.2 days.

The highest occurrence probability of this phenomenon is in January, when the highest frequency of black ice days is recorded, that is, 50.3%. In December the frequency of black ice days is 28.7%. The lowest frequency and, thus, the lowest probability of the occurrence of this phenomenon is in March, with 2.1% (Table 1).

Table 1
Multiannual and monthly averages, monthly and multiannual totals and percentages of monthly values of black ice days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Month	I	II	III	XI	XII	Multiannual
Average	1.4	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.8	2.8
Total	72	18	3	9	41	143
Frequency (%)	50.3	12.6	2.1	6.3	28.7	100

Source: ANM Archives

The month with the highest number of black ice days was January 1982, when there were 10 such days, followed by December 2002, when there were 7 days.

Frost

The multiannual average of frosty days in Oradea is 7.9 days/year, but there were rather significant variations from one year to the other.

Figure 6. Annual variation of frosty days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Thus, in 1977, 1986 and 2003 the highest number of such days was recorded, 19 days,

while in 2002, 2004, 2007 and 2012 this phenomenon did not occur at all (Figure 6).

The years with positive deviations from the multiannual average make up 46.2% of the total number of years, while the years with negative deviations 53.8% accordingly (Figure 7). It can be seen that in the last period of the study the annual number of frosty days was lower, except for the years 2003, 2011, 2016, 2017 and 2020, which means a low frequency of this phenomenon between 2002 and 2021 and there were even four years when it did not occur at all (2002, 2004, 2007, 2012).

Figure 7. Deviations of the annual numbers of frosty days from the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Frost occurs in Oradea between November and March. The month with the highest multiannual average of frosty days is January, 3.3 days, followed by December with 2.8 days. In the months at the end of autumn and at the beginning spring the phenomenon

occurs rarely, the averages are 0.4 days and 0.2 days respectively.

Advection of cold and wet arctic maritime air masses leads to a high frequency of frosty days in the cold period of the year. The hydrometer can also appear at the contact point of two air masses of Mediterranean origin with different thermal characteristics, one warm and the other dry. In the contact zone of the two air masses fog occurs along with frost and this is an often present phenomenon in the area of Oradea in the cold period of the year.

The highest probability occurrence of this phenomenon is in January, the month when the highest number of frosty days were recorded (173 days), which means a frequency of 42.1% of the total number of such days. The lowest probability of this phenomenon to occur is in March, when there were only 8 such days in the period included in the study and that means a frequency of 1.9% (Table 2).

The month with the highest number of frosty days was December 1986, when there were 16 days with appropriate conditions for this phenomenon to occur. In January the highest number of frosty days was recorded in 2020, 14 days altogether. In March and November the highest number of frosty days were 2 and 4 respectively.

Table 2

Multiannual and monthly averages, monthly and multiannual totals and percentages of monthly values of frosty days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

Month	I	II	III	XI	XII	Multiannual
Average	3.3	1.3	0.2	0.4	2.8	7.9
Total	173	65	8	20	145	411
Frequency (%)	42.1	15.8	1.9	4.9	35.3	100

Source: A.N.M. Archives

Snow gust

The multiannual average of snow gust days in Oradea is 2.7 days.

In the period included in the study (1970-2021) the highest numbers of snow gust days were recorded in 1985, 2003 and 2005, 11 days in each year.

Figure 8. Annual variation of snow gust days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

There were 17 years in which this hydrometer did not occur, in 1972, 1974, 1978, 1990, 1994, 1997, 1998, 2007, 2008, 2011, 2013, 2014, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2020 and 2021,

and they make up 32.7% of the total number of years included in the study (Figure 8).

The variation in time of snow gust days shows that there were more years with negative deviations from the multiannual average, they made up 59.6% of the total number of years, while the positive deviations made up 40.4% (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Deviations of the annual numbers of snow gust days from the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

During the year snow gust occurs between November and March. The highest values are recorded in January because this is the month with the greatest snow depth. Thus, in January the multiannual average was 1 day and the highest number, 7 days, occurred in 2003. In February, the highest number of snow gust days was 5 days, in 1985, and the multiannual average of this month was 0.8 days. The highest number of snow gust for December was 4 days, in 1973, 1980 and 2005, the average for this month being 0.6 days.

Figure 10. Multiannual monthly averages of snow gust days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

The lowest values are recorded in the month at the end of the snowy period, that is, in March, as well as in the month when the snow starts to fall, in November, when the multiannual average of the months is 0.1 days (Figure 10).

Blizzard

In the area of Oradea the frequency of blizzards is low. The multiannual average of this phenomenon is 1.0 day and it can occur between November and February.

The low number of blizzard days in Oradea is the result of the characteristics of the atmospheric dynamics in this part of the country, which shows the weak influence of the eastern and north-eastern European continent climate which generates such phenomena.

In the period included in the study (1970 – 2021) the highest annual number of blizzard days occurred in 1987, when 7 such days were recorded, all of them in January. It is worth mentioning that in Oradea in 30 years (57.7%) from the 52 years included in the study blizzard did not occur at all (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Annual variation of blizzard days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

The annual numbers of blizzard years fluctuated around the multiannual average, the negative deviations made up 57.7% of the total number of years, while the positive ones 21.2%, and in 21.2% of the years there were no deviations from the average (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Deviations of the annual numbers of blizzard days from the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

During the year, the highest multiannual averages of blizzard days are recorded in January and February, 0.4 days in each case. Both in November and December the multiannual average was 0.1 days (Figure 13). The highest number of blizzard days was recorded in January 1987, when 7 such days occurred, followed by February 1999, with 4 days.

Figure 13. Multiannual monthly averages of blizzardy days in Oradea, 1970 – 2021

CONCLUSIONS

The most frequent hazardous climatic phenomenon is hoarfrost, which in certain conditions can become a climatic hazard due to the intensity of its coldness, the moment in the year when it occurs and due to its consequences. In the period included in the study the multiannual average of hoarfrosty days is 49.7 days/year. This phenomenon can occur between September and May, with highest values in the winter month (9 – 10 days), when thermal inversions occur.

Ice becomes a hazardous climatic phenomenon both when it covers the ground (it hampers or even prevents transport) and when it coats wires or tree branches, which can break.

Snow gust and blizzard are not too frequent due to a weak influence of the eastern and north-eastern European continent climate which generates such phenomena.

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THE RAINY AND DROUGHT YEARS OF THE PERIOD 1961-2021, IN ORADEA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

To highlight the rainy, normal and drought years at the Oradea meteorological station, the annual amounts of precipitation were analyzed for the period 1961-2021 (61 years), using the method of Standardized Precipitation Anomaly (SPA). The method highlighted the positive and negative annual anomalies of precipitation. Later, based on the percentile method, the intervals of climatic risk associated with the excess or deficit of precipitation were established. The decennial amounts of precipitation were also analyzed, as well as the polynomial and linear trend of the annual SPA values. The result was that in Oradea, during the period 1961-2021, the annual amounts of precipitation showed a slight increase. The rainiest decade was the 5th (2001-2010), and the driest decade was the 6th (2011-2020). Most of the extremely dry/rainy years occurred in the 1990-2021 interval, which coincides with the increase in the frequency of climatic extremes in recent years, reported at the planetary level. Using the percentile method, 9 intervals of pluviometric risk were established. Thus, the very high risk generated by excess can occur from annual SPA values higher than +1.56 and annual amounts of precipitation over 800 mm. The very high risk generated by deficit can occur from annual SPA values lower than -1.35 and annual amounts of precipitation below 450 mm. The interval without risk is represented by annual SPA values between -0.29 and +0.15 and annual amounts of precipitation between 578 and 630 mm.

Keywords: standardized precipitation anomaly; precipitation excess; precipitation deficit; climate risk; trend.

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INTRODUCTION

Oradea City is the residence of Bihor County and is located in western Romania, along the Crișul Repede River. The city is located in the contact region of the Crișurilor Plain with the Piedmont Hills of Oradea. The Hills of Oradea, with altitudes of about 300 m, are situated in the north-east of the city, part of the city's hearth being located on these hills. The Crișurilor Plain stretches to the west, north-west and south, being characterized by its smooth relief. The Oradea-Bratca Depression opens to the east, drained by the Crișul Repede River. It falls into the category of "gulf-depressions", which are typical of the western limit of the Apuseni Mountains (Pop, 2000, 2005; Posea, 1997; Șerban, 2010).

The climate of Oradea City is temperate-continental, with predominant oceanic influences, typical of north-western Romania (Bogdan & Niculescu, 1999).

In recent years, due to the global warming of the earth's atmosphere, the rains fall more and more unevenly during the year. Thus, the heavy rains falling in short intervals of time, which cause the precipitation excess, but also the droughts are increasingly intense and frequent. This situation also occurs in the territory of Oradea City and the surrounding agricultural lands. These phenomena have negative effects on agriculture, forestry, underground and surface water reserves, electricity production, etc., in a word on the local economy. The increasingly intense humidity excess and droughts represent increasing risks for the population, but also for biodiversity.

The study of these two phenomena – drought and humidity excess – has been done for a long time, being among the most studied climatic phenomena. Thus, in Romania they were studied starting with C. Donciu, N. Topor, continuing with O. Bogdan, C. Dragotă and many others, until the recent studies of different

authors. Among the more recent studies of the foreign authors, we list those of Apurv et al. (2017), Luo et al. (2017), Dai & Zhao (2017), Mukherjee et al. (2018), Christian et al. (2021), Naumann et al. (2021) and so on.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the present paper, the meteorological data related to the annual amounts of precipitation were used, from the Oradea meteorological station, for the period 1961-2021 (61 years).

The Oradea weather station is located at an altitude of 137 m, having the code 15080 and the following geographic coordinates: 47°02' N latitude, 21°53' E longitude. It is situated in the south-west of the city, in open land covered with cultivated vegetation, near the Oradea-Arad road and the Oradea airport (Șerban, 2010).

To highlight the rainy, normal and drought years at the Oradea meteorological station, the annual amounts of precipitation were analyzed using *the method of Standardized Precipitation Anomaly (SPA)*.

By means of this method of calculation, positive and negative annual precipitation anomalies are highlighted. Based on them, intervals of climatic risk associated with the excess or deficit of precipitation can be established.

The annual standardized precipitation anomalies were calculated with the following formula (Busuioc, 1992):

$$SPA = (x - \bar{x}) / \sigma \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

where:

\bar{x} - the multiannual average amount of precipitation;

x - the amount of precipitation of a particular year;

σ - the standard deviation (average quadratic deviation) of the annual amount of precipitation;

n - the length of the data set.

The analysis of precipitation using the SPA method is often found in the specialized literature, the authors assigning different pluviometric ratings to the years/months, from "exceptionally rainy" to "exceptionally dry". The thresholds chosen between the classes of values differ from one author to another (Kutiél & Paz, 1998, Maheras et al., 1999, Păltineanu et al., 2000, Dumitrașcu et al., 2002, quoted by

Cheval & Dragne, 2003; Holobăcă, 2010; etc.). As a result, for a better highlighting of the risk intervals, *the percentile method* was used to establish the thresholds between the pluviometric ratings, a method considered more efficient (Busuioc, personal communication; Șerban et al., 2008; Șerban, 2010, 2015, 2016; Șerban & Dragotă, 2014; etc.). The method is based on the ascending ordering of the n values from a data set and dividing them into a number of k equal parts (n/k) (Țarcă, 1998, quoted by Dragotă et al., 2003).

Thus, 10 classes of values were established for the annual SPA. For example, the SPA values of the 90-100% class represented the "extremely rainy" years and the interval of very high risk generated by surplus, and the values of the 0-10% class, the "extremely dry" years and the interval of very high risk generated by deficit. The SPA values of the 40-50% and 50-60% classes represented the "normal" years and the risk-free interval.

All the meteorological data used in the paper came from the database of the National Meteorological Administration of Romania and from the website www.meteomanz.com.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The annual amounts of precipitation

At the Oradea meteorological station, the multiannual average amount of precipitation was **612.7 mm**, in the period 1961-2021.

The multiannual average precipitation value is slightly higher than at other meteorological stations in the Crișurilor Plain, due to the positioning of the Oradea station at the contact of the plain with the hills, where the oceanic air masses, coming from western Europe, rich in moisture, are forced to escalate the landforms. This forced upward movement contributes to the intensification of cloudiness and, therefore, to the increase of precipitation amounts on the slopes exposed to the advections of air masses.

During the period 1961-2021, the annual amounts of precipitation oscillated between 364.2 mm (in the year 2000) and 884.0 mm (in the year 1996) (Figure 1). The highest amounts of precipitation exceeded 750 mm. There are 8 years with more than 750 mm of precipitation. These are the rainiest years, when the cyclonic activity persisted. Five of them recorded very high amounts, over 800 mm. Most of these years were reported in the period 1996-2010.

The lowest annual amounts of precipitation were ≤ 450 mm. There are 6 years with amounts ≤ 450 mm. These are the driest years, when the anticyclonic activity predominated. Most of them were reported in the period 1990-2021. Only one year recorded a value below 400 mm. It is the year 2000, which stands out for its very low value compared to the values of the other years.

It should be noted that *both the rainiest years and the driest years occurred in the second half of the analyzed period, i.e. in 1990-2021.*

Figure 1 also shows the linear trend of the annual precipitation amounts. During the period 1961-2021, precipitation showed a slight

increase in Oradea. The upward trend is due to the higher values since 1996. The cause lies in the increase in air temperature in recent decades, which has amplified the thermal convection.

The decennial amounts of precipitation

In order to highlight the distribution of precipitation over the 6 decades of the analyzed period, the annual amounts were averaged over each decade. The maximum and minimum annual amount from each decade was also extracted (Figure 2).

Figure 1 The annual amounts of precipitation and their linear trend, at the Oradea meteorological station (1961-2021)

Figure 2 The average, the maximum and the minimum of the annual precipitation amounts for the six decades of the period 1961-2020, at the Oradea meteorological station

The result was that the rainiest decade was the 5th (D5), followed by D4 and D2, and the driest decade was the 6th (D6). The 5th decade (2001–2010) recorded an annual average precipitation amount of 659.1 mm, and the 6th decade (2011–2020), an average amount of 586.6 mm. The 3rd decade (1981-1990) was also dry, having an annual average of 588.7 mm.

Overall, there is a trend of increasing annual average amounts in the first 5 decades and a decrease in them towards the last decade. Thus, *the annual precipitation increased from D1 to D5 by 52.9 mm and decreased from D5 to D6 by 72.5 mm.* It is also noteworthy that after the rainiest decade, the driest decade followed. Both occurred at the end of the analyzed period, showing once again the unevenness of rainfall in recent years.

Regarding the maximum and minimum annual amounts from each decade, it is noted

that the 4th decade (1991-2000) recorded both the highest and the lowest annual amount of precipitation.

The annual pluviometric anomalies

Using the percentile method, it was possible to establish the classes of values and the pluviometric ratings of the years of the period 1961-2021, in Oradea (Table 1).

The positive precipitation anomalies of the 90-100% class are between +1.56 and +2.26, and the negative ones of the 0-10% class are between -1.35 and -2.07 (Table 2). It is observed that the positive anomalies reached higher values than the negative ones, a sign that the rainfall surplus of the rainiest years from the period 1961-2021 was more intense than the rainfall deficit of the driest years, in Oradea.

Table 1

Rainy, normal and drought years recorded at the Oradea meteorological station (1961-2021)

STATION/ YEARS	Extremely rainy	Very rainy	Rainy	Moderately rainy	Normal
Oradea	1996	1998	2017	2007	1968
	2010	1980	1997	2006	1985
	1999	1966	1981	1995	1988
	2001	2004	1970	1982	1969
	1974	2016	1987	2018	1977
	1978	1965	2005	1991	2009
					2014
STATION/ YEARS	Extremely dry	Very dry	Dry	Moderately dry	
Oradea	2000	1973	1993	2008	2013
	2011	1983	1975	1962	2020
	1961	2012	1967	1972	1963
	1990	2019	1979	1986	1984
	1992	1971	2002	1964	1989
	2021	2003	1994	2015	1976

Table 2

The extremely rainy/dry years, the SPA values and the annual precipitation amounts corresponding to those years, at the Oradea meteorological station (1961-2021)

YEARS	Year	SPA value	Precipitation amount (mm)
Extremely rainy	1996	+2.26	884.0
	2010	+2.20	876.9
	1999	+2.14	869.7
	2001	+1.74	821.8
	1974	+1.56	800.6
	1978	+1.56	799.7
YEARS	Year	SPA value	Precipitation amount (mm)
Extremely dry	2000	-2.07	364.2
	2011	-1.62	418.1
	1961	-1.52	430.4
	1990	-1.43	440.3
	1992	-1.36	449.0
	2021	-1.35	450.8

As specified above, the rainiest year was **1996**, and the driest was **2000**. Most of the extreme years occurred in the 1990-2021

interval. The year 2000 was an extremely dry year throughout the country, with major negative effects on the national economy. In

Oradea, it was preceded and followed by two extremely rainy years: 1999 and 2001. Moreover, it is included in a period of very rainy years (1996-2001). The extremely rainy year 2010 was followed by the extremely dry year 2011. The analyzed period starts and ends with two extremely dry years: 1961 and 2021.

As in the case of the Timișoara meteorological station, it is also observed at the Oradea station that, *in general, the extremely dry years occurred at an interval of about 10-11 years, which coincides with the solar activity cycle* (Șerban & Dragotă, 2014).

Table 3 shows the intervals of pluviometric risk due to excess, pluviometric risk due to deficit, respectively the intervals without risk from the Oradea station. They were obtained using the same method of percentiles. For each risk interval, the classes of SPA values and the annual amounts of precipitation between which that risk is reported can be observed.

Thus, the very high risk generated by excess can occur from annual SPA values higher than +1.56. These values correspond to annual amounts of precipitation over 800 mm. The high risk generated by excess can occur at annual SPA values between +0.95 and +1.55 and annual amounts of precipitation between 726 and 799 mm. Similarly, very high risk generated by deficit can occur from annual SPA values lower than -1.35. They correspond to annual amounts of precipitation below 450 mm. The high risk generated by deficit can occur at annual SPA values between -0.92 and -1.34 and annual amounts of precipitation between 451 and 502 mm. The interval without risk is represented by annual SPA values between -0.29 and +0.15 and annual amounts of precipitation between 578 and 630 mm.

Figure 3 shows the years with positive and negative precipitation anomalies, as well as the periods of consecutive surplus or deficit years.

Table 3

The intervals of pluviometric risk at the Oradea meteorological station (1961-2021)				
RISK BY EXCESS	Very high risk	High risk	Moderate risk	Low risk
SPA value	+1.56 – +2.26	+0.95 – +1.55	+0.36 – +0.94	+0.16 – +0.35
Annual amount of precipitation (mm)	800 – 884	726 – 799	656 – 725	631 – 655
RISK BY DEFICIT	Very high risk	High risk	Moderate risk	Low risk
SPA value	-1.35 – -2.07	-0.92 – -1.34	-0.67 – -0.91	-0.30 – -0.66
Annual amount of precipitation (mm)	364 – 450	451 – 502	503 – 532	533 – 577
WITHOUT RISK	Without risk			
SPA value	-0.29 – +0.15			
Annual amount of precipitation (mm)	578 – 630			

Figure 3 The linear and polynomial trend of the annual SPA values, at the Oradea meteorological station (1961-2021)

The longest period of consecutive surplus years (1995-1999) is equal in length to the longest period of consecutive deficit years (2011-2015): 5 years. But the surplus period is much more intense than the deficit period. On the other hand, the periods of consecutive deficit years have a higher frequency (10 periods) than the surplus ones (8 periods).

The polynomial trend of the annual SPA values (Figure 3) shows that, after the drought of the years 1961-1964, there follows a long surplus period of 18 years (1965-1982), then a deficit one of 12 years (1983-1994), a long rainy period of 16 years (1995-2010), followed by a deficit period of 11 years (2011-2021). In the long rainy period 1995-2010, the great drought of the year 2000 can be found.

Normally, if this rainfall distribution will be maintained in the future, as the year 2022 had a large rainfall deficit in Oradea, it would mean that starting from the following years, we would enter a long period of rainfall surplus.

The linear trend of the annual SPA values (Figure 3) is slightly *upward*, for the period 1961-2021. This trend is due to the high SPA values of the last surplus period.

CONCLUSIONS

During the period 1961-2021, the annual amounts of precipitation showed a slight increase in Oradea. The upward trend is due to the higher values since 1996. The cause lies in the increase in air temperature in recent decades, which has amplified the thermal convection and therefore the cloudiness, generating richer rainfalls in favorable synoptic situations, with Atlantic or Mediterranean circulation. Also, through the expansion of the city, the "heat island" effect generated by the built surfaces, overheated in the summer and which amplifies the thermal convection, has been amplified.

The rainiest year was 1996, and the driest was 2000.

The rainiest decade was the 5th (2001-2010), and the driest decade was the 6th (2011-2020). The annual average precipitation amounts increased from the 1st decade to the 5th decade by 52.9 mm and decreased from the 5th decade to the 6th decade by 72.5 mm.

Most of the extremely dry/rainy years occurred in the 1990-2021 interval, which coincides with the increase in the frequency of climatic extremes in recent years, reported at the planetary level.

In general, the extremely dry years occurred at an interval of about 10-11 years, which coincides with the solar activity cycle.

Using the percentile method, 9 intervals of pluviometric risk were established, in Oradea. Thus, the very high risk generated by excess can occur from annual SPA values higher than +1.56 and annual amounts of precipitation over 800 mm. The very high risk generated by deficit can occur from annual SPA values lower than -1.35 and annual amounts of precipitation below 450 mm.

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THE FUTURE OF INDUSTRIAL SITES OF ORADEA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The present work addresses a current phenomenon: the desire to recapture industrial urban areas, most of which are in decline or abandonment. It is about the city of Oradea in Romania, which is part of today's European space, but with traces of the past. The authors deal with the industrial sites of the past, still present in fact or in the memory of the inhabitants. At the same time, the work highlights the attitude of the inhabitants of the city of Oradea, analyzing the results of a questionnaire launched to them. The subject of the questionnaire is several industrial sites from 1900 onwards, as well as the vision of the population from different areas of the city regarding their perspective. The majority's option coagulates towards various ways of reusing and preserving the memory of industrial sites and their buildings, contrary to the current reality, a striking phenomenon, of erasing them.

Keywords: heritage site, urban, sustainable development, tabula rasa.

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INTRODUCTION

The city of Oradea, located in a geographically favorable area and at the intersection of important trade routes, has always had a strategic geographic, historical and economic position vis-à-vis the west and center of Europe. This aspect has influenced the development of the city in the past as well as in the present. Oradea is a city that developed radially with the Oradea Citadel as "0 point".

The city took shape during the Transylvanian Voivodeship period, in the Medieval Era, when this area entered a stage of much greater development due to the pilgrimage of the faithful.

In the pre-industrial era, the 18th century, craft occupations gradually took the place of agrarian ones. "It is obvious that in this century and a half of the city's history, Oradea has become an economic-craftsmanship and commercial center - if not of the first size, like Cluj or Braşov, at least one of considerable importance" (Borcea & Gorun, 1995).

In 1850 the population of the four cities (Oradea - "Olosig"/ Oradea - "Oraşul Nou"/ Oradea - "Subcetate"/ Oradea - "Velenta") was 18,904 souls (Hungarians, Germans, Romanians, Jews). A purely political unification took place under the same mayor, but the neighborhoods also retain their own administration and well-

defined identity. "Subcetate" and "Orasul Nou" continue their expansion

A first decisive period, the peak of economic development, is around the years 1880 - 1920. "As a relevant indication of the degree of industrialization, in 1892 26 factories operated in Oradea, among which the most important were related to the food industry and beverage manufacturing, construction materials industry, chemical industry, machinery, machinery and equipment industry. Some of them satisfied the requirements of agriculture, such as the mills." (Fleisz, 2010).

A second period of rapid, even forced, development is around the 1940s.

"The urbanization of Oradea was particularly dynamic. Appreciating this period as a whole, she represented for Oradea the period of peace, "la belle époque" (Fleisz, 2010). Thus, in the last decade of the 19th century, there was a boom in the construction of public institution buildings (the archbishopric school, the new town hall, the slaughterhouse, the water plant, the barracks, the cadet school), roads and bridges (two metal bridges over the "Crişul Repede" river), market facilities (place for fairs). The population is growing. A densification of the urban fabric is noticeable (Fig.1.).

Figure 1. Oradea între 1869 – 1887

source: <https://mapire.eu/en/map> (accessed in 04.12.2022)

At the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, the construction of the Oradea palaces is accelerated, street lighting is introduced, three tram lines are introduced. The transition from classicism to romanticism is made, eclectic influences make their presence felt, and secession takes off in Oradea. The city is still a strong industrial and especially commercial core. It is the Jews who catalyze industry and commerce. This active nucleus is characterized in the interwar period by 8 important industrial categories: the food industry (the most important and characterized especially by the factories of yeast, spirit and alcoholic beverages, milling and baking, sweets and meat processing); chemical industry; the textile one; followed by the printing industry; construction materials industry; that of metallurgy and machine construction; of leather and footwear; forestry and wood processing industry. The development of the industry went hand in hand with the establishment of banking and credit institutions and with flourishing commerce. The economic situation and cultural life in the period 1919-1940 is marked by regression. On the political level, major changes are occurring. After the nationalization of factories, workshops and houses in 1948, five-year plans were introduced. After 1945, in Oradea, units of several industrial branches merged. The chemical industry (after 1948) is concentrated in two factories: "Transilvania", a varnish and paint factory, and "Sinteza", a chemical products factory. The metalworking workshops first become "Phoebus", and after nationalization "Înfrățirea". The state

intervenes by rescuing abandoned enterprises. Since 1962, the industrial area on the western platform of the city has been developing at an overwhelming pace: the Sugar Factory, the "Alfa" Furniture Factory, "UAMT" Oradea, "Alumina" Oradea, "Sinteza" Oradea... This was finally made up of twelve units. The intensive development of the industry leads to an increase in the number of inhabitants and implicitly in the housing capacity. The first blocks appear. Thus compared to 1948, when the number of inhabitants of Oradea was approximately 87,000, there are data that claim that in 1989 - 229,823 inhabitants lived here (Borcea & Gorun, 1995). Rapid urbanization is taking place, a lot is being built. The first draft of the systematization of Oradea appears in 1960, then another in 1970, another in 1976, the latter targeting a city with 1,560,000 inhabitants and 2,787 hectares. The revolution of December 1989 brings great changes in political and economic terms. After the revolution, investments and activity cease, but various programs forgotten during the communist period are reactivated: churches, social-cultural buildings, individual housing and what concerns privatization. The industries disappear one by one, the western industrial platform of Oradea is abandoned. It invests in industrial parks.

The object of this study is several industrial objectives and their historical and urban route towards a sustainable development: "Emilia" Mill, "Rovex" area, "Adria" area, Sugar Factory, "Înfrățirea" Factory.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The authors extracted from the studied documents / references / interviews with witnesses data about the establishment of the industrial sites that are the subject of the study. At the same time, he visited the locations by carrying out photo surveys, used the personal archives of the interviewed witnesses as well as data from the digitized press or found in the archives. Regarding the site development projects, the authors collected data from the competent institutions: Oradea City Hall and the project approval commissions: Municipal Commission for Urban Planning and Spatial Development and Zonal Commission of Historical Monuments. Thus, data were obtained regarding the evolution over time of the five sites, contained in table no. 1:

In order to know the opinion of the society and extract information about the way of perception of the evolution of industrial sites by the inhabitants of the city of Oradea, the authors developed a set of questions focused on the notion of heritage and industrial site, focusing on several sites of interest.

A Google Forms type form was created and distributed online to the residents of the municipality of Oradea. In order to complete it, the respondents had access for one week to the web page from 23.02.2023. The data were processed with the help of two software, the one provided by Google (in the body of Google Forms) and the statistical data processing software SPSS 24.

The questions target not only the respondents' knowledge, but also an emotional component - how they relate to some landmarks of past times. The results are based on the response of 448 people from different backgrounds and age groups between 18 and 75 years, and their processing was done together with an expert in statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the context of the evolution of the industrial sites of the city of Oradea, the data collected for the five sites were processed: "Emilia" Mill, "Rovex" area, "Adria" area, Sugar Factory, "Înfrățirea" Factory, these being included in table no. 1.

Table 1

Attitudes over time towards former industrial premises (data processing by the author)

Industrial objective / site	Year of construction	Approach - year	Site currently 2023	Project stage
"Emilia" Mill	1884-1885 (Emödi, 2011)	<i>Tabula rasa</i> / Total demolition in 2014 Proposals in principle - residential complex / 2021-2022	Vacant land On hold 10 years ago	ATP* rejected by the commission ZCHM**, design in progress
"Adria" Distillery	1915 (Emödi, 2020)	Partial conversion and construction of new bodies, Masterplan – mixed assembly, consultation phase 2020	On hold	ATP phase consultation in the ZCHM and MCUPSD, design in progress
"Rovex" Factory	1870 (Pafka, 2019)	Partial conversion and construction of new bodies / PUD approved in 2021 for the restructuring of the former Rovex premises, Partial demolition in 2023	Site in progress	Site in progress
"Înfrățirea" Factory	1904 1949 (https://www.ebihoreanul.ro)	<i>Tabula rasa</i> / Totally demolished between 2017-2021, Area Town Planning approved in 2016 for building collective housing, Area Town Planning modifier approved in 2019	Partially residential area 1,500 apartments, Prima – Premium Decebal neighborhood, Ioșia Nord, Ared, site in progress	Completion of construction works
Sugar Factory	1968 (https://www.ebihoreanul.ro)	<i>Tabula rasa</i> / Proposal for demolition in 2018, Total demolition between 2020-2021	Vacant land	Real estate development project - design in progress

*ATP - Area Town Planning

**ZCHM - Zonal Commission of Historical Monuments

***MCUPSD - Municipal Commission for Urban Planning and Spatial Development

As it follows from it, three of the studied sites had a "tabula rasa" treatment, so there is only the memory of the place. Figures 2 and 3 (results by modeling images from Google Earth) are given as examples:

Figure 2. Interventions over time on the premises – "Emilia" Mill (Emódi, 2011)

Development projects are underway on two of the studied sites, in which their buildings are partially maintained, while the the General Urban Plan of the city of Oradea allows a wide variety of functions, especially in the sphere of housing, administrative functions, tourism,

cultural and educational functions on the plots of former industrial premises in the heart of the settlement. Figures 3 show the present location of "Rovex" and presents a development proposal, which is currently not approved.

Figure 3. Rovex existing and proposal (Planwerk, 2020)

Following the distributed questionnaire, it appears that a significant number of people did not address the subject of industrial heritage in educational institutions, during the years of study (figure 4). However, comparing the graphs - interpretation of the answers received to questions, aimed at the appreciation of the industrial heritage, it is found that the majority strongly agrees with valuing it. The questionnaire offers the possibility of expression regarding methods of approach to these premises and buildings, considered suitable. The majority appreciates that the industrial heritage should be reused (figure 5, table 2). If the respondent chose REUSE, they were asked to present what new functions they would propose for these constructions. The answers are presented in figure 6, in the order

of the most common nominations. Table 2 includes only the sites of the "Emilia" Mill, the "Adria" Distillery, the "Rovex" Factory and the Sugar Factory, the site of the "Infrățirea" factory being completely demolished and occupied with

a residential complex (residential blocks and shopping centers).

Figure 4. **Industrial heritage - subject of study in education** (data processing by the author), (Prada, 2022)

Figure 5. **Industrial heritage - subject of study in education** (data processing by the author) (Prada, 2022)

Figure 6. **Functions proposed for the conversion of former industrial buildings in Oradea** (data processing by the author) (Prada, 2022)

Table 2

Opinions of the population regarding the image of former industrial sites in Oradea (Prada, 2022)

Pictures of former industrial buildings (some disappeared)	Opinions of the population for the industrial site ...
<ul data-bbox="1118 353 1430 533" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reuse ● Conservation ● Demolition to make way for new investments ● Left to decay naturally 	
<ul data-bbox="1118 705 1430 884" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reuse ● Conservation ● Demolition to make way for new investments ● Left to decay naturally 	
<ul data-bbox="1118 1059 1430 1238" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reuse ● Conservation ● Demolition to make way for new investments ● Left to decay naturally 	
<ul data-bbox="1118 1431 1430 1610" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reuse ● Conservation ● Demolition to make way for new investments ● Left to decay naturally 	

Another important result of the questionnaire is that most of the respondents would work near such a building/industrial site or even live nearby. One of the most valuable results of the questionnaire: asked if this questionnaire had awakened their interest in the subject, 52.8% answered positively, and 35.8% understood better what industrial heritage means. The industrial heritage is a material tool that helps people to remember their past (Prada, 2019).

CONCLUSIONS

It can be seen that each project outlines a separate identity, supported and ultimately promoted by communities, private investors and the municipality.

In the case of the "Emilia" mill, 75% of the people who answered the questionnaire did not know that it was demolished 10 years ago.

The questionnaire can become a tool and a method of learning and education.

Most respondents understand the value of buildings in terms of the potential they offer – potential for reuse.

There are 3 groups of functions that the inhabitants of Oradea would consider necessary and suitable for these types of structures and premises (most of them located in the heart of the city): cultural functions, offices and social functions - gathering places.

These considerations can be the basis of the decisions of the project approval commissions and of the authorities in the elaboration of the sustainable development strategy of the respective city for intervention on the former industrial sites. At the same time, they can be a starting point in the decision-making management of real estate developers.

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